

GO-FORWARD

G EOTHERMAL EXPLORATION AND O PTIMIZATION THROUGH F ORWARD MODELLING AND RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

Deliverable 5.1: Current state of the societal readiness level in the tested countries

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Authors	Roman Seidl, Claude Baltensperger, Eszter Körtvély, Kristina Koch, Matthias Holenstein

No.	Short	Participant Organization Name	Country
1	F-IEG	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FÖRDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV	DE
2	GEUS	GEOLOGICAL SURVEY OF DENMARK AND GREENLAND	DK
3	TNO	NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO	NL
4	GSA	GEOSPHERE AUSTRIA – BUNDESANSTALT FÜR GEOLOGIE, GEOPHYSIK, KLIMATOLOGIE UND METEOROLOGIE	AT
5	ICGC	INSTITUT CARTOGRAFIC I GEOLOGIC DE CATALUNYA	SP
6	UNIBA	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI BARI ALDO MORO	IT
7	UNIVIE	UNIVERSITÄT WIEN	AT
8	DTU	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DK
9	EVN	EVN WÄRME GMBH	AT
10	SGE	SWISS GEO ENERGY SA	CH
11	SRD	STIFTUNG RISIKO-DIALOG	CH
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List of Abbreviations

ADEME	Agence de l'environnement et de la maîtrise de l'énergie
ARPAT	Agenzia Regionale per la Protezione Ambientale della Toscana
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières
CCUS	Carbon capture and storage
CfD	Contracts for Difference
CoCEn	Politique énergétique et Conception cantonale de l'énergie
CoSviG	Consorzio per lo Sviluppo delle Aree Geotermiche
DEA	Danish Energy Agency
DTU	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet
EABG	Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Beschleunigungsgesetz
EBN	Energie Beheer Nederland
EGS	Enhanced Geothermal Systems
ESRI	Environmental Systems Research Institute
EU	European Union
EVN	Energieversorgung Niederösterreich
F-IEG	Fraunhofer Research Institution for Energy Infrastructures and Geotechnologies
GE	Geothermal Energy
GEL	Geothermal Engineering Ltd.
GEUS	Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland
GSA	GeoSphere Austria
ICGC	Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya
IGME	Instituto Geológico y Minero de España
InvKG	Investitionsgesetz Kohleregionen
MW	Megawatt
MWth	Megawatt thermal
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NPO	Nonprofit organization
NRW	North Rhine-Westphalia
PRSU	Surface research permit
PRTR	Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan
RNES	National Economic Affairs Subsidies Regulation
SDE	Subsidie duurzame energie
SED	Swiss Seismological Service
SEL	Societal Embeddedness level
SFOE	Swiss Federal Office of Energy SFOE
SGE	Swiss Geo Energy
SRD	Stiftung Risiko-Dialog (Risk-Dialogue Foundation)
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TRUDI	Transformation Unterstützung durch Reallabore zur Dekarbonisierung der Infrastruktur
UDDGP	United Downs Deep Geothermal Power
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
UNIBA	Università degli studi di Bari Aldo Moro
UNIVIE	Universität Wien
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

1.1 Challenges of geothermal energy exploration

More geothermal energy (GE) is needed for stable baseload renewable energy/heat supply and seasonal heat storage. Because of the high up-front investments in drilling and the risk of failure, non-invasive early exploration methods are important to minimize the uncertainty of geological conditions while reducing exploration costs. However, the limited availability of subsurface data hinders the development of the geothermal industry's ability to identify and focus on the most promising sites, e.g., in terms of probability of success or lowest risk for seismicity.

In addition to geological and technological risks, political and economic conditions vary from country to country and within a country from one administrative level to another (national, regional, local). Moreover, the societal acceptability of a technology whose details are unknown to most non-experts requires trust in experts and trust in decision-making bodies (Siegrist, 2021, Seidl et al., 2022).

This report presents the results of an extended desk study that includes data on all 14 cases in nine countries that were studied in the GO-Forward project. The research question reads as follows: “What is the current state of the societal embeddedness level (SEL) of deep GE technologies in each of the 14 cases in nine countries that are studied in GO-Forward?”

1.2 The societal embeddedness of and readiness for geothermal energy

Societal acceptance is a decisive factor in geothermal project success, so understanding community attitudes is critical in exploration. Surveys confirm that public perception strongly affects project feasibility; communities tend to welcome geothermal development if environmental and safety issues are addressed properly (Balzan-Alzate et al., 2021; Renoth et al., 2023). Reflecting this, EU and national policies emphasize stakeholder engagement: many countries have set national geothermal targets and roadmaps, and the EU urges Member States to raise public awareness and involve local communities to build acceptance of geothermal projects (Council of the European Union, 2024). In practice, this means directing exploration and development toward areas where geothermal use is environmentally sustainable and supported both socially and economically.

GO-Forward addresses the public awareness of geothermal developments from the early stages of exploration. By incorporating innovative approaches to citizen engagement and stakeholder dialog, it aims to increase the level of societal readiness for geothermal exploration, which serves as the first step in geothermal development. The variability of challenges at different scales and societal levels is reflected in the desk study of the cases reported in this document. The case areas on which the GO-Forward project focuses were addressed in terms of the general situation of geothermal activities in their respective countries. By applying the Societal Embeddedness Level approach (SEL, see Sprenkeling et al., 2022, as well as Mendrinós et al., 2022, Garcia, 2023, but also Büscher & Cronshaw, 2022) to structure the analysis, we address the general consideration of GE activities in the exploration endeavors proposed by GO-Forward (2023) in four dimensions (environment, stakeholders, policy/regulation, market/financing, confer Table 1) with the question of how well GE is integrated into a country’s society (e.g., the respective country’s energy strategy). In addition, a regional/local acceptance assessment was considered by zooming in on the specific projects and highlighting their challenges regarding the four dimensions (see Table 2).

Table 1: The levels of societal embeddedness with description and in relation to Technology Readiness Level (TRL). Source: Sprenkeling et al., 2022.

Technology Readiness Level	Societal embeddedness	Description
TRL 1 – 3	SEL 1	Exploration: explore the social aspects, possible impact
TRL 4 – 6	SEL 2	Development: assess societal aspects
TRL 7 – 8	SEL 3	Demonstration: integrate societal needs
TRL 9	SEL 4	Deployment: prove innovation in societal context

Figure 1 illustrates the different special scales of analysis and which respective frameworks can be applied. For example, the SEL framework focuses on the national level, whereas the Societal Readiness Framework (SRL, see Bernstein et al., 2022) examines the regional and local contexts, aligning with the Technology Readiness Level framework (TRL, see, for example, Sauser et al., 2006, Bruno et al., 2020). The SRL framework is particularly relevant for specific projects and is expected to assume greater significance in future tasks of WP5, particularly when at least two cases are selected for further analysis (see section 4.4). Subsequently, the emphasis will shift to the preliminary exploratory phase, encompassing the modeling approach being developed in GO-Forward. Accordingly, the technology under discussion in D5.1 pertains to the field of (hydrothermal) GE in general, and the subsequent focus will shift toward the realm of early exploration through the application of advanced modeling techniques.

Table 2: The four dimensions in the light of societal embeddedness. Source: adapted from Sprenkeling et al. (2022).

Dimension	Description
Aspects related to <i>environmental</i> impact	The siting of the technology, its physical characteristics, its impact on the natural, built or social environment and the risks associated with the technology and its use.
Aspects related to the public and <i>stakeholders</i>	Public perception/societal acceptance, stakeholder communication and engagement, equity, concern and uncertainty about risks, place attachment and trust, siting of a technology or project, physical characteristics, impacts on the natural, built or social environment, and risks associated with technology and its deployment.
Aspects related to <i>policy</i> and <i>regulations</i>	Interaction with levels of government, government alignment, public funding, political support, understanding the political landscape and regulatory framework.
Aspects related to (financial) <i>resources</i> and <i>market</i>	Funding (public and private), resources, costs and market base (strong or weak).

Consequently, it appeared rational to integrate the two approaches of SRL and SEL (as suggested also by O'Brien et al., 2024), as Deliverable 5.1 addresses the comprehensive incorporation of GE into a nation's existing systems, employing the SEL framework, while subsequent phases involve a shift towards a more case-specific approach at the local level, where the target questions of the SRL can be applied (these are not explicitly displayed in this report to avoid confusion, but see Bernstein et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Scales of case analysis, from national to local. Further details in the main text. Source: Own visualization. TRL = technology readiness level; SRL = societal readiness level; SEL = societal embeddedness level.

As this report demonstrates, substantial variations exist between the case areas with regards to the stage of implementation, ranging from exploration phases to the successful operation of demonstration plants. Concurrently, the social dimension can exhibit variability, with high degrees of acceptance in some instances and low acceptance in others. The report's conclusion section offers a comprehensive overview of the multifaceted challenges confronting geothermal projects across various dimensions. It is not possible to conclude that any particular approach will lead to political, environmental, economic, and social success. However, some conclusions can be drawn from this analysis. The overarching objective is to provide insights into how societal aspects must be considered to ensure that the procedure is perceived as sound by stakeholders and the public.

It is important to note that the selection of the case study areas was based on geological criteria, rather than on political boundaries (such as national borders) that are evident on the surface. The references for chapters 1 and 2 are listed at the end of the document, while the case specific references are listed at the end of the case descriptions in chapter 3.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data collection workflow (survey, desk study, expert feedback)

This report investigates the current state of the Societal Embeddedness Level (SEL) of deep GE technologies across 14 selected regions in nine European countries. The research aims to capture a qualitative and comparative snapshot of stakeholder perspectives, with a focus on understanding how GE technologies are perceived, discussed, and institutionally integrated in terms of both regulatory and market-level incorporation. Importantly, although the original SEL framework was designed as a quantitative tool for ranking technologies across four dimensions and four levels (1–4), we refrain here from assigning explicit numerical values to our assessments (cf. Figure 1). This indicates a cautious approach to categorization based on available data through a desk research approach.

The research design was based on a comparative case study approach, whereby each case represented a specific city, region, or geothermal project. These cases vary in scale and data availability but were selected based on their relevance for the GO-Forward project (2023). Data collection was carried out using a combination of three methodological components: (1) an exploratory expert survey, (2) a 3-month desk research and (3) semi-formal expert feedback on each case. Please see the Acknowledgements (p. 101) for a list of GO-Forward colleagues who helped with tasks (1) and (3).

The combined data from the survey and desk research were qualitatively analyzed, and findings were validated through expert feedback. A thematic and interpretative approach was applied, with key themes and patterns emerging iteratively. Findings are summarized in a descriptive form and the sources used are listed immediately after each case.

First, the exploratory expert survey by Risiko-Dialog (2024) served as the initial entry point for each case (see Appendix: expert survey, page 106). Ten participants (n=10) were selected from the GO-Forward consortium based on their direct involvement in, or oversight of, geothermal initiatives in the respective regions. The survey was introduced during the project's kick-off meetings in September 2024 and conducted in November 2024 using the Survey123 tool by ESRI. It consisted primarily of structured, open-ended questions designed to elicit informed impressions of each case's societal context. The survey was not intended to produce representative data, but rather to offer brief, context-rich perspectives on stakeholder constellations, perceived relevance, and the public visibility of geothermal energy. Completion time was estimated to range from 15 to 20 minutes, and the depth of responses varied, reflecting different levels of expertise, professional roles, and proximity to the subject matter. Due to the selection of respondents from within the consortium, a degree of bias was inherent in the sample, and the survey results should therefore be considered indicative rather than comprehensive. The findings are meant to complement the information from the literature review.

Second, a 3-month desk research was conducted by two research assistants from February to April 2025 via Google and Google Scholar, drawing on publicly accessible sources such as academic publications, policy documents, planning reports, grey literature, and local media. Search terms typically included combinations of “deep geothermal”, the case location, and stakeholder-related terms, so for example “geothermal AND Aarhus AND environment”. The search was mostly conducted in English and German, and where possible, local-language sources were translated and included. AI-supported tools such as ChatGPT and DeepL were used to identify and translate documents in regional languages, thereby improving access to otherwise underrepresented sources. ChatGPT's Deep Research functionality was used systematically to enhance the breadth of coverage, particularly for local-language and non-indexed literature.

During this desk research, documents were included if they were openly accessible and addressed at least one of the key dimensions of societal embeddedness according to Sprenkeling et al. (2022). Exclusion criteria applied to paywalled materials. The availability and quality of documents varied considerably between regions, depending on local transparency standards, the presence of public debate, and the maturity of geothermal initiatives. This resulted in a heterogeneous but thematically rich collection of materials, which served as the empirical basis for subsequent analysis.

Third, after an extensive data collection for each case, the initial text drafts were sent out to experts from the consortium – either to the ones who filled out the survey or different ones, depending on their availability. Those experts provided semi-formal feedback, commenting on the information's correctness and whether they think that most relevant aspects regarding deep geothermal in that area were covered. The text drafts were adapted accordingly.

2.2 Limitations

However, several limitations were acknowledged during the research. First, reliance on open-access sources led to significant variation in data quality and depth across the cases. Some regions offered detailed documentation and extensive stakeholder discourse, while others showed limited publicly available material. Second, despite the use of translation tools, language barriers remained a challenge and increased reliance on AI tools like ChatGPT's Deep Research. Third, the sample size of the expert survey (n=10) drew from a small, specialized group of experts from within the project consortium. This, on the one hand, offered easier access to in-depth information on the regions, but on the other hand, might inherently be slightly biased. Finally, time constraints restricted the opportunity for deeper engagement with external stakeholders or the inclusion of longitudinal perspectives. Nevertheless, the combined methodology enabled a structured and context-sensitive examination of geothermal SEL in diverse regional settings, providing a foundation for comparative analysis and further research.

2.3 Structure and Spider-Diagram scoring approach

All cases follow the same structure. First, they provide a brief overview of the case's context. Then, they delve deeper into the four SEL dimensions, as outlined in the Methodology section and detailed in Sprenkeling et al. (2022). Additionally, each case is summarized by describing its key points. A Conclusions section at the end of the document summarizes the lessons learned from all the cases. It also provides guidance on selecting two cases for further study, as specified in the proposal (GO-Forward, 2024).

Direct numerical comparison of all cases is not meaningful due to the diversity of national and local contexts. However, we provide a way to compare case patterns with respect to selected, more easily quantifiable criteria. The exact numbers are not relevant; rather, it is a qualitative comparison among the cases visualized by spider diagrams. We chose the following criteria, which form the dimensions of the diagram. Numbers from 1 to 6 had to be assigned to populate the diagrams (see Table 3 and explanation below).

Table 3: The application of the numbers to the selected dimensions of the diagrams.

Criterion	Description of 1–6 scale	The number was selected in the following way
Project maturity	1 = no activity, 6 = full-scale plant operating	Expert survey (Risiko-Dialog 2024)
Data richness	1 = very little data, 6 = abundance of good data	Proposal info + expert judgment
History of problems / mistrust	1 = no past issues, 6 = serious legacy problems	Desk research + expert judgment
Public awareness	1 = low, 6 = high	Desk research + expert judgment
Public acceptance	1 = low, 6 = high	Directly from expert survey

- Project maturity: The *maturity of each case* was measured by expert judgment during the survey among consortium colleagues (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). The six ordinal response options were then assigned numbers as follows: No exploration activities so far = 1, Early exploration phase = 2, Mature exploration = 3, Geothermal pilot activities = 4, Geothermal pilot plant active = 5, Geothermal plant(s) operational = 6.
- Data richness: Whether a region was *data-rich* (6), *data-poor* (1), or in-between (3) was based in part on the proposal, see GO-Forward (2023), and in part on the expert judgment of Risiko-Dialog (2024).
- History of problems / mistrust: The *degree of historical problems* in a region or in other regions of the country resulting in legacies of mistrust in a region (e.g., Monte Amiata region, Italy, and Basel and St. Gallen, Switzerland) was based on the results of the desk research and the description from the expert judgments (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). The numbers were roughly assigned from no problems = 1 to many/big problems = 6.
- Public awareness: The *degree of national/local awareness* or knowledge of geothermal exploration was based on the judgments in Risiko-Dialog (2024) and the desk study, with low awareness = 1 and high = 6.
- Public acceptance: The *level of public acceptance* was taken directly from Risiko-Dialog (2024), where the experts provided numbers in the survey.

Spider graphs are included in each summary section. Since the focus is on patterns, there is no scale depicted in the diagram. The spider diagrams were evaluated by the consortium partners at the first GO-Forward General Assembly in Copenhagen. We updated the figures where adjustments had been suggested.

3 Case Studies

This section presents an analysis of 14 selected regions across nine European countries (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Italy, Spain/Catalonia, Switzerland, and the Netherlands) identified within the project proposal of GO-Forward (2023). Figure 2 shows the participating countries and the case areas. The general systematization follows the geological situation, as indicated by the blue legend boxes. Only those case areas where GO-Forward will undertake specific investigations are explicitly mentioned (see, Niederau, J., Bruhn, D., De Boever, E., Olivarius, M., Winterleitner, G., Welch, M., Smit, F., van Wees, J.D., Wellmann, F., Hoyer, S., and the GO-Forward Consortium, 2025). An interactive map covering all points, such as the Paris Basin, is available on the project homepage: <https://go-forward-project.eu>.

Figure 2: The map shows the countries and case areas that are the focus of the project, after Niederau et al. (2025).

3.1 Sandstones

3.1.1 Upper Triassic – Lower Jurassic Gassum Formation, Denmark

Three focus cases have been selected from the Gassum Formation, which is the most promising reservoir in the Danish subsurface, according to the project (GO-Forward, 2023): (a) the Stenlille Sandstone Reservoir, (b) the Aarhus site, and (c) the entire onshore Danish territory.

3.1.1.1 Case Overview

(a) Stenlille Sandstone Reservoir

The Stenlille structure is located in rural surroundings in Sorø municipality in central Zealand with a population of 31'000 people. Small villages with populations of roughly 500 people each are situated in the countryside around the case study site. (Risiko-Dialog, 2024; Gregersen et al., 2022, p. 2)

This site has been used for natural gas storage for 36 years. It is owned by the Danish State and run by the company Gas Storage Denmark. According to Weibel et al. (2020, p. 12), the area could provide geological suitability for geothermal exploitation. However, this site is not intended for geothermal production since it is used for natural gas storage and considered for CO₂ storage. The Stenlille case has been included in the project due to the excellent subsurface data and as an example of generally high public acceptance.

Despite the differences between natural gas storage and deep GE exploitation, some insights from this case can still be applied to cases of geothermal development. According to GO-Forward (2023), this site is data-rich and has the most subsurface data available to prove the GO-Forward concept, increasing its suitability for this analysis.

(b) Aarhus Site

Aarhus, Denmark's second-largest city, spans 91 km², including its suburban areas. It is a key economic and industrial hub, home to a university, an industrial harbor, and diverse business sectors, including tobacco, furniture, electronics, and food production (Risiko-Dialog, 2024).

The Aarhus Geothermal Project is Denmark's largest geothermal district heating initiative. Developed by Innargi A/S (Innargi) in collaboration with Kredsløb, the system will consist of three geothermal plants¹, with the first plant in Skejby expected to start operating by late 2025. Wells reach a depth of 2.5 km (Euroheat & Power, 2024). With a total capacity of 110 MW, it will cover 20% of Aarhus's district heating needs, equivalent to the demand of roughly 34'000 households, and reduce CO₂ emissions by up to 165'000 tons annually, supporting the city's goal of CO₂ neutrality by 2030 (Richter et al., 2024; Innargi, 2023b).

Again, it is important to highlight that the Aarhus project focuses on geothermal heating and not on deep GE generation per se. However, certain insights for deep GE still can be drawn from this real-life case as well.

(c) Onshore Danish Territory

This site does not focus on one specific plant or area but comprises the entire Danish onshore territory. In terms of geothermal, it is highly promising with several suitable geothermal reservoirs (Weibel et al., 2020, GO-Forward, 2023). Geothermal plants in the Danish area comprise a successful

¹ There were seven plants planned, but assumed synergies suggest the same amount of heat can be delivered by three plants (see <https://innargi.com/from-seven-to-three-geothermal-project-to-deliver-same-amount-of-heat-from-fewer-locations>, retrieved August 5, 2025).

plant in Thisted that has been in production since 1984, besides more recent plants in Sønderborg and Margretheholm that have faced difficulties. Data availability is highly varying across the country – therefore, findings from the specific Danish cases can be extrapolated for further insight. However, more in-depth research with experts is strongly advised here.

The following sub-chapters assess the SEL of deep GE in Denmark, with a particular focus on the Aarhus case, as the project is already underway and, comparatively, has the most available data.

3.1.1.2 Impact on the Environment

This section analyzes the impact of deep geothermal on the natural, built, and social environment in Denmark.

First of all, GE generally produces significantly lower CO₂ emissions and pollution compared to non-renewable alternatives. Forecasts of geothermal production for 2050 suggest that greenhouse gas emissions can be mitigated by 100 Mt per year with geothermal electricity production and more than 300 Mt per year with direct applications, much of which could be accomplished by district heating (Yadav et al., 2021, p. 260–261; 267) – this aligns with Denmark’s long-term climate goals, particularly in reducing carbon emissions under the Paris Climate Agreement. The Aarhus geothermal project alone is expected to cut CO₂ emissions by up to 165’000 tons per year through geothermal heating (Cariaga, 2022).

However, a point that would require further clarification in this case is the long-term impact of deep GE on the natural environment in Denmark, like on air, soil and groundwater. While protective measures are in place, such as for example extra casings to prevent contamination, there is no comprehensive study to be found in this desk research on how geothermal heat extraction may affect groundwater temperature, chemical balance, and ecosystem health over time (Poulsen, 2019). Comparative studies from other European geothermal sites such as those in Germany, Iceland, and the Netherlands, could provide useful insights into best practices for environmental protection and further research. Involving the Danish Water Works, as suggested by expert feedback on this case, would also be beneficial.

Furthermore, throughout the research, noise disturbance was an aspect mentioned comparatively often (e.g. see Cariaga, 2023). In the exploration phase during testing activities by Innargi around Copenhagen, particularly vibrations from seismic trucks driving by during the night, were feared to raise concerns among residents (see Garcia, 2024a). Thus, Innargi has proactively reassured the public on their website by explaining and emphasizing that their operations pose no risk to public safety regarding people or buildings (see Hamilton, 2023; Garcia, 2024b).

At later stages, the presence of large construction sites, drilling rigs, and heavy machinery was feared to cause further disruptions. To mitigate aesthetic and physical intrusions, there are ongoing efforts to bury infrastructure underground and use modularized plant designs including an electric drilling rig to minimize visual impact and drilling noise (Richter, 2022).

Looking at the information from the Stenlille Sandstone Reservoir, it becomes evident that residents have lived near the site for almost 36 years² without any noteworthy protest (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). The site’s visible infrastructure is somewhat comparable to a geothermal plant in terms of noise and aesthetics. This might suggest hypothetical acceptance within the population; however, further confirmation is needed.

Overall, while deep geothermal is already operating in some regions and certain environmental impacts have been proactively mitigated, unanswered questions about certain long-term

² The storage of natural gas in the Stenlille reservoir began in 1989.

environmental implications, such as specific groundwater effects in this particular research, prevent full integration into the societal system.

3.1.1.3 Stakeholder Involvement

This section focuses on the current stakeholder involvement regarding deep geothermal in Denmark.

It is important to mention that most of the research on stakeholder involvement was conducted in English, which could explain the somewhat sparse data availability. It is recommended to conduct further in-depth research with locals to verify these findings.

According to the results of the desk research for this case, the key stakeholders for this project are private actors (residents, local communities, general public), economic actors (local district heating companies, energy companies such as Innargi) and political actors (city council, municipalities, and the Danish government).

The industry leader Innargi has worked on public engagement by putting up information posters and hosting small interactive information events to educate communities (see Cariaga, 2023). Additionally, the board chairmen of the Aarhus district heating company have framed geothermal as a “piece of green national history”, emphasizing its role in Denmark’s transition to sustainable heating (Cariaga, 2023).

On this note, apparently, there is still only limited public in-depth knowledge in Denmark about geothermal energy, which could maybe also be attributed to the fact that there have not been many geothermal projects in the country so far. Yet, the overall perception still remains positive. According to a survey by Risiko-Dialog (2024), it is viewed as a green and sustainable long-term solution, but trust in its technical reliability is low due to previous failures in Denmark, especially in Sønderborg. This distrust might extend to local district heating companies, which have been reluctant to invest in geothermal solutions due to perceived risks of failure (Risiko-Dialog, 2024).

Thus, the Aarhus project includes an important trust-building measure: Innargi carries all subsurface risks, ensuring that the city council and residents are not financially liable for unforeseen technical failures (Kombrink, 2022). Given that two previous Danish geothermal projects failed due to well design issues, this reassurance might play a significant role in securing stakeholder buy-in (see Kombrink, 2022).

In terms of energy supply security, well-working geothermal sites could be seen as a secure and stable heat source, especially in response to historical oil price fluctuations in Denmark (Egean, 2021).

From a socio-economic perspective, both sites offer additional workplaces and currently employ around 50 people directly in both Aarhus and Stenlille (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). There is a faculty at the University of Aarhus exclusively focusing on geoscience that has been operating since the 1960s.

All in all, it can be observed that even though trust in the technology is still developing, and some trust issues remain, stakeholder participation has been managed through public engagement events and some risk-sharing mechanisms. Knowledge transfer and proactive educational programs seem essential to further increase the stakeholder’s trust.

3.1.1.4 Policy and Regulations

This section focuses on Danish policies and regulations governing geothermal.

First, obtaining precise and up-to-date information about policy and regulations of geothermal in Denmark was particularly challenging during this research, which could also be either attributed to the language barrier or potentially to the lack of transparent and publicly accessible information.

Denmark has a structured legal framework for renewable energy development, which also includes geothermal energy. Primarily, it is governed by the Act on Promotion of Renewable Energy

(Consolidated Act No. 1791 of 2021) and the Electricity Supply Act (Consolidated Act No. 984 of 2021) (Klingberg-Jensen et al., 2022). The Danish Subsoil Act and the Heating Supplies Act regulate licensing, technical requirements, and financial planning. According to some sources, these frameworks have historically been complicated and challenging for private investors to navigate (Klingberg-Jensen et al., 2022). Municipal governments play an important role in issuing geothermal heating licenses, requiring them to consider groundwater restrictions and conduct environmental impact assessments before granting approvals (Poulsen, 2019, p. 3). Wells up to 250 meters deep can be approved by municipalities, but for deeper geothermal drilling, the Danish Energy Agency (DEA) must be contacted in advance to oversee the project plan and to ensure that certain “good practice” guidelines are met (Energistyrelsen, 2025).

However, while GE is legally classified as a renewable energy source, it does not receive the same level of financial incentives as other renewables, e.g., as wind or solar energy (Klingberg-Jensen et al., 2022). In 2024, the grant pool offered by the DEA for the country’s green energy transition covered up to 50% of investment costs only for individual cases (Intelligence, 2024). The Danish government has gradually reduced subsidies for renewable energy as technologies have become more market competitive. Unlike offshore wind, which benefits from Contracts for Difference (CfD)³ and construction subsidies, geothermal development relies primarily on market-driven investments, with no direct financial support from the government (Klingberg-Jensen et al., 2022). However, high fossil fuel taxes (CO₂ taxes) and tax-cuts for electricity heating indirectly incentivize geothermal energy, making it more economically viable in the long run (Klingberg-Jensen et al., 2022; Ernst & Young, 2024).

Moreover, in an effort to support geothermal heating projects, the Danish Parliament passed a law exempting geothermal heat projects from existing price regulations. Instead, pricing is now set by contracts between district heating companies and geothermal operators with a consumer cost ceiling to protect both consumers and utilities from excessive price fluctuations. The Danish Supply Authority oversees these exemptions to ensure compliance (Cariaga, 2023b; Klingberg-Jensen et al., 2022). One can observe that there is growing political support for geothermal energy, reinforced by Denmark’s broader renewable energy policies (Richter et al., 2024). Nevertheless, at the current moment, local governments still remain hesitant to invest taxpayer money, mainly due to the perceived financial risks associated with past project failures such as the one in Sønderborg (Risiko-Dialog, 2024; Klingberg-Jensen et al., 2022). This creates a mismatch between market interest and government commitment, slowing the pace of geothermal deployment.

From an SEL perspective, the current policy and regulatory framework for GE in Denmark can be located around a rather mature stage. While key regulations are in place, stakeholders continue to face barriers due to regulatory complexity and a lack of financial incentives. Denmark could focus more on simplifying permitting procedures, developing risk-mitigation measures for investors, and aligning financial support mechanisms with those of other renewable energy sources.

3.1.1.5 Market and Financial Resources

This section focuses on the current market situation of deep geothermal in Denmark.

According to Richter et al. (2024), renewables made up 82% of Denmark’s energy supply mix in 2023. Major green sources of energy are wind and biomass power. However, a significant increase in GE could also be observed over the past years.

³ CfDs are a financial support mechanism used to promote investment in renewable energy projects. They provide stability for investors by guaranteeing a fixed price for electricity generation over a set period. (Khodadi & Poudineh, 2024, p. 1).

The market demand for geothermal heating is growing and Innargi is planning expansion into Copenhagen (Hamilton, 2023). The market is consolidated, with Innargi A/S, GreenTherma and Geoop being the major players.

One of the biggest barriers to geothermal development in Denmark seem to be high initial investment costs. While Denmark promotes private investment, there is no direct government funding for geothermal projects (Poulsen, 2019). Instead, high taxes on fossil fuels create financial incentives for renewable energy adoption (Poulsen et al., 2019).

High perceived financial risks remain a deterrent. Some license holders have sought insurance coverage against potential financial losses (Poulsen, 2019). If better risk-mitigation measures were in place, more stakeholders might be willing to invest in geothermal projects.

Furthermore, a detailed cost-benefit analysis comparing geothermal to other renewable energy sources in Denmark, such as wind and solar, would be recommended. Since geothermal heating and energy involve high upfront costs but low long-term operational costs, such a comparison would help clarify its financial competitiveness in this case.

All in all, from an SEL perspective, these developments can be located around a rather mature stage as well. Investor interest is growing, but funding risks seem to still be perceived as high. Insurance mechanisms need development to further increase trust within investors, especially since there is no direct governmental funding in place now.

3.1.1.6 Summary Gassum Formation, Denmark

After having analyzed the environmental impact, the stakeholder involvement, the policies and regulations as well as the market and financial resources for geothermal projects in Denmark, the overall SEL can be located at a rather mature level (see Figure 3 for a visualization of selected dimensions for all three case areas. The figure is more about the pattern than specific numbers).

The Aarhus project is showing strong progress towards full deployment, such as for example proactively mitigating noise and aesthetic concerns through stakeholder communication, helping Denmark to reach their CO₂ goals in the long run.

However, some key challenges remain. Public perception is positive, but trust in the technology's reliability is fragile due to past failures. While regulations are in place, their complexity slows development, and local political hesitation limits public investment. The market is growing, with rising private investor interest, but high upfront costs and a lack of government funding create financial risks.

Taking these aspects into account, it seems necessary to implement further policy adjustments and financial mechanisms to bridge the gap between technological readiness and societal embeddedness. To further increase the SEL level, Denmark could focus on simplifying regulatory processes, increasing financial incentives or risk-sharing mechanisms, and enhancing public trust through transparency and long-term environmental monitoring. Addressing the research gap on the environmental impact, aligning investment conditions with other renewables, and strengthening stakeholder engagement will be critical steps toward full societal integration.

If these barriers are effectively tackled, geothermal could become a fully socially embedded and scalable heating solution in Denmark's renewable energy transition.

Figure 3: Profiles of the three case areas in Denmark for selected criteria. The Stenlille case is evaluated as a natural gas storage site rather than for geothermal.

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3.1.2 Upper Jurassic – Lower Cretaceous Nieuwerkerk Formation (West Netherlands Basin) and Neogene Shallow Marine, Siliciclastic Dominated Aquifers, Netherlands

Two focus areas have been selected based on their geological potential and current relevance in the Dutch energy transition in the project's proposal (GO-Forward, 2023): (a) the Delft Sandstone, a member of the Nieuwerkerk Formation, and (b) the Neogene Upper North Sea Group, which hosts multiple aquifers.

3.1.2.1 Case Overview

Deep GE in the Netherlands is increasingly seen as a key technology for heat decarbonization. Currently, the sector's development is still focused on direct heat for greenhouses, however, an expansion to urban heat networks is essential for driving further growth and supporting the country's climate ambitions (Toth et al., 2025, p. 5). Since the first geothermal doublet was drilled in 2007, over 80 wells have been developed, primarily in the western part of the country. However, societal trust, regulatory clarity, and geological data gaps still challenge widespread deployment (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). The Dutch government aims to scale geothermal output to 15 petajoules of sustainable energy by 2030 (which is the equivalent of the average gas and electricity consumption of 2.2 million or roughly ¼ of Dutch households), supported by strategic public-private partnerships and national programs. This results in the installation of 700 direct-use doublets to cover at least 30% of the country's heating demand (Klimaat, 2017; Master Plan Geothermal Energy in The Netherlands, 2018; Vardon et al., 2024, p. 1).

(a) Delft Sandstone

Located in the West Netherlands Basin, the Delft Sandstone area within the Nieuwerkerk Formation is one of the most prolific geothermal aquifers in the Netherlands. It hosts around 38 wells of which 13 are drilled doublets (Ministry of Climate Policy and Green Growth, 2024) and benefits from high data availability due to extensive oil and gas exploration in the region (GO-Forward, 2023).

The Geothermie Delft project, led by a consortium of TU Delft, Shell Geothermal, EBN, and Aardyn, combines heat production with a national research infrastructure. The project will supply low-carbon heat to Delft University of Technology and adjacent urban districts and serve as a testbed for monitoring and simulation of geothermal operations in sedimentary settings (Vardon et al., 2024, p. 1; TU Delft, n.d.). Heat will be supplied from a low-enthalpy range (<100°C) through doublets of 2.5 km depth with the first production planned in 2025. The doublet will be connected to a heating grid, an aquifer thermal energy storage system, and a heat pump to form a comprehensive urban heating system (Vardon et al., 2024, p. 1).

The site is situated in an urban environment with a high density of built infrastructure, as well as a population that has historically expressed mixed views on subsurface operations, shaped by the legacy of (comparably low) induced seismicity due to gas extraction in the Groningen region (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). However, when installed in greenhouse areas where geothermal is seen as a welcome source of energy, public acceptance is higher.

(b) Neogene Upper North Sea Group

The Neogene Upper North Sea Group covers a large portion of the Dutch subsurface, consisting primarily of shallow marine Cenozoic sediments, including formations like the Breda and Oosterhout. These formations are increasingly being explored for low-to-medium temperature GE and HT-ATES, particularly in urban areas. However, this region is considered data-poor, with limited well logs and seismic information available (GO-Forward, 2023; Risiko-Dialog, 2024).

Due to the early exploration phase with only a few installations in operation and the scarcity of subsurface data, the environmental, technical, and social uncertainties in this region are high. Research and policy actors have identified it as a strategic target for development (see GO-Forward, 2023), but further site-specific investigations are still needed to assess feasibility and risks. An exploration well targeting the Breda Fm is currently being drilled as part of the EBN and TNO SCAN drilling program.

3.1.2.2 Impact on the Environment

This section analyzes the impact of deep geothermal on the natural, built, and social environment.

First, in the Delft Sandstone area, ground vibrations during the exploration and noise impacts during the drilling phase are explicitly acknowledged: operations take place 24/7 over three to six months and include disturbances such as drilling noise, bumping rods, truck movement, and occasional light pollution at night. These nuisances are temporary and are apparently monitored continuously, with mitigating measures like restricted work hours and physical barriers (Geothermie Nederland, 2025). It should be noted that the drilling process for the Delft doublet required a significantly greater amount of time in comparison to other doublets. This delay can be attributed to the complexity of the logging and coring procedures, as well as the intricate nature of the well design. Once operational, the industry association Geothermie Nederland (2025) further proactively informs the public that the plant is quiet, with minimal noise detectable outside the facility fence.

Concerns around pollution and effects on animals have not been found during this desk research, but local communities (particularly in the northern Netherlands) still remain skeptical due to prior experiences with subsurface extraction – particularly the seismic events linked to gas production in the Groningen gas field (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). As a result, public sensitivity around induced seismicity and subsidence remains high (Mendrinós et al., 2022, pp. 901–902). It should be noted, however, that parts of the general public oppose also other energy related activities, such as CCUS, wind, or nuclear power.

Regarding water quality, no contamination incidents are known at this stage, but NGOs, industry and government actors continue to raise questions about potential impacts on drinking water and subsurface conditions of GE in the Netherlands (Metze et al., 2023, p. 4; Vewin, 2025). In Delft, this concern is actively addressed through extensive data monitoring as part of the EPOS-NL research infrastructure, which studies pressure changes and fault behavior during operation (TU Delft, n.d., Geothermie Delft, 2021).

In contrast to Delft, the Neogene Upper North Sea Group is still in the exploration phase.⁴ The formations, such as the Breda, Oosterhout and Maassluis, are shallow marine siliciclastic aquifers covering a large portion of the country. However, as this region is data-poor, no known environmental assessments have been carried out so far. As such, the environmental impact of geothermal development in these formations remains speculative (GO-Forward, 2023; Risiko-Dialog, 2024).

Overall, in terms of SEL, environmental concerns in Delft are actively addressed through monitoring, communication, and design measures, whereas in the Neogene region, environmental risks remain mostly theoretical at this stage due to a lack of data. Continued attention to groundwater safety and long-term monitoring will be essential for public trust and future scalability.

3.1.2.3 Stakeholder Involvement

This section focuses on the current stakeholder involvement in the Netherlands regarding deep geothermal energy.

Since the Netherlands have historically focused on GE in greenhouse horticulture, it is important to highlight that this is different to implementation in the built environment (Richter, 2020). A chairman of the Dutch Platform Geothermie, an NPO (Schoof, cit. in Richter, 2020, n.p.), emphasizes that geothermal in greenhouse horticulture and in the built environment are “the same on a technical level, but everything around it is different [...] The construction of a heat network in a residential area means something to that area. Residents must be helped to participate. They need to know what the environmental effects are and what the sources are that are connected to the heat network.” He highlights the need for transparent communication and a participatory approach.

It has been communicated that the supposedly unique research project of global relevance will contribute to a “smooth transition to sustainable energy in a widespread manner in the Netherlands and beyond” (TU Delft, n.d.). Furthermore, public engagement efforts include proactive communication about expected nuisances such as noise, light pollution, and traffic during drilling phases, which are shared in advance with residents along with the planned work schedule (see Geothermie Nederland, 2025). The concise and proactive public information stood out during the research for this case.

The geothermal project in Delft has a dual function as both a heat provider and a full-scale research infrastructure (TU Delft, n.d.). Its presence results in several new job positions as well as even its own campus research program for students at the Technical University of Delft (TU Delft, n.d.). According to the University itself (TU Delft, n.d.), Geothermal Science and Engineering is a focus area within the Department of Geoscience and Engineering that serves as a global knowledge center for geothermal research and development –, showcasing strong stakeholder involvement.

Several in-depth interviews conducted in 2016 and 2017 by Metze et al. (2023) examined the main uncertainties of stakeholders from the industry, government, NGOs, citizen groups, journalists and experts in the Netherlands to identify their preferred ways of involvement in deep GE projects. Generally, all stakeholders were positive about the potential contribution of GE to a more sustainable energy system. At the same time, it also became evident that there were four primary types of uncertainties at that time, namely: informational ones (knowledge gaps), normative ones (differences in values and goals of the project), conceptual ones (confusion around definitions and terminology, e.g. deep vs. ultra-deep geothermal) and institutional ones (doubts about the appropriateness of governance and legal structures in place) (Metze et al., 2023, p. 4). A range of four main participatory preferences has been identified, from local and societal dialogues to joint fact-finding processes,

⁴ A doublet was drilled in the Middle North Sea Group, Brussel Sands Fm (700m depth), but operations ceased after 1.5 years of production.

suggesting that inclusive engagement is an expectation amongst stakeholders (for details see Metze et al., 2023, p. 7).

It stands out that historical events related to Groningen seem to have reduced public trust in subsurface projects more broadly – more precisely towards the operating company as well as the supervising authorities – resulting in emotional responses and a desire for (participatory) monitoring in geothermal initiatives (Mendrinós et al., 2022, pp. 901–902).

Further concerns about safety, procedural fairness, and long-term risks, such as drinking water contamination or seismic events, are commonly expressed across stakeholder groups, including NGOs, local authorities, and industry actors (Metze et al., 2023, p. 4). Thus, a publication of Geothermie Nederland (2023) – the Dutch association for companies and institutions actively engaged in GE – emphasizes: “Geothermal and safety management are inseparable. It is a prerequisite for development of the sector; if it is not right, you lose confidence and there is no support [...] concerns about safety can get in the way of geothermal growth”. This highlights the importance of addressing safety concerns early-on instead of what Duijn et al. (2024, p. 2) call a “decide–announce–defend” strategy, putting the project on the wrong foot from the start.

In the Neogene Upper North Sea Group, although many people are affected, stakeholder involvement is still minimal due to the early exploration phase (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). During this research, no systematic public or institutional engagement has been identified yet. Extrapolating from the available data from other regions, it can be expected that emotional reactions and public skepticism will arise once projects progress, especially if local stakeholders and their communities are not included early in the process. Therefore, further research and proactive mitigation measures are highly recommended as the projects in the area move forward.

Overall, from an SEL perspective, stakeholder involvement in Delft is characterized by high transparency and proactive communication, with efforts made to address historical mistrust and ensure public awareness. In the Neogene region, engagement is currently lacking, and further efforts will be needed to address the informational and emotional uncertainties identified by various stakeholder groups. Early, inclusive, and context-sensitive communication will be essential to avoid skepticism and resistance as exploration advances.

3.1.2.4 Policy and Regulations

This section focuses on Dutch policies and regulations governing deep geothermal.

The regulatory landscape for GE in the Netherlands is relatively well-developed, anchored in national laws and institutional coordination. Municipalities are increasingly empowered under new legislation, including the Heat Act 2.0 (Warmtewet in Dutch) and planned gas disconnection mandates, which shall facilitate the rollout of sustainable heating systems, including geothermal (Herreras Martínez et al., 2025, p. 11).

Exploration and extraction of geothermal resources deeper than 500 meters require permits under the Dutch Mining Act and Environmental Licensing Act, with safety oversight conducted by the State Supervision of Mines and two extra sections regulating the licensing for pure scientific research. Under the Environmental Licensing Act, it is also mandatory to hold an environmental permit (NLOG, 2025; Klimaat, 2017).

The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy is the central authority for licensing⁵, while EBN, a state-owned policy holding, now has the legal right to participate in all new geothermal projects,

⁵ It is interesting to note that there is a Ministry of Economic Affairs (for economic activities including mining), while the Ministry of Climate and Green Growth is heavily involved in the energy transition, too.

combining financial investment and policy alignment (Harings, 2023). This dual role has raised institutional concerns among developers, particularly over potential conflicts between EBN's oversight and investor functions (Metze et al., 2023, p. 6).

Furthermore, spatial and zoning frameworks – such as the STRONG instrument for subsurface planning – add another layer of governance (Metze et al., 2023, p. 5). Additional support comes from the SCAN program, which includes the acquisition of seismic lines and the drilling of several exploration wells to help investigating the subsurface suitability for geothermal heat extraction (SCAN *Scouts the Dutch Subsurface for Geothermal Opportunities*, n.d.). To accelerate geothermal development, the government has introduced targeted incentives. These include the SDE++ scheme⁶, which provides long-term subsidies based on the market price of heat, and the RNES risk coverage program, which insures against geological risks in drilling (Zaal et al., 2021, p. 9; Klimaat, 2017).

In summary, from an SEL perspective, the Dutch geothermal policy framework demonstrates a mature institutional structure with relatively clear legal procedures and well-targeted financial instruments. Municipalities are gaining a stronger role and gas disconnection mandates. Despite these developments, further progress depends on improved institutional clarity, regulatory simplification, and better cross-level alignment to ensure stakeholder confidence and system scalability.

3.1.2.5 Market and Financial Resources

This section focuses on the current market situation of deep geothermal in the Netherlands.

The Netherlands were part of the cross-country Interreg DGE-ROLLOUT project, which has arguably advanced the country's deep geothermal sector by enhancing geological understanding of the Dinantian carbonate formations, developing decision-support tools for investors, and integrating findings into national programs like Ultra-Deep Geothermal (TNO, n.d.). It could be argued that these efforts, supported by Dutch partners such as EBN and TNO, have accelerated the transition to geothermal heat sources in the country, even though their primary focus was not on the Lower Cretaceous Nieuwerkerk Formation or the Neogene Shallow Marine, Siliciclastic Dominated Aquifers, but rather on the Dinantian carbonate formations.

The Dutch geothermal market is developing steadily but continues to face financial barriers. The expansion into urban heat networks remains limited due to lower load hours and higher perceived investment risks (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). This is particularly challenging, as around 80% of the heating demand in the Netherlands exists in areas where there is little or no subsurface knowledge, creating a significant gap between market potential and investment readiness (Master Plan Geothermal Energy in The Netherlands, 2018, p. 30).

Initial capital investment remains a critical bottleneck similar to the other countries analyzed in this paper. Direct-use geothermal projects have high upfront costs, particularly for drilling, permitting, and infrastructure. Although the government provides substantial support – including the SDE++, which offers production-based subsidies over 15 years, and the RNES⁷, which covers failed drillings – financial uncertainty persists, especially in early-stage areas where subsurface data is scarce (Zaal et al., 2021, p. 9; Klimaat, 2017). As such, many projects seem to depend on public co-investment from entities like EBN to reduce financial risk and ensure long-term viability (Harings, 2023). Additionally, licensing takes a long time. Therefore, new legislation has been put in place recently, speeding up the licensing process.

⁶ <https://clean-energy-islands.ec.europa.eu/countries/netherlands/legal/electricity-support/subsidy-sde-scheme-producing-renewable-energy-and>

⁷ <https://www.nlog.nl/en/rnes-warranty-regulation>

The national heat market is expected to shift, as from 2026, all new heating systems must utilize sustainable sources starting in 2026, and municipalities will be legally permitted to ban natural gas connections from 2024 onward (Herrerias Martínez et al., 2025, p. 11). These regulatory changes increase geothermal's market potential, particularly in densely built environments.

At the same time, affordability remains a central concern for both residents and developers. As of 2021, the heat price in the Netherlands was determined as 90% of the Dutch market price of gas (Zaal et al., 2021, p. 9). However, probably due to the high initial costs, sustainable heat continues to struggle to compete with relatively cheap gas without continued subsidies or cost-reduction strategies. (Richter, 2020). Trust in fair pricing and freedom of choice are important elements of perceived energy justice, especially for low-income neighborhoods (Metze et al., 2023, p. 5).

Overall, in terms of SEL, the geothermal market in the Netherlands shows increasing momentum, supported by strong government incentives and national climate goals. However, project financing still relies heavily on subsidies and public investment, while commercial uptake in the urban sector remains limited.⁸ Long-term scaling will require further cost reductions, improved business models, and trust in fair pricing mechanisms to ensure broad societal support. With these aspects in mind, both areas, namely the Delft Sandstone and the Neogene Upper North Sea Group, seem to be highly promising targets for further geothermal exploration.

3.1.2.6 Summary Upper Jurassic, Netherlands

This case study assessed the societal embeddedness of deep GE in the Netherlands through the lens of two geologically distinct focus areas, namely the Delft Sandstone Member and the Neogene Upper North Sea Group (see Figure 4 for a visualization of selected criteria for both case areas. The figure emphasizes the pattern rather than specific numbers).

From an environmental perspective, the Delft Sandstone region stands out for its proactive communication and mitigation of expected impacts during drilling, such as noise and light pollution. Long-term environmental risks like seismicity and groundwater contamination are supposedly addressed through integrated monitoring but could be further clarified in future research. In contrast, the Neogene Upper North Sea Group remains in an early exploration phase, with environmental impacts still speculative due to a lack of data and operational experience.

Stakeholder involvement in Delft is relatively advanced. Public engagement is managed transparently through scheduled updates, participatory communication, and institutional collaboration with TU Delft and other partners. Historical mistrust from the Groningen gas field experience has led to a strong need for safety monitoring and procedural fairness, especially among NGOs and local groups. In the Neogene area, no structured stakeholder engagement has been identified yet, highlighting a critical need for early communication and inclusive planning as exploration progresses.

Policy and regulation at the national level are well-developed, with a clear legal framework anchored in the Mining Act, zoning instruments, and new legislation empowering municipalities. Government support includes permitting clarity, mandatory public participation by EBN, and financial risk mitigation tools. However, institutional overlap and investor concerns about governance roles still present barriers to seamless project implementation.

The financial and market outlook for deep GE is cautiously optimistic. While greenhouse horticulture has proven commercially viable, urban heating remains a challenge due to lower load hours and higher investment risks. Around 80% of the country's heat demand lies in regions with little subsurface

⁸ Put differently, private companies are afraid of the government getting involved in urban heating, while the government would like to get in and accelerate development.

data, further limiting private-sector confidence. Public subsidies (SDE++, RNES) and upcoming natural gas phase-outs offer strong policy signals, but cost competitiveness and perceived fairness – especially for end users – remain key factors for wider adoption.

From an SEL perspective, the Delft Sandstone case reflects strong integration, with proactive communication, stakeholder engagement, and risk monitoring supporting public trust. The project benefits from high data availability and institutional collaboration.

In contrast, the Neogene Upper North Sea Group is still in an exploratory phase with limited stakeholder involvement and high uncertainty, particularly due to sparse subsurface data. While national regulations and financial tools are in place, institutional clarity and cost competitiveness remain key challenges. Closing these gaps especially in early-stage regions will be essential for broader societal acceptance and successful geothermal scale-up across the Netherlands. Applying the SEL framework in this context reveals not only the existing societal gaps, but also the areas where future project design and stakeholder processes can be targeted to strengthen societal alignment as technologies transition from development to deployment.

Figure 4: Profiles of the two Dutch case areas for selected criteria.

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3.2 Carbonates

3.2.1 Mid-Jurassic Carbonate Ramp (Paris Basin), France

3.2.1.1 Case Overview

Geothermal energy is a key component of France's strategy for decarbonizing its energy sector as well as enhancing energy sovereignty (Bouillon-Duparc, 2023; Renoth, 2023, p. 1). Among the country's geothermal regions, the Paris Basin stands out as one of the most advanced and productive ones: supplying heat to urban networks for over five decades, it is one of the most detailed and longest studied geothermal provinces in Central Europe (Toth et al., 2025, p. 2; Richter 2020; Risiko-Dialog, 2024).

The first geothermal plant in the region of 1100 km² around Paris began operating in 1969. Today, several geothermal plants are in production, contributing to a total annual heat output of 1.7 TWh (Risiko-Dialog, 2024; Schmidlé-Bloch et al., 2022). As of 2023, *near surface* geothermal supplied ⅔ of France's geothermal heat production (Cariaga, 2023). *Deep* geothermal, on the other side, accounted

for 58 plants in the Île-de-France region (Cariaga, 2023). The Paris Basin primarily relies on the Dogger aquifer, a vast mid-Jurassic limestone reservoir located 1500–2000 meters deep, where water temperatures range between 60–80°C (Richter, 2020). This resource has made the region a global leader in geothermal district heating, with currently around 50 networks supplying heat to 250'000 homes across the Île-de-France region (Richter, 2020).

However, despite its huge potential and the comparatively large number of geothermal plants, geothermal heating only represented 1% of the final consumption of renewable heat in France in 2021 (Bouillon-Duparc, 2023). Moreover, the geothermal *electric* sector stays relatively underdeveloped (Mikalauskas & Stanislovaityte, 2025, p. 239). Thus, there are specific action plans in place to further boost geothermal development in the Paris Basin, since decarbonization of heating systems plays a major role in enabling France to meet their climate neutrality goals by 2050 (Pannier-Runacher, 2023, p. 2).

The following section presents an analysis of the Paris Basin based on the four SEL dimensions as outlined by Sprenkeling et al. (2022).

3.2.1.2 Impact on the Environment

This section analyzes the impact of deep geothermal on the natural, built, and social environment.

First, noise pollution during the construction phase seems to be a primary issue, as drilling occurs 24/7 for several months, raising concerns among residents and nearby schools (Richter, 2021). Planned mitigation measures by one of the drilling companies include acoustic barriers, electrically powered tools, and noise modeling studies commissioned by local authorities to refine strategies (Richter, 2021).

Visual disruption is most significant during drilling and testing phases, when large industrial rigs modify the landscape (Gombert et al., 2018, p. 2). However, once operational, geothermal plants are reported to require minimal land and can integrate well into urban or industrial settings (Gombert et al., 2018, p. 2). Gombert et al. (2018, p. 2) argue that since most geothermal plants are located in already urbanized areas, their impact on the natural environment is minimized. One project in Saint-Denis, for instance, showcases efforts to enhance urban integration by revegetating sites and adding public spaces post-construction, such as building a playground on one of the geothermal sites to reduce its impact on the social environment (Bardavid, 2024).

Potential earthquakes are apparently monitored by sensors and specific tools for safety (Richter, 2021). Even though drilling deeper comes with greater technical risk (Deboyser, 2020), no significant seismic incidents have been recorded in the Île-de-France region so far – a distinction that is frequently highlighted in public communication efforts, since the demand for transparency about environmental impacts such as seismicity and air, soil and groundwater pollution remains high (Chavot et al., 2021, p. 50; p. 47).

In terms of CCUS, GE supports France's climate goals with its low carbon footprint (17–60 g CO₂/kWh) compared to fossil fuels (Gombert et al., 2018, p. 2). Expanding geothermal district heating is crucial to the country's 2050 carbon neutrality strategy, as decarbonizing heat is a key lever in reducing emissions (Pannier-Runacher, 2023, p. 2).

Overall, the environmental impact of deep GE in the Paris Basin aligns with a relatively mature stage in terms of SEL. While the technology is already operational and integrated into the urban infrastructure, some environmental concerns remain, and mitigation measures are actively being refined. The potential negative impacts, such as noise pollution and aesthetic disruptions, have been acknowledged, and steps have been taken to minimize them. However, continued monitoring of potential environmental impacts is needed to further increase the SEL by ensuring that all

environmental concerns (such as groundwater, soil, or air pollution) are systematically addressed, and societal acceptance is secured.

3.2.1.3 Stakeholder Involvement

This section focuses on the current stakeholder involvement in the Île-de-France region.

As found in this desk research, the success of deep geothermal projects in the Paris Basin seems to heavily rely on the inclusion of multiple stakeholders, including government institutions, private companies, and local communities. Simultaneously, according to experts, local NGOs might have a significant influence on project success as well (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). It became evident that a lot of different players cooperate throughout the execution of a geothermal project in France (see Chavot et al, 2019, p. 112–113).

Overall, stakeholder perception of geothermal energy in the area seems to be rather positive (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). However, a study conducted by Lagache (2012, cited in Chavot et al, 2019) on the acceptability of risks associated with deep geothermal in France suggests that the construction of a site in close proximity to one's private home is not widely accepted by the public (Chavot et al., 2019, p. 118). It can be assumed that this likely reflects the current perception in the Paris region, as well. Thus, it is suggested to continuously inform the public about the site's benefits (Chavot et al., 2019, p. 118) and carry out further acceptability studies.

The greater Paris urban area is home to around 12 million people. Community perceptions seem to significantly influence public acceptance of geothermal projects, as demonstrated in the following example: In Alsace, for instance, one project was imposed in a top-down way on the local community without prior debates. Shortly after, opposition groups (comprising residents, environmental NGOs (e.g. Alsace Nature), and politicians) expressed concerns over safety risks (induced seismicity, groundwater pollution, radioactive upwelling, and even the risk of explosion), corporate control, and lack of transparency, leading to the rejection of projects in the 2010s (Chavot et al., 2019, p. 115–117).

Conversely, in Illkirch-Graffenstaden, where projects were co-designed with local stakeholders through upstream discussions, acceptance was much smoother (Chavot et al., 2019, p. 18–19). Local governments and municipalities play a key role in decision-making, funding, and community engagement (Energynews, 2024). In the Paris Basin, strong municipal involvement has likely contributed to greater public trust by allowing more direct dialogue between residents and decision-makers (Falque-Masset & Pottier, 2024).

Thus, it seems important to highlight the importance of integrating all affected stakeholders into the decision-making process to ensure acceptance for geothermal projects in France. One way to do this is through public inquiry forums such as the one in Malakoff for example, where residents could contribute ideas and opinions in written or spoken form (see Gubian, 2022). This seems to give them a sense of direct involvement. Information materials on the topic can be found in large numbers on government or company websites in both French and English language. In this context, the desk research suggests that the feeling of having a voice and being heard might be more important to local stakeholders than the technicalities of the respective geothermal project.

Moreover, according to Bouillon-Duparc (2023), geothermal energy has a very high level of energy supply security over a time horizon of several years. Geothermal energy is said to be among the few renewable energy sources capable of efficiently producing heating, cooling, chilling, and electricity 24/7 in all seasons, regardless of weather conditions. Due to the unpredictability of oil and gas prices caused by geopolitical tensions, such as the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, a constant and predictable heating supply is becoming increasingly attractive to the population (Energynews, 2024).

Lastly, from a labor market perspective, it can be estimated that geothermal in France would create around 5500 opportunities for employment (Mikalauskas & Stanislovaityte, 2025, p. 241) – this number being among the highest across Europe.

All in all, stakeholder involvement in the Paris Basin is relatively strong due to multi-level governance, private-sector expertise, and proactive municipal engagement. Compared to controversial cases like Strasbourg, the Paris region benefits from transparent communication efforts and procedural justice, fostering higher levels of public trust and acceptance. Therefore, from an SEL perspective, the Paris Basin currently stands at a mature stage. Stakeholder engagement has been well integrated into the system, and active trust-building measures are in place. For continued acceptance, it seems important to keep up this level of stakeholder integration.

3.2.1.4 Policy and Regulations

This section focuses on French policies and regulations governing deep geothermal in France.

The Paris Basin's long history with geothermal (since 1969) has created a more favorable political climate (Risiko-Dialog, 2024; Chavot et al., 2021, p. S52). Politically, GE enjoys strong national support, particularly as part of France's target of 38% renewable heating by 2030 (Bouillon-Duparc, 2023). The Ministère de la Transition Énergétique has developed a detailed Action Plan for geothermal energy in the coming years, apparently co-created with all relevant players in the sector and aimed at further promoting geothermal development in France (Cariaga, 2024; Pannier-Runacher, 2023, p. 2).

Generally, geothermal exploration and exploitation are governed by the mining law, which confers natural ownership of natural resources to the French state (Global Geothermal Alliance, 2025). The governance of GE in the Paris Basin is shaped by France's multi-level policy framework, which coordinates national, regional, and local actors. Projects are subject to several assessments, controls and public consultations, with slight procedural differences depending on whether they focus on high or low temperature geothermal (Chavot et al., 2019, p. 114). Specifically, deep geothermal projects over 200 meters have to undergo multiple approval stages, requiring both state and municipal involvement. Mandatory public consultation occurs at several points, including during licensing, exploration, and final project approval (Chavot et al., 2019, p. 114; for details see Chavot et al., 2019, p. 115, Table 1).

However, regulatory complexity and lengthy approval times remain obstacles to faster project deployment (Schmidlé-Bloch et al., 2022, p. 8). Thus, certain efforts are in place to speed up the approval process and reduce permit acquisition time by 50 % (Cariaga, 2024c).

Nevertheless, according to Pannier-Runacher (2023, p. 2), the general policy environment in France is reported to be strongly supportive of geothermal energy. At the national level, the Ministry of Ecological Transition oversees geothermal regulation, while ADEME plays a critical role in funding infrastructure through subsidies and investment programs such as the Fonds Chaleur, which allocates €820 million annually to support renewable heating (European Commission, n.d.; Schmidlé-Bloch et al., 2022, p. 7). The Multi-Year Energy Plan (PPE) reflects strong national commitment, setting a target to double geothermal heat consumption to 5.2 TWh by 2028 by reaching at least 110 active operations (Pannier-Runacher, 2023, p. 2). Key actors also include GEODEEP⁹, a consortium of professional associations focused on GE development, and AFGP, which represents geothermal professionals across various sectors (Schmidlé-Bloch et al., 2022, p. 3).

All in all, France's geothermal sector benefits from strong national policies. From an SEL perspective, the policy and regulatory framework for GE in the Paris Basin can be located at a rather mature stage.

⁹ <https://www.geodeep.fr>

France's policy framework ensures coordination across national, regional, and local levels, with strong public involvement and national commitment reflected in the PPE target to double geothermal heat consumption to 5.2 TWh by 2028. Regulatory and financial support mechanisms, such as ADEME's Fonds Chaleur, further reinforce geothermal development. However, regulatory complexity and lengthy approval times remain significant barriers, hindering faster project deployment despite ongoing efforts to streamline permitting processes and reduce approval times. Further simplification of regulatory procedures might be beneficial to progress towards a higher SEL.

3.2.1.5 Market and Financial Resources

This section focuses on the current market situation of deep geothermal in France.

The financial viability of deep geothermal projects in the Paris Basin is shaped by high upfront costs, strong public subsidies, certain risk mitigation mechanisms, and a stable market base.

At the regional and national levels, agencies such as ADEME and BRGM provide policy alignment, funding, and technical oversight, supporting the long-term viability of geothermal initiatives (Schmidlé-Bloch et al., 2022, p. 7). The private sector, including companies like Dalkia, Engie, Coriance, and IDEX, frequently handles the technical implementation and long-term operation of projects. While some heating networks are managed as public-private ventures, most are operated by these private companies, emphasizing their role in shaping the expansion of geothermal heating (Schmidlé-Bloch et al., 2022, p. 3).

One of the most significant barriers to expansion is the high initial investment cost, estimated at €15 million per geothermal doublet, making public subsidies and risk-sharing mechanisms essential for project feasibility (Grenier, 2024). Due to the high upfront investment costs, especially the political left emphasizes that the sector remains largely dominated by the well-capitalized companies mentioned above (Grenier, 2024). However, to offset a part of these costs, France has developed several financial support mechanisms. One of them, the Fonds Chaleur managed by ADEME, has funded over 678 geothermal projects (Schmidlé-Bloch et al., 2022, p. 7), which has steadily fostered the expansion of geothermal in France (Grenier, 2024). Additionally, ADEME, regional authorities, and municipalities frequently co-finance projects, reducing financial risks for developers and improving project bankability (Schmidlé-Bloch et al., 2022, p. 8). Risk mitigation funds, such as SAF, GEODEEP or the guarantee fund by the Ministry of Ecology, offer protection against drilling failures, ensuring that investors are safeguarded from unpredictable geological risks (Global Geothermal Alliance, 2025).

Moreover, the market base for geothermal heating in the Paris Basin is strong, with 250'000 homes currently using geothermal district heating (Schmidlé-Bloch et al., 2022, p. 3). Due to the funds, heat can be produced at a competitive price compared to the use of fossil fuels (Chavot et al., 2019, p. 111). A tax reduction on renewable heating from 20% to 5.5% lowers financial burdens for consumers, making geothermal heating more attractive for municipalities and housing developments (Bardavid, 2024). This tax policy, combined with state-backed financial support, further reinforces the economic appeal of geothermal energy. Unlike volatile fossil fuel prices, GE offers cost stability over decades, making it an attractive option for municipalities and housing estates looking to hedge against price fluctuations (Energynews, 2024).

Future market growth is expected, as France aims to reach 110 geothermal operations before 2030, and a pipeline of new deep drilling projects, such as Bobigny's Triassic aquifer at 2100m, could further enhance the sector's potential (Pannier-Runacher, 2023, p. 16; Deboyser, 2020). Demand remains steady for heating, with 79 geothermal plants currently operating within the country supplying heat to consumers (Mikalauskas & Stanislovaityte, 2025, p. 243). However, geothermal electricity remains underdeveloped, with only three plants and 17,2 MWe installed (Mikalauskas & Stanislovaityte, 2025, p. 239). This might be due to the fact that geothermal energy was first and foremost explored as a reaction to the oil crisis in the 1980s, looking for a stable heat supply for homes and industries and

thus putting a higher focus on its heating potential instead of the electricity supply potential (Chavot et al., 2019, p. 109). Mikalauskas and Stanislovaityte (2025, p. 238) speak of France as an “emerging” GE market.

Overall, from an SEL perspective, the market and financial environment for deep geothermal in the Paris Basin is at a rather mature stage. Strong public funding, tax incentives, and risk-sharing mechanisms support market development, but high upfront costs and regulatory complexity still pose financial hurdles. The stability of GE prices strengthens its attractiveness, particularly for municipalities and housing estates. However, while demand for geothermal heating is well established, the electricity sector remains underdeveloped, limiting the technology’s full market integration. Further efforts should focus on improving access to private capital, streamlining approval processes to accelerate investment, and exploring ways to scale geothermal electricity production alongside heating projects. Expanding risk-sharing mechanisms, maintaining favorable tax policies, and ensuring continued public funding beyond 2028 will also be key to sustaining long-term growth.

3.2.1.6 Summary Paris Basin

The analysis has shown that the Paris Basin is a leading deep geothermal region in France, supplying 1.7 TWh of annual heat to 250’000 homes (as a comparison, Denmark’s Aarhus heating initiative is supposed to produce heat for the annual demand of 34’000 households (see Denmark Case, section 3.1.1 and section 3.1.1.6). France displays high ambitions (Mikalauskas & Stanislovaityte, 2025, p. 239) but also significant potential for growth to establish itself as Europe’s leader in geothermal energy: Despite its potential, geothermal heating accounted for only 1% of France’s renewable heat consumption in 2021, with the geothermal electricity sector remaining underdeveloped so far. See Figure 5 for a visualization of selected criteria for the case area. The figure emphasizes the pattern rather than specific numerical values. Although there are environmental impacts, such as noise pollution, landscape disruption, and seismic risks, mitigation measures and low carbon emissions support its role in decarbonization. Stakeholder involvement is strong, as national and regional authorities, private companies, and municipalities collaborate effectively. Public trust is higher in Paris than in other regions due to proactive engagement and transparency. France’s policy framework supports geothermal expansion, but regulatory complexity and long approval times could further be optimized. Market growth is driven by public subsidies, risk-sharing mechanisms, and tax incentives, though high upfront costs and limited private investment remain challenges. Advancing to full deployment in terms of SEL requires streamlined regulations, continued stakeholder engagement and increased private capital. Looking at the mature TRL of geothermal in the Paris Basin, a slightly more mature SEL would be required, setting clear development goals for the region's future.

Figure 5: Profile of the French case area for selected criteria.

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3.2.2 Upper Jurassic Carbonate Ramp (Iberian Basin), Spain

For this case study, please refer to Chapter 3.3.3, p.83, as the Upper Jurassic Carbonate Ramp (Iberian Basin) has been analyzed in combination with the Catalan Coastal Range (Vallés Basin) due to their geographical location.

3.2.3 Upper Jurassic Reef-Rimmed Shelf – Southwestern Part of the Swiss Molasse Basin, Switzerland

3.2.3.1 Case Overview

In the following case studies, we use the SEL framework to analyze how socially accepted geothermal projects are in three Swiss regions. These cases illustrate the interplay of public perception, regulatory frameworks, and financial mechanisms in shaping the future of GE in the following three areas: Eclépens, Western Vaud Area (Vinzel/La Côte), and Geneva.

On a national scope Switzerland is advancing GE as part of its transition to renewable energy under Energy Strategy 2050 (Geothermie Schweiz, 2017). While GE is recognized for its baseload reliability, low carbon footprint, and domestic availability, its implementation faces technical, regulatory, and societal challenges. In particular, public perception has emerged as a decisive factor influencing project feasibility.

Public attitudes toward GE in Switzerland are complex. While the general concept of GE is widely accepted, specific projects often encounter resistance due to concerns about induced seismicity, financial risks, and local disruptions (Cousse et al., 2021). Events such as the Basel (2006) and St. Gallen (2013) earthquakes, caused by deep geothermal drilling, have reinforced public skepticism and led to risk perceptions that are disproportionate to actual hazards (Knoblauch et al., 2019). These incidents have shaped media narratives, resulting in a higher degree of opposition in German-speaking Switzerland, where the focus on past failures by induced seismicity like in Basel or St-Gallen has been more pronounced than in the French-speaking Romandie, where support remains stronger (although unsuccessful outcomes (in Lavey, Vinzel) have also driven debates (and some newspaper articles). Still, general support for geothermal initiatives stays high (Manzella et al., 2019).

Recent research emphasizes the role of context and framing in shaping public acceptance. Risk perception is not solely based on objective hazard levels but is influenced by how projects are

communicated and the degree of local involvement (Ejderyan, 2019). Studies indicate that projects emphasizing local energy security, district heating, and direct community benefits are perceived more positively than those focusing on electricity production for the national grid (Knoblauch et al., 2019). Acceptance is also linked to prior experience with infrastructure projects – regions with a history of negative interactions with large-scale developments tend to exhibit lower trust in authorities and project developers (Cousse et al., 2021).

The regulatory landscape plays a key role in geothermal development. Switzerland's federal energy policy supports geothermal exploration through subsidies and risk-sharing mechanisms, but implementation is largely determined at the cantonal level. In Geneva and Vaud, GE has been integrated into district heating expansion plans, benefiting from structured frameworks for public-private partnerships and long-term policy commitments (PDE_Genève, 2020; CoCEn_Vaud, 2019). However, other regions remain hesitant due to public opposition, lack of subsurface data, and regulatory uncertainty (Manzella et al., 2019). The Swiss government has introduced financial guarantees for geothermal electricity projects, yet high drilling costs and geological unpredictability continue to pose barriers (SFOE, 2024).

Switzerland's experience highlights the importance of effective risk communication, early stakeholder engagement, and policy stability in securing public support for geothermal energy.

3.2.3.2 Eclépens Area

3.2.3.2.1 *Impact on the Environment*

The GeoCogen Eclépens project, led by Swiss Geo Energy (SGE), is a deep geothermal initiative aimed at producing renewable heat and electricity. The site was selected due to high underground temperatures exceeding 110°C at 2,100 meters depth, making it one of the most promising geothermal locations in the Canton of Vaud (Swiss Geo Energy, n.d.).

The hydrothermal technology used does not require hydraulic stimulation (fracking), reducing potential environmental risks. However, seismic activity remains a concern, as past geothermal projects in Switzerland – such as in Basel and St. Gallen – experienced induced seismicity. Geo2X SA, the company responsible for 3D seismic acquisition (active seismic), planned real-time vibration monitoring¹⁰ and intensity adjustments based on proximity to buildings (Cariaga, 2023). However, the proper seismic monitoring phase has not yet started. It is scheduled to begin approximately six months before drilling, in line with requirements from the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) and will involve installing multiple seismic stations in the area in collaboration with the Swiss Seismological Service (SED) (RTS, 2023).

Additionally, the Canton of Vaud's energy strategy (CoCEn_Vaud, 2019) recognizes the potential of GE as a key component of the 50% renewable energy target by 2050. However, it emphasizes the need for strict groundwater protection measures, particularly in regions like Eclépens where subsurface exploration has a long history dating back to oil drilling in the 1970s (Lapierre, 2023).

3.2.3.2.2 *Stakeholder Involvement*

The GeoCogen Eclépens project involves multiple stakeholders, including Swiss Geo Energy (SGE), which leads the project, and Geo2X SA, responsible for conducting seismic surveys. Holcim, though

¹⁰ It's important to note that the seismic acquisition, which is used to create a 3D image of the subsurface, has nothing to do with induced seismicity. This means it cannot cause earthquakes, even small ones. So, there's no need for seismic monitoring. Instead, the "monitoring" involves taking measurements of buildings, especially old ones, to make sure that the structures don't get damaged.

not a direct investor, is involved as its district heating network is expected to integrate geothermal heat from Eclépens (Lapierre, 2023).

Public communication efforts have been proactive, with information sessions and demonstrations organized in La Sarraz and other communities to address residents' concerns (Laurent & Marty, 2023). Several "informative" sessions have been organized, as well as an "open day" for anyone interested. The open day showed the project's objectives and provided practical information about 3D seismic acquisition. For example, there were demonstrations of receivers and vibrotrucks. These were complemented by additional measures such as explanatory videos outlining key project steps and disciplines involved, flyers distributed to local populations, and a dedicated hotline during seismic operations.

Eclépens has also witnessed strong environmental activism in the recent past. In 2021, a protest camp opposed Holcim's expansion, citing risks to local ecosystems (Berner Zeitung, 2021). While this protest was unrelated to geothermal energy, it signals a general sensitivity to environmental issues in the region, which could influence public perception of the project. Given this history, the CoCEn_Vaud (2019) report emphasizes the importance of early and transparent engagement with local communities to preempt opposition and facilitate public trust in geothermal projects.

3.2.3.2.3 Policy and Regulations

The GeoCogen Eclépens project operates under the Cantonal Law on Subsurface Natural Resources (LRNSS, 2018), which governs subsurface activities in Vaud. The State of Vaud granted Swiss Geo Energy a permit for the prospection phase, covering a 100 km² area and allowing for surface-based activities such as seismic surveys and geological mapping (Cariaga, 2023). If promising geothermal reservoirs are identified, the company will need to apply for a subsurface research permit (PRSS) to begin the exploration phase, which involves drilling.

The Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) supports geothermal projects by subsidizing up to 60% of exploration costs. Projects receiving public funding are required to make their data publicly available – seismic data after 24 months, and drilling-related data within 12 months of acquisition (Lapierre, 2023). Regulatory support for GE in Vaud, as outlined in CoCEn_Vaud (2019), aims to de-risk private investment while ensuring that geothermal projects meet environmental and public safety standards.

The Eclépens project benefits from Vaud's exclusive geothermal exploration zones, where companies compete for permits based on technical and financial viability. However, exploration remains financially risky due to uncertainties in locating economically viable heat sources (Lapierre, 2023).

3.2.3.2.4 Market and Financial Resources

Swiss Geo Energy is backed by private investors and has dedicated significant financial resources to the GeoCogen Eclépens project (RTS, 2023; Lapierre, 2023). The initiative aims to:

- Supply heat to 5,000 households and businesses.
- Generate electricity for approximately 3,700 homes, feeding into the Swiss power grid (Swiss Geo Energy, n.d.).

Despite strong financial support, geothermal exploration is inherently high-risk. Similar projects in Vinzel, Lavey, and Montagny encountered challenges, such as unexpectedly low water temperatures, affecting economic feasibility (Lapierre, 2023).

- To address these risks, the Canton of Vaud's energy strategy includes:
- Public-private partnerships to distribute financial risks.
- Flexible regulatory frameworks to adapt to new geological findings.
- Support for technological advancements, such as 3D seismic mapping, to improve exploration success rates (CoCEn_Vaud, 2019).

Due to space limitations, only a brief overview is provided here. For more detailed information, refer to the relevant policy document, CoCEn_Vaud (see the references section for the link).

3.2.3.3 Western Vaud Area (Vinzel/La Côte)

3.2.3.3.1 *Impact on the Environment*

The Western Vaud region has been identified as a strategic area for medium-depth geothermal development, particularly in Vinzel and La Côte, where naturally permeable geological formations in the Dogger and Malm aquifers allow for hydrothermal energy extraction without the need for hydraulic stimulation (fracking) (EnergieÖ, 2025).

The Vinzel project, led by EnergieÖ, encountered an exceptional water flow rate of 150 liters per second, one of the highest recorded in Europe. However, the measured temperature of 33°C was significantly lower than the expected 50°C, necessitating a reassessment of its feasibility for direct district heating use (Geothermie Schweiz, 2023). The project has now entered a strategic evaluation phase, working closely with federal and cantonal authorities to identify potential solutions (EnergieÖ, 2025).

The La Côte geothermal project is currently focused on subsurface mapping and seismic surveys to assess fault structures and aquifer properties. The 2021 2D seismic survey confirmed promising geothermal potential, prompting a planned 3D seismic survey in 2025 to refine drilling targets and minimize environmental risks (Geothermie Schweiz, 2024).

The CoCEn_Vaud (2019) report underscores the necessity of comprehensive environmental impact assessments (EIAs), emphasizing groundwater protection, seismic risk mitigation, and sustainable geothermal resource management. The ongoing GEOBEST 2020+ project, funded by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) and implemented by ETH Zurich, is actively monitoring seismic activity in Vinzel and the surrounding region to ensure that geothermal activities remain environmentally safe (Schweizerischer Erdbebendienst & ETH Zürich, n.d.).

3.2.3.3.2 *Stakeholder Involvement*

The Vinzel and La Côte geothermal projects involve multiple stakeholders, including EnergieÖ, which oversees project development, and Geo2X SA, responsible for seismic surveying and geological modeling (Geothermie Schweiz, 2025). The Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) has provided financial subsidies to support geothermal exploration, while the Canton of Vaud regulates project implementation under its exclusive geothermal exploration zones framework (CoCEn_Vaud, 2019).

The Vinzel geothermal site was chosen following extensive feasibility studies, with most of the geological work – including geological analysis, seismic interpretation, and target definition – carried out by the local company Hydro-Géo Environnement (Hydro-Geo Environment, n.d.). ERDWERK GmbH joined the project consortium at a later stage to support drilling preparation and site construction (ERDWERK GmbH, n.d.). These geological assessments guided the decision to redirect drilling from the Dogger aquifer to the Malm aquifer, ultimately resulting in the discovery of a high water flow rate at a depth of 1,500 meters.

The CoCEn_Vaud (2019) energy framework emphasizes the need for co-designing processes in geothermal projects, advocating for municipalities, businesses, and local communities to play an active role in shaping project decisions. This principle is being applied in La Côte, where subsurface exploration is being conducted in coordination with local authorities to optimize future drilling sites while maintaining ongoing public dialogue (Geothermie Schweiz, 2024).

3.2.3.3.3 *Policy and Regulations*

Geothermal projects in Western Vaud operate under the previously mentioned “Loi sur les Ressources Naturelles du Sous-Sol” (LRNSS, 2018), which provides a structured permit system for exploration and energy production. The regulatory process follows three key stages:

- Surface research permits (PRSU) – Authorizing geophysical surveys and exploratory drilling for data collection.
- Subsurface research permits (PRSS) – Required for deeper drilling if preliminary surveys indicate geothermal viability.
- Production concessions – Granted for 30–50 years if commercial feasibility is confirmed (CoCEn_Vaud, 2019).

In contrast to deep geothermal projects in Basel and St. Gallen, which faced seismic concerns, Western Vaud's projects emphasize naturally permeable hydrothermal reservoirs that do not require artificial stimulation. However, the unexpectedly low temperatures in Vinzel have prompted discussions on modifying regulatory frameworks to accommodate lower-temperature geothermal integration within district heating models (Geothermie Schweiz, 2023).

The CoCEn_Vaud (2019) report highlights the need for adaptable regulatory structures to support geothermal initiatives that deviate from initial expectations. The canton is also exploring policy adjustments to incentivize geothermal projects with lower temperatures but high water flows, potentially integrating them into hybrid heating systems that combine geothermal with waste heat recovery.

3.2.3.3.4 *Market and Financial Resources*

The Western Vaud geothermal projects rely on public and private funding, with EnergieÖ leading private investments and the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) providing subsidies for exploratory drilling. However, the unexpected results in Vinzel have raised financial uncertainties, delaying the transition to full-scale production (EnergieÖ, 2025).

The La Côte project, still in the exploration phase, has received strong financial support due to potential deeper, higher-temperature reservoirs. The planned 2025 3D seismic mapping campaign aims to refine drilling strategies, improve exploration success rates, and attract further private investment (Geothermie Schweiz, 2024).

3.2.3.4 *Geneva Area*

3.2.3.4.1 *Impact on the Environment*

Geneva has identified a significant geothermal potential of 2,820 GWh/year, but only 10 GWh/year is currently utilized, leaving an untapped capacity of 2,810 GWh/year (PDE_Genève, 2020). To leverage this potential, the canton has prioritized geothermal development as part of its long-term energy strategy, aiming for 150 GWh/year of GE production by 2030 and 20% of heating demand supplied by GE by 2050 (Canton de Genève, 2020).

The environmental impact of geothermal projects is carefully managed through a strict regulatory framework. The Plan Directeur de l'Énergie 2020-2030 (PDE_Genève, 2020) underscores the importance of seismic risk assessments, groundwater protection, and sustainable resource management. The canton has implemented a seismic monitoring network, operated by the SED and ETH Zurich, to track natural and induced seismicity in the Geneva Basin. This monitoring is essential to ensure that geothermal drilling does not trigger seismic events similar to those observed in Basel and St. Gallen (Schweizerischer Erdbebendienst & ETH Zürich, n.d.).

Geothermal projects in Geneva are integrated into district heating networks to enhance energy efficiency. The SIG (Services Industriels de Genève) network is expanding to 250 km by 2030, with a goal of covering 50% of the canton's heating demand with renewable energy by 2050 (Scuderi & Etienne, 2025). The canton has also developed innovative solutions, such as waste heat recovery from data centers and wastewater treatment plants, to complement GE sources and ensure a stable renewable energy supply.

3.2.3.4.2 Stakeholder Involvement

The Geneva geothermal program is a collaboration between the Canton of Geneva and SIG (Services Industriels de Genève). The initiative is part of the GEothermies program, which began as GEothermie2020 in 2014 and has since evolved into a broader framework for geothermal development in the region (GEothermies, n.d.). The Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) has also provided significant support, allocating 27.5 million CHF in funding for geothermal prospecting (Bundesamt für Energie, 2020).

Public engagement is a critical component of Geneva's geothermal strategy. The official platform www.geothermies.ch provides project updates, information on exploration campaigns, and details on upcoming public consultation events (Kanton Genf, n.d.). Lessons from past controversies, such as public resistance to seismic surveys, have informed Geneva's current approach to transparent communication and proactive public involvement.

The Geneva Energy Master Plan encourages multi-stakeholder collaboration, involving municipal governments, industry partners, and academic institutions in decision-making. The PDE_Genève (2020) emphasizes that the success of geothermal integration depends on maintaining a balanced dialogue between energy producers, local authorities, and the public.

3.2.3.4.3 Policy and Regulations

Geneva's geothermal development follows a structured regulatory pathway. Like the regulatory framework for the canton Vaud (CoCEn_Vaud, 2019), the PDE_Genève (2020) defines targets, regulations, and financial mechanisms to support geothermal expansion. Key elements of Geneva's regulatory framework include:

Exploration and drilling permits: Issued by the canton, ensuring compliance with environmental and safety standards.

Seismic monitoring requirements: All projects must be assessed for potential seismic risks before, during, and after drilling.

Public funding eligibility: Projects receiving subsidies must contribute to Geneva's renewable energy targets and undergo periodic evaluations.

Integration with district heating networks: The PDE_Genève (2020) stipulates that geothermal projects prioritize direct heat usage to maximize efficiency and reduce dependence on fossil fuels.

Geneva's regulatory framework differs from Vaud's in its focus on urban energy infrastructure and cross-border cooperation. Recent 2D and 3D seismic surveys (2021-2023) have explored geothermal structures extending into France, raising the possibility of binational geothermal projects (GEothermies, n.d.).

3.2.3.4.4 Market and Financial Resources

The Geneva geothermal sector is supported by public funding, private investment, and federal subsidies. The Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) has played a crucial role in de-risking exploration projects by providing financial assistance for feasibility studies and test drilling (Bundesamt für Energie, 2020).

The Satigny and Lully exploration wells, completed in 2018 and 2020, confirmed the presence of geothermal resources. The Geo-01 well in Satigny encountered a notable water flow from a fractured zone, although at relatively shallow depth and thus low temperature. The Lully well, drilled to 1,456 meters, found 53°C water but with limited flow rates, underscoring the need for detailed geological assessments before full-scale development (GEothermies, n.d.).

To attract further investment, the canton is implementing financial mechanisms such as:

- Guaranteed feed-in tariffs for geothermal heat integrated into district heating.
- Incentives for infrastructure development, ensuring that new buildings are designed to connect to geothermal networks. (PDE_Genève, 2020)

Despite strong financial support, challenges remain. Unlike Germany or France, Switzerland lacks a history of broad oil and gas exploration, limiting subsurface knowledge. Each new geothermal drilling project contributes valuable geological data, gradually improving understanding of Geneva's underground resources (Geothermie Schweiz, 2022).

3.2.3.5 Summary Swiss Molasse Basin, Switzerland

Switzerland's deep GE projects vary in their degree of societal embeddedness, depending on regional conditions and the interaction of environmental concerns, public involvement, regulatory frameworks, and financial structures (see Figure 6 for a visualization of selected criteria for all three case areas. The figure emphasizes the pattern rather than specific numerical values).

In **Eclépens**, the GeoCogen project builds on favorable geological conditions without the need for hydraulic stimulation. Geo2X SA was responsible for the 3D seismic acquisition (active seismic). Seismic monitoring phase is planned to begin approximately six months prior to drilling, in line with Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) requirements and will involve the installation of multiple seismic stations in the area in collaboration with the SED. Public engagement has included information events and collaboration with Holcim's district heating system, but the region has seen recent environmental protests unrelated to geothermal energy, suggesting a general sensitivity that could resurface. The regulatory framework is well defined, with exploration zones and financial support in place, but uncertainty about subsurface conditions and the absence of demonstrated public support place the project in a stage of Development.

In the **Western Vaud area** (Vinzell and La Côte), geothermal projects focus on medium-depth hydrothermal resources with naturally permeable aquifers, avoiding the need for fracking. The Vinzell site produced exceptionally high water flow, but unexpectedly low temperatures undermined the original heating goals, delaying further development. Seismic monitoring is comprehensive, supported by the GEOBEST 2020+ project, and additional 3D surveys are planned. Stakeholder involvement is active, with municipalities participating and regular public outreach in place. Still, the projects remain in an exploratory and planning phase, with no confirmed delivery of energy to local populations or long-term societal benefits. The canton is adjusting its regulatory approach to support low-temperature projects, but financial feasibility remains uncertain.

In **Geneva**, GE plays a prominent role in the canton's long-term energy strategy. The region has significant theoretical potential, and targets for 2030 and 2050 aim to increase its share in the heating mix. Environmental risks are addressed through mandatory seismic monitoring and integration into a district heating network. Stakeholder processes are well established, with public consultations, inter-institutional coordination, and the GEothermies platform ensuring transparency. The regulatory framework is coherent and linked to policy targets, with incentives for integration into urban heating systems. However, geothermal energy currently contributes only a small fraction of Geneva's energy needs, and tangible benefits for the public remain limited. While the canton has taken meaningful

steps toward broad societal acceptance, the actual anchoring of GE in daily life is still at an early stage.

At the national level, the Swiss Energy Strategy 2050 and federal legislation explicitly support geothermal development, offering subsidies, risk guarantees, and long-term policy support. However, implementation is delegated to the cantons, where significant disparities remain. Cantons like Geneva and Vaud have developed structured legal and institutional frameworks to promote geothermal energy, while others fall behind due to public resistance, regulatory uncertainty, or a lack of comprehensive geological data. This uneven regional translation of federal goals contributes directly to the differing levels of societal embeddedness across Switzerland.

A cautious assessment places all three regions in the Development phase. Eclépens and Western Vaud are in early to mid-Development, with promising structures but limited societal anchoring. Geneva is at the upper end of Development, approaching Demonstration, due to its integrated policy approach and advanced stakeholder processes. However, none of the projects has yet reached a point where GE is widely accepted, socially embedded, and providing visible public value – a key requirement for higher SEL levels.

Figure 6: Profiles of the three case areas in Switzerland for selected criteria.

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3.2.4 Triassic Dolomites and Limestone – Southern Part of the Vienna Basin, Austria

3.2.4.1 Case Overview

At present, there are no advanced deep geothermal projects with publicly available data underway in the southern Vienna Basin (Südliches Wiener Becken). While the region is geologically suitable for deep geothermal development – featuring thermal aquifers and a long history of balneological use – concrete projects remain in early phases. Feasibility studies and exploratory initiatives have been undertaken, in particular by EVN Wärme and – to a lesser degree – in the context of the Klima- und Energie-Modellregion “Thermenregion” (EVN, 2023; Götzl & Hengel, 2024). These activities have not

yet reached a mature stage in terms of SEL dimensions – such as stakeholder consultation, risk communication, or regulatory implementation – can be empirically analyzed. However, since February 2025, EVN has begun informing the mayors of communities that may be affected by exploration or drilling. Public events for citizens will start in the first quarter of 2026.

In the absence of such data, this case study draws on the geothermal project currently being developed in Vienna's Aspern district. While situated in the northern Vienna Basin, the project offers valuable insights into how deep GE is embedded within Austria's institutional and societal frameworks. As Vienna's first large-scale geothermal heating project, it involves cooperation between municipal and private actors (Wien Energie and OMV), as well as structured public communication and permitting processes (OMV, 2023). These features make it a suitable reference case for examining the SEL dimensions of geothermal development under current Austrian conditions.

At the same time, it is important to acknowledge that stakeholder constellations in the southern Vienna Basin may differ in relevant ways. The region includes smaller municipalities and semi-urban or rural areas, in contrast to Aspern's urban and municipally integrated setting. While it cannot be assumed that public attitudes, institutional trust, or risk perceptions are fundamentally different, the governance structures, land use priorities, and socio-spatial characteristics of the southern basin may shape stakeholder engagement in context-specific ways (BMK, 2022). In particular, the presence of spa tourism, agricultural land use, and more decentralized administrative structures could influence the design and reception of participation processes and the framing of environmental concerns.

The Aspern project is therefore not presented as a direct blueprint but rather as an indicative case for analyzing currently observable practices related to stakeholder engagement, environmental assessment, and institutional coordination in Austria's geothermal sector. These findings may inform future analysis and project development in the southern Vienna Basin once projects there proceed beyond their exploration phase.

The Aspern geothermal project, located in the northern part of the Vienna Basin, is further advanced in development. Information about this project might hint at the challenges and opportunities faced by upcoming projects in the southern area of the Vienna Basin. The project, led by Wien Energie and OMV under the joint venture "Deeep," is expected to provide 20 MW of thermal energy to supply district heating for up to 20,000 households (OMV, 2024). By 2040, six additional plants are planned to serve 200,000 households (News.at, 2025).

The project received €90 million in funding, including environmental subsidies from the Austrian Ministry for Climate Protection (OMV, 2024). Drilling is scheduled to begin in Winter 2024/2025, with initial exploratory wells determining the viability of further investments (Wien Energie, 2025).

3.2.4.2 Impact on the Environment

The key areas of concern include potential noise disturbances, aesthetic considerations, pollution risks, land use impact, water quality, and the possibility of induced seismicity (Sprenkeling et al., 2022). Available data indicates that environmental risks associated with geothermal development in this region are minimal. This is largely due to advanced drilling techniques, strict containment measures, and real-time monitoring systems.

One major concern in GE projects is noise pollution, particularly during the drilling phase. However, Wien Energie states that due to the drilling method used in the Aspern project, no significant surface impacts, such as vibrations, noise, or air emissions, are expected. The borehole first extends vertically to a depth of approximately 1,000 meters, after which it is directionally drilled to reach a final depth of around 3,500 meters. This approach reduces the impact at the surface, ensuring that local residents and surrounding infrastructure are not affected by drilling-related disturbances (Wien Energie, 2025).

The aesthetic impact of the geothermal infrastructure is considered low, as the Aspern project has been designed to minimize visual intrusion. No reports indicate public opposition due to visual concerns, and Wien Energie's communication strategy has focused on highlighting the environmental benefits of geothermal heating rather than its physical footprint (Wien Energie, 2025). Unlike wind farms or large-scale solar installations, geothermal plants occupy a relatively small surface area, making them a less obtrusive addition to the urban environment.

A key concern for many geothermal projects worldwide is pollution, particularly in relation to water contamination and the protection of ecosystems, mainly in the context of hydraulic stimulation. In the case of Aspern, no hydraulic stimulation (external water injected into the reservoir) is planned. Instead, the system relies on the naturally occurring permeability, the extracted hot water is reinjected into the same geological formation to maintain reservoir pressure and prevent depletion (News.at, 2025). Hence, no significant pollution risks are associated with the project. Additionally, comprehensive seismic monitoring measures have been implemented to detect any potential underground changes that could lead to environmental risks (Wien Energie, n.d.).

Water quality is often a major factor in assessing the viability of GE projects. In Austria, concerns regarding the potential interaction between geothermal extraction and groundwater reserves have been carefully addressed. According to Wien Energie, usable groundwater and geothermal reservoirs are completely isolated from each other. The Aderklaaer Conglomerate geothermal reservoir, located at a depth of approximately 3,500 meters, bears high-salinity water and has no interaction with shallow groundwater, which typically flows at depths between 10 and 40 meters (Wien Energie, 2025). This means that geothermal extraction has no impact on Austria's drinking water supply or groundwater ecosystems.

To further ensure water protection, multiple safety barriers are in place to completely seal off the borehole from groundwater layers. These include protective casing, specialized sealing materials, and strict containment procedures that prevent any contamination risks (Wien Energie, 2025). During drilling, the only point at which the borehole intersects groundwater layers is at the drilling site itself, where additional protective layers have been installed to prevent leaks. In addition, surface contamination is prevented using sealed drilling areas and controlled containment systems (Wien Energie, 2025). Based on these measures, concerns about groundwater contamination are not an issue for the Aspern project.

Another commonly debated issue in GE projects is induced seismicity, where deep drilling and water reinjection could potentially trigger minor earthquakes. Due to the geological conditions of the (Northern) Vienna Basin, the risk of induced seismic activity has been evaluated as low. Extensive seismic modeling studies conducted using 3D geological mapping and real-time monitoring technology indicate that no significant seismic events are expected (GeoSphere Austria, n.d.). Additionally, a dedicated monitoring system has been installed by GeoSphere Austria, ensuring that any unusual seismic activity can be detected and addressed immediately (News.at, 2025). Unlike other geothermal projects that involve high-pressure water reinjection, the Aspern project does not introduce external water into the subsurface, thereby further reducing the likelihood of induced seismicity. These efforts not only intend to increase the general safety of deep geothermal projects but also the trust of the local community.

From an SEL perspective, the environmental impact of geothermal heating in Vienna is at the demonstration stage. The risk-mitigation measures implemented in the Aspern project have successfully addressed key environmental concerns, including seismic activity, water contamination, and pollution risks. While extensive safety measures are in place, further long-term monitoring will be essential to ensure continued environmental protection and stakeholder confidence.

3.2.4.3 Stakeholder Involvement

Stakeholder involvement plays a crucial role in the acceptance and successful implementation of geothermal projects. The Aspern project in Vienna has benefited from proactive communication strategies and structured public engagement efforts. Despite this, some challenges remain, including residual distrust from past project failures, the need for enhanced knowledge transfer, and labor shortages in the geothermal sector.

One of the most critical aspects of stakeholder involvement is the identification of key actors. The direct stakeholders in the Aspern geothermal project include Wien Energie, OMV, GeoSphere Austria, the City of Vienna, and the Ministry for Climate Protection, all of whom play an active role in project planning, implementation, and oversight (Wien Energie, 2025). Indirect stakeholders include residents, district heating customers, industrial energy users, and environmental groups, whose support is essential for ensuring public acceptance of the project (GeoTief Wien, 2025). Unlike in some other geothermal projects, where industries that rely on groundwater might be considered involuntary stakeholders, this is not the case in Austria. Due to the complete isolation of the geothermal reservoir from shallow groundwater sources, no conflicts exist between GE production and groundwater-dependent industries (Wien Energie, 2025).

A key factor influencing public perception of geothermal projects is knowledge and awareness. In Austria, public knowledge of GE is moderate to high, largely due to media coverage and online resources provided by Wien Energie and other stakeholders (Salzburger Nachrichten, 2024). One particularly important initiative is the Geothermal Atlas (GeoSphere Austria, 2024; Salzburger Nachrichten, 2024), which provides residents with insights into their local geothermal potential. However, it is important to note that this platform is specifically designed for shallow geothermal projects, which are intended to complement the district heating network rather than replace it.

The communication strategy for the Aspern project has been a key factor in building trust with the public. Wien Energie and OMV provide extensive public engagement through their websites and FAQ sections, which address common concerns about GE (Wien Energie, 2025). To further increase transparency, a visitor center has been established in early 2025 at the Aspern drilling site, allowing residents to gain firsthand insights into the project's operations (Krois, 2024). However, while communication efforts carried out by OMV and Wienenergie have been visible, no specific outreach programs have been documented for rural areas or other regions where geothermal expansion might take place in the future, especially in the Southern Area of the Vienna Basin.

A central element of stakeholder engagement is the degree of public influence over decision-making. In Austria, there have been no recorded public referendums or major protests against GE projects. However, early stakeholder engagement is recommended due to concerns about potential seismic risks in the Southern Vienna Basin (News.at, 2025). While experts confirm that the risk of induced seismicity is low, public fears surrounding earthquakes triggered by deep drilling are a source of opposition in other geothermal projects worldwide (cf. Manzella et al., 2019). Therefore, ensuring that local communities are well-informed and actively involved in discussions about seismic monitoring and risk mitigation will be crucial for future project acceptance.

Another important consideration is the public perception of risk versus benefit. The Austrian government has introduced financial incentives and policy measures to encourage geothermal adoption, which is expected to increase public trust in the long-term benefits of the technology (Sponring et al., 2023). However, historical skepticism remains due to a failed deep drilling attempt in 2012, when unexpected geological conditions forced the project to be abandoned (News.at, 2025).

Public trust in GE is generally positive, largely due to transparent communication and government backing. Positive media coverage and public information campaigns have helped build confidence in the Aspern project (Wien Energie, 2025). However, some level of distrust remains, particularly among

those who remember past failures or who question the long-term stability of geothermal heating (News.at, 2025). A key challenge for future projects will be ensuring that trust is maintained through continuous stakeholder engagement and education initiatives.

In terms of safety, the Aspern project incorporates comprehensive seismic monitoring and mitigation measures, which exceed standard safety requirements (GeoSphere Austria, n.d.). No major safety concerns have been raised by regulatory agencies, and the combination of real-time monitoring systems, controlled drilling procedures, and advanced geological assessments ensures that risks are minimized (Wien Energie, 2025).

Several further factors influence stakeholder perceptions of geothermal energy. Emotional and psychological aspects play a role in public attitudes, particularly among communities that have experienced past failures, like the one in 2012, or have concerns about long-term environmental impacts (News.at, 2025). Place attachment is not a major issue in this case, as the Aspern project is located in an urban development zone, where industrial activities are already part of the landscape. However, energy justice considerations remain relevant, as geothermal expansion aims to provide affordable, low-carbon heating solutions to a growing number of households, particularly in Vienna's district heating network (Salzburger Nachrichten, 2024).

From an SEL perspective, stakeholder involvement in Austria's geothermal sector is at the demonstration stage. Public trust in the Aspern project is strong, and effective communication strategies have been implemented, but residual concerns from past failures and possible gaps in public knowledge could still pose challenges towards the implementation of new geothermal projects. To advance to the deployment stage, future efforts should focus on expanding outreach to rural areas, addressing the labor shortage in geothermal fields, and strengthening knowledge transfer initiatives to improve public understanding of deep geothermal technologies.

3.2.4.4 Policy and Regulations

The regulatory framework for GE in Austria shows both promising opportunities and structural challenges, particularly for deep geothermal development in areas such as the Vienna Basin. The legal responsibilities are distributed across federal, provincial, and municipal levels. While this multi-level governance allows for local adaptation, it also leads to fragmented procedures and uncertainties in the approval process – one of the main reasons why geothermal expansion has been slow (Bundesministerium für Klimaschutz, Umwelt, Energie, Mobilität, Innovation und Technologie, 2024; Rajal & Barabas, 2025).

Although GE is formally recognized as a renewable source under the Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz (EAG), the law predominantly focuses on technologies like solar photovoltaics, wind, and hydropower. As a result, geothermal projects – especially those aiming at heating rather than electricity production – are often marginalized in national policy instruments. This lack of specific regulatory attention contributes to a situation in which geothermal initiatives face unclear pathways for approval and limited eligibility for subsidies or market premiums (Sponring et al., 2023; ICLG, 2024). Moreover, GE has not yet been classified as a strategic resource under federal law, in contrast to fossil energy sources like oil and gas. This absence of prioritization limits the technology's visibility in strategic planning and hinders the implementation of targeted legislative support.

The complexity of geothermal regulation in Austria is further complicated by legal provisions regarding subsurface ownership. Under Austrian law, geothermal heat is treated as part of the property, meaning that it belongs to the landowner. This "grundeigen" principle becomes especially problematic in cases where directional drilling is necessary, as projects may require negotiation with multiple property owners. These legal hurdles slow down project timelines and increase financial uncertainty, particularly in densely settled areas or where geological conditions demand horizontal drilling (Rajal & Barabas, 2025).

Austria's National Energy and Climate Plan (BMK, 2024) acknowledges that the fragmented regulatory landscape is one of the most significant obstacles to geothermal development. Planning and permitting processes for GE are spread across a wide array of sectoral laws, including those governing environmental protection, building codes, water rights, and mineral resources. These regulations vary by province, leading to inconsistency and inefficiency in project development. To address this, the NEKP advocates for greater coordination between governance levels and a streamlining of procedures through standardization of data protocols and more transparent approval pathways (BMK, 2024).

In an effort to improve the regulatory environment, several legislative reforms have been announced. The proposed Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Beschleunigungsgesetz (EABG) aims to expedite permitting procedures for renewable energy projects, including geothermal, through mechanisms like one-stop-shop approvals and simplified environmental impact assessments. Similarly, planned amendments to the Mineral Resources Act and the Water Rights Act are expected to clarify the legal framework around the use of underground thermal reservoirs and the associated access rights (Rajal & Barabas, 2025). While these reforms reflect a growing political interest in enhancing geothermal regulation, they are still under parliamentary review and have yet to be enacted.

In parallel, the revised EU Energy Efficiency Directive introduces new obligations for municipalities to develop local heating and cooling plans. These plans, once implemented, are expected to serve as important instruments for identifying geothermal potential and facilitating its integration into district heating networks. Their role is not only technical but also strategic, helping to align local infrastructure with national climate goals and renewable energy targets. The integration of geothermal into such plans is especially important in urban contexts like Vienna, where the expansion of district heating is a core element of decarbonization efforts (BMK, 2024).

Despite these policy efforts, legal uncertainty remains a central challenge. According to the International Comparative Legal Guides (2024), Austria's geothermal regulatory regime continues to be shaped by a series of overlapping and often ambiguous legal instruments. Developers must navigate multiple layers of jurisdiction and a wide range of sector-specific laws. This situation results in costly and time-consuming approval processes, particularly for deep geothermal projects, which tend to involve more complex technical and environmental assessments.

From an SEL perspective, the current state of geothermal regulation in Austria corresponds to the development-to-demonstration phase. Political support is clearly present, and legislative initiatives are underway, but the implementation and integration of these reforms into a coherent framework remains a work in progress. Legal inconsistencies, coordination challenges between federal and provincial authorities, and the absence of targeted regulatory instruments continue to act as barriers to broader deployment. Whether Austria will succeed in transitioning toward a more integrated and effective regulatory system for GE depends largely on the political follow-through on announced reforms and the establishment of unified national standards.

Importantly, with the end of the main research phase, the new Austrian government, which took effect in the first quarter of 2025, aims to develop a federal geothermal strategy (Bundesstrategie Geothermie, see <https://www.bmb.gv.at/Themen/regierungsprogramm.html>).

3.2.4.5 Market and Financial Resources

One of the most significant financial challenges for geothermal projects in Austria is the high initial investment required for deep drilling and infrastructure development. The Aspern project, for example, has an estimated total investment cost of €90 million, which includes drilling, infrastructure setup, and operational integration into the district heating system (News.at, 2025). These capital-intensive requirements make it difficult for smaller investors and municipal energy providers to finance geothermal projects without substantial government support (Sponring et al., 2023). Unlike wind and solar energy, which benefit from well-established subsidy schemes, GE in Austria does not yet have a comprehensive financial incentive structure (Salzburger Nachrichten, 2024).

Currently, government funding mechanisms for geothermal projects are limited compared to other renewable energy technologies. While the Climate and Energy Fund provides some financial support for feasibility studies and research projects, it does not yet offer direct subsidies for commercial-scale geothermal plants (News.at, 2025). However, the Austrian government has announced plans to expand funding options through the Climate and Energy Fund starting by 2024, which could include state-backed financial guarantees and risk-mitigation measures for geothermal developers (Sponring et al., 2023).

According to the National Energy and Climate Plan (NEKP), Austria aims to establish tailored financing instruments for GE under the Environmental Subsidies Act and the expanded Climate and Energy Fund. The plan envisions a combination of co-financing, investment grants, and risk-sharing instruments to support deep geothermal development. A total of €151.9 million is allocated annually for renewable energy projects, alongside an additional €250 million in special funds until 2026, a portion of which is designated for geothermal initiatives (BMK, 2024).

A critical financial risk for geothermal developers is the uncertainty surrounding exploratory drilling success. Unlike wind or solar projects, which have predictable energy yields, geothermal drilling carries the risk of encountering insufficient heat or water flow, making financial planning more complex (Salzburger Nachrichten, 2024). In Austria, there is no publicly available insurance mechanism to cover the financial losses associated with unsuccessful drilling attempts, meaning that developers must absorb the full cost of failed projects (Sponring et al., 2023). In contrast, some other European countries, such as France and Germany, offer state-backed insurance programs that reduce the financial risks associated with geothermal exploration. The lack of such financial instruments in Austria discourages private investment, as developers face potentially high sunk costs if a project does not yield the expected geothermal output.

Market demand for geothermal heating is steadily increasing, particularly in Vienna, where the city is actively working to decarbonize its district heating network. Approximately 460,000 households currently rely on district heating, with 42% of this energy coming from renewable sources (News.at, 2025). The city of Vienna aims to increase this share to 60% by 2040, and GE is expected to play a key role in achieving this target (Salzburger Nachrichten, 2024).

Another important development is the Austrian government's plan to review and potentially reform the current system of grid fees and energy charges. These costs – such as fees for connecting to and using the heat grid – can make geothermal projects less competitive, especially compared to fossil-fuel-based systems that still benefit from older, more favorable pricing rules. To address this, the 2025–2029 government program includes the formation of an expert group to examine how energy prices, levies, and tariffs can be adjusted to support more affordable and climate-friendly heating solutions.

One idea under discussion is to reduce or waive certain grid charges for renewable heat sources like geothermal energy, particularly when used in district heating networks. These changes are intended to make clean heating options more financially attractive for utilities, municipalities, and end users. Although the details of these reforms are still being worked out, the National Energy and Climate Plan confirms that changes to pricing rules are part of Austria's strategy to support the expansion of renewable heat technologies, including geothermal (BMK, 2024; Rajal & Barabas, 2025).

From an SEL perspective, the market and financial resources for GE in Austria are considered to be at the demonstration stage. While there is growing demand for district heating solutions, high upfront costs, lack of direct subsidies, and financial risks associated with exploratory drilling continue to hinder large-scale investment. To progress to the deployment stage, Austria will need to expand financial incentives, introduce risk-mitigation measures, and develop long-term price stabilization mechanisms to attract greater private investment and accelerate the growth of the geothermal sector.

3.2.4.6 Summary Southern Part of the Vienna Basin

In Austria, GE has achieved a high level of societal acceptance and is increasingly recognized as a vital component of the country's renewable energy strategy. The Austrian government has implemented policies aimed at promoting renewable energy. In comparison to neighboring countries, Austria appears to have achieved a higher level of public acceptance of renewable energy sources (see Figure 7 for a visualization of selected criteria for the case area. The figure is more about the pattern than specific numbers).

The Aspern geothermal project poses minimal environmental risks due to advanced drilling techniques, noise-reducing practices and real-time monitoring. Noise and surface disturbance are mitigated by deep directional drilling, and the visual footprint of the infrastructure is low. The closed-loop water reinjection system prevents pollution, and geological studies confirm no risk to groundwater or ecosystems. Multiple protective barriers ensure groundwater safety, while seismic risk remains low due to favorable geology and constant monitoring. Overall, comprehensive risk mitigation strategies ensure strong environmental protection and community trust.

The Aspern project benefits from proactive public engagement and support from key stakeholders, including government agencies and energy companies. Public awareness is relatively high, supported by communication tools such as the Geothermal Atlas (GeoSphere Austria, 2024), although outreach to rural areas could be improved. Transparent information sharing through websites and site visits has built trust, but no formal mechanisms such as referendums have been implemented for public decision-making. Safety assurances and incentives have improved perceptions, but skepticism remains due to past project failures. Progress toward broader adoption will require addressing labor shortages, expanding education, and tailoring communications to diverse communities.

Austria's regulatory framework for GE is hampered by fragmentation across federal, provincial and municipal levels, leading to delays and uncertainty. Although recognized as a renewable energy source, geothermal receives little political attention compared to solar or wind, resulting in limited funding and support. Subsurface property rights complicate project development, especially for directional drilling in urban areas. The National Energy and Climate Plan highlights regulatory inconsistencies as a major barrier and calls for better coordination and standardized procedures. Forthcoming reforms such as the EABG and amendments to the Mineral Resources Act aim to streamline approvals and improve geothermal integration.

Figure 7: Profile of the case area in Austria for the selected criteria.

3.2.4.7 References

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3.2.5 Devonian-Carboniferous Carbonate Platforms – Rhine-Ruhr Area, Germany (and the Netherlands)

The following section presents an SEL-based analysis of the societal acceptance of deep GE in the Rhine-Ruhr metropolitan region. This case is particularly interesting due to the geographical location of the underlying Devonian-Carboniferous carbonate platforms, especially the Massenkalk formations. Stretching from North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), Germany, into the Netherlands and, to a

lesser extent, Belgium (GO-Forward, 2023), they comprise an area of 26300 km² with 18.2 million inhabitants (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). These deep geological structures are considered promising geothermal reservoirs with lots of untapped potential and, thus, have been the focus of several exploratory and research-driven initiatives (e.g., the EU-funded DGE-ROLLOUT) in recent years.

For the sake of simplicity, the focus of this case study will primarily be on the German side, as the previous chapters already presented an analysis of geothermal in the Netherlands. For further, more in-depth information on the Netherlands, please refer to the previous chapters.

3.2.5.1 Case Overview

Germany has set a national target to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 65% by 2030, aiming for climate neutrality by 2050 (Gonzalez de Lucio & Thiel, 2022, p. 23). Since heat accounts for 56% of the country's final energy demand (Bracke & Huenges, 2022, p. 6), expanding the use of geothermal heating is one of several levers to potentially achieve these climate goals.

Germany is among the European countries with the highest number of geothermal district heating systems, aiming to generate 10 TWh of GE annually by the end of the decade (Toth et al., 2025, p. 4). In concrete numbers, currently, there are 42 deep geothermal plants in active operation across the whole country, 16 under construction, and 163 in planning or research stages. Additionally, Germany is home to 170 thermal baths (Bundesverband Geothermie, 2025).

The focus area for this case, the Rhine-Ruhr metropolitan region in North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), is one of Europe's most densely populated and industrialized areas, with approximately 10 million residents and a historically coal-dependent energy system. The region hosts some of the largest district heating networks in Europe, which are currently primarily powered by waste heat from fossil fuel plants (Lippert et al., 2022, p. 1). With Germany's statutory coal phase-out scheduled by 2038 (Lippert et al., 2022, p. 1), transforming this infrastructure will be essential. Accordingly, the NRW state government has identified deep GE as a key component of a secure, base-load capable, and low-emission heat supply, as outlined in both the "Interreg DGE-ROLLOUT" and the "Masterplan Geothermie" programs (Gonzalez de Lucio & Thiel, 2022; Masterplan Geothermie, 2024). The regional objective is to meet up to 20% of NRW's heat demand with GE by 2045 (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 10).

To implement these goals, NRW has launched a specific support strategy. Measures include public funding for exploration activities (e.g., 3D seismics), the creation of insurance schemes for drilling risks, the digitalization and streamlining of permitting processes, and the development of targeted public engagement formats. As of 2025, geothermal development in NRW remains in a formative phase, but key pilot and research projects have established a foundation for scaling up and accelerating deployment (Moeck et al., 2021, p. 4).

As of 2025, NRW hosts four operational deep geothermal plants, with three under construction and 17 more in the planning or research phase (Bundesverband Geothermie, 2025). The following non-exhaustive list presents selected flagship projects from the Rhine-Ruhr area, chosen for their high data availability and regional relevance:

3.2.5.1.1 *Research-oriented Projects under the DGE-ROLLOUT: Balmatt (BE), Bochum and Weisweiler (DE)*

The transnational EU-funded project "Roll-out of Deep Geothermal energy in North-West Europe" (DGE-ROLLOUT) aimed to accelerate geothermal development in countries such as Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium and France from 2018 until 2023 – setting the base for current geothermal exploration in the region. Outputs included an interactive web application integrating surface and subsurface data to identify geothermal investment hotspots, a toolbox for exploration and evaluation support, and enhanced production processes at selected pilot sites with deep GE extraction for

district heating. The two key pilot sites for this project include (1) Balmatt in Belgium and (2) Bochum in Germany (Interreg North-West Europe, n.d.).

Located near Mol, the **Balmatt** site is home to Flanders' first geothermal power plant, established by VITO (Flemish Institute for Technological Research). Initiated in 2015, the project involved drilling to depths of approximately 3,600 meters, successfully accessing water at temperatures around 138°C. The facility began trial operations in 2019, supplying heat to nearby institutions. Research at this site has concentrated on understanding the subsurface impact of geothermal extraction and optimizing production processes (Vito, n.d.).

In **Bochum**, several geothermal projects are planned, including the “Mark 51°7” district heating initiative, which repurposes former industrial grounds (Bundesverband Geothermie, 2024). However, the most relevant one to the DGE-ROLLOUT program is TRUDI (Transformation Unterstützung durch Reallabore zur Dekarbonisierung der Infrastruktur), coordinated by Fraunhofer IEG. This project aims to convert the 115 MWth Bochum district heating network from natural gas to deep geothermal energy. It investigates the hydrothermal potential at depths of 4,000 to 5,000 meters within folded sedimentary formations of the Variscan basement, as well as options for seasonal heat storage (Moeck et al., 2021, p. 6). The TRUDI site serves as a demonstration platform for advanced geothermal technologies, including high-temperature heat pumps and thermal energy storage. A key element involves using the existing subsurface infrastructure of an old coal mine to supply heat to local networks (Moeck et al., 2021, p. 6). The project contributes to developing more efficient and scalable geothermal solutions for urban areas.

However, it is important to mention that the Balmatt and Bochum sites are not the only research-oriented projects around geothermal in the region. For instance, the research infrastructure at the former coal mining area in **Weisweiler**, operated by Fraunhofer IEG, serves as another central site for geothermal technology development in NRW. At this site, two wells were drilled in 2023 and 2024 to depths of 100m and 500m, respectively and seismic monitoring stations and a geothermal probe have been installed. The goal is to evaluate the geothermal potential in the region and to develop scalable technological concepts for the energy transition in coal regions (Richter, 2025).

3.2.5.1.2 *Winners of the NRW Deep Geothermal State Competition: Straelen, Düsseldorf-Duisburg, Düren-Kreuzau*

The NRW state competition “Wärme aus Tiefengeothermie für NRW”, funded by the NRW Ministry of Economic Affairs, awarded funding of €0.5 million each to three pilot projects in 2021. Each of the selected cases targets a different application context: greenhouse horticulture, urban district heating as well as industrial and private heat. (Richter, 2021)

In **Straelen**, the project DEEP Straelen aims to supply low-carbon heat to large-scale greenhouses. The project seeks subsidies for heat prices and reduced grid fees, analogous to the Dutch SDE++ programme, to ensure economic viability. The project is supported by Fraunhofer IEG (Straelen am Niederrhein, 2024).

In **Düsseldorf** and *Duisburg*, exploratory seismic surveys are underway, focusing on the Massenkalk and Kohlenkalk formations. In Duisburg, target formations lie significantly deeper than in Düsseldorf.

In **Düren-Kreuzau**, a geothermal system is in the feasibility phase. The heat demand is primarily industrial (e.g. paper production). The region is geologically promising but requires further exploration. Planning duration is estimated at around three years. Key barriers identified include electricity costs for heat pumps and long permitting processes (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024).

The three pilot projects illustrate the range of possible applications for deep GE in NRW as well as the diverse current development that is taking place.

3.2.5.1.3 Other projects: Münster, Gelsenkirchen-Hassel, Hagen

In **Münster**, a 3D seismic campaign covering 140 km² was conducted to investigate deep geothermal potential. The project received €5.7 million in state funding and is part of the NRW geothermal roadmap. The project is considered a potential first implementation site for a geothermal heating plant in NRW (Informationsportal Tiefe Geothermie, 2025b).

In **Gelsenkirchen-Hassel**, a geothermal system is being integrated into a new residential quarter on the site of a former coking plant. This project demonstrates the repurposing of brownfield industrial areas for renewable heat production. It symbolically connects NRW's coal past with its energy transition future (BMWK, 2024).

In **Hagen**, geological pre-assessments are being carried out to evaluate feasibility. No seismic exploration or drilling has been conducted yet. The municipality participates in the state's geothermal coordination platform and has signaled interest in long-term development in cooperation with Fraunhofer IEG and GD NRW (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 11).

These examples showcase the recently increased development of deep geothermal in the Rhine-Ruhr area, indicating continued growth and relevance in the upcoming years.

The following sub-chapters assess the SEL of deep GE in the Rhine-Ruhr area according to Sprenkeling et al. (2022).

3.2.5.2 Impact on the Environment

This section analyzes the impact of deep geothermal on the natural, built, and social environment.

The GE rollout in the Rhine-Ruhr region is shaped by a relatively favorable environmental profile. Currently, most projects are in the development stage and large parts of environmental data for NRW are provided by the regional state office LANUV (Gonzalez de Lucio & Thiel, 2022, p. 22).

The drilling phase of a geothermal project can extend up to two years and may cause temporary noise emissions, which are tightly regulated under the German TA-Lärm framework. For instance, in the Düsseldorf-Duisburg area, it is mandatory to conduct ongoing noise measurements to ensure compliance and protect residents and the environment. During operation, it is highlighted that geothermal heating systems are nearly silent. (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024b, p. 13)

Public seismic surveys involving vibro-trucks, such as those conducted in Münster, are designed to minimize nuisance, with measurements occurring mostly at night and expected to cause disturbances of one to two hours (Informationsportal Tiefe Geothermie, 2021) – all this being openly and proactively communicated to the local stakeholders.

Further environmental considerations regarding the reclamation of land are addressed in certain projects through the reuse of existing industrial sites. In Gelsenkirchen-Hassel, for instance, geothermal district heating infrastructure is being developed on a former coking plant site, significantly reducing new land use and aesthetic impacts (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, 2024). This approach aligns with observations in similarly urbanized areas (e.g. Paris), where Gombert et al. (2018, p. 2) argued that the environmental impact is minimized as the projects are built in already urbanized areas. According to the DGE-Rollout (Gonzalez de Lucio & Thiel, 2022, p. 22), areas are carefully assessed through landscape planning around protected areas for nature conservation, which have apparently been chosen for their easy recognition among the population.

Public concerns around seismic risks remain. In the Netherlands, for example, a geothermal project in Californië (Gelderland) has been suspended after a mild earthquake occurred at the depth of 6km (Geothermie Nederland, n.d.). Communication efforts highlighted the unlikelihood of the connection between geothermal extraction and earthquakes, as the extraction took place in an already naturally seismic region but also failed to completely rule it out. The government will decide whether and under

what conditions extraction may be restarted (Geothermie Nederland, n.d.). It can be assumed that public concerns regarding seismicity are significant in the German part of the Rhine-Ruhr area as well.

Moreover, environmental impact is further mitigated by the exclusive use of hydrothermal technology in NRW, explicitly excluding fracking as this method is associated with supposedly higher risks (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 50).

Lastly, in terms of broader environmental contribution and CCUS, GE is expected to play a key role in the decarbonization of the regional heat supply. Existing heating infrastructure, such as for example in the Bochum-Süd network, is being evaluated for conversion to geothermal sources (Moeck et al., 2021, p. 6). Given its high base-load capacity and low spatial footprint, GE is regarded as especially suitable for densely populated urban areas (Bracke & Huenges, 2022, p. 6), allowing for a significant CO₂ saving potential as a result (Lippert et al., 2022, p. 1).

Overall, the environmental embeddedness of deep geothermal in NRW is comparatively strong, with proactive regulatory oversight and low environmental footprint positioning it as a resilient component of the regional heat transition.

3.2.5.3 Stakeholder Involvement

This section focuses on the current stakeholder involvement in the Rhine-Ruhr area.

During the desk research for this case, which was conducted in English and German, it became evident that plenty of informational materials for stakeholders regarding GE can be found online, with Bundesverband Geothermie or the municipalities themselves being the main publishers. Another observation was the high involvement of the Fraunhofer IEG (F-IEG), which participated in almost every geothermal project considered for this case, indicating extremely high relevance and influence on the topic.

According to a survey cited by Gonzalez de Lucio and Thiel (2022, p. 15), renewable energies are part of Germany's climate protection agenda, and the expansion of these energies is supported by the population, meaning that 83 % of the surveyed population (n=1051) consider it important or very important. This may also suggest a generally positive attitude towards geothermal as a renewable energy source.

In terms of stakeholder acceptance, one policy innovation stood out: In its current action plan, NRW now explicitly links public acceptance to funding eligibility, integrating stakeholder engagement as a criterion in grant schemes (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 11). The Bundesverband Geothermie (2020) emphasizes that effective communication is crucial for the successful implementation of large-scale visible geothermal projects, especially if the subject is complex or there is a general lack of trust within the population. This further underscores the importance of stakeholder engagement during all stages of a geothermal project.

The FAQ catalogue on geothermal energy, developed by the Landesforschungszentrum Geothermie with national experts and funded by the Ministry for the Environment of Baden-Württemberg, addresses key stakeholder concerns using the latest scientific and technical insights. While partially regionally focused, its findings are relevant across Germany, including the Rhine-Ruhr area. It became clear that the main stakeholder concerns seem to include groundwater protection, surface deformation, changes in subsurface pressure, seismic risks, economic viability, environmental impacts, and insurance-related issues. These reflect widespread considerations in the planning and acceptance of deep geothermal projects and should therefore be addressed accordingly. (Bundesverband Geothermie, n.d.)

Regarding stakeholder identification and active engagement, initial actions are already in place for many locations. Local authorities and institutions have started to implement participatory formats.

Examples include virtual information sessions, such as the public webinar on the Masterplan Geothermie (Landesregierung NRW, 2024) and in-person outreach events like the “Vibro-Truck zum Anfassen” (“Touch a Vibro-Truck”) in Münster, where residents could directly engage with experts and inspect seismic survey vehicles (Informationsportal Tiefe Geothermie, 2021).

In addition to individual events, there are also noticeable efforts to disseminate knowledge on a broader scale. Public workshops, such as *Stadtwerke.Nutzen.GEOTHERMIE*, jointly organized by NRW.Energy4Climate, Fraunhofer IEG and the Bundesverband Geothermie, brought together almost 90 stakeholders from municipalities, utilities, and academia in 2022 (Cariaga, 2022). These formats indicate increasing institutional awareness of the need for inclusive discourse on geothermal development.

While municipalities such as Münster, Aachen, and Duisburg have started to communicate planned activities and timelines transparently, large-scale awareness campaigns have not yet been carried out (Risiko-Dialog, 2024). Given the early stage of most projects and the sensitivity of public perception to environmental and safety concerns (e.g. seismicity or groundwater protection), proactive trust-building measures remain essential. Communication strategies must be designed to navigate framing sensitivities, such as differentiating between “Erschütterung” and “Erdbeben,” or avoiding terms like “Fracking” that are believed to provoke ideological resistance (Bundesverband Geothermie, 2020). In this sense, the exemplary communication by Bracke, the Director of the Fraunhofer Institute IEG (cit. in Cariaga, 2022), showcases the following framing: “The Rhine-Ruhr region, with its strong tradition as a location for energy, industry and mining, has everything it needs to meet the challenges of the heat transition [...] Geothermal energy can cover over 70 percent of municipal heating requirements in NRW. Stadtwerke and Fraunhofer Gesellschaft together can leverage this potential and make geothermal energy a key element of the heat transition. Together we are shaping the climate-neutral energy systems of the future” – highlighting values such as tradition, collaboration and community.”

Lastly, especially the DGE-ROLLOUT in the Rhine-Ruhr area seems to enable closer collaboration amongst various stakeholders. The project partners include the national geological surveys of Belgium (RBINS–GSB), France (BRGM), and the Netherlands (TNO), alongside industry partners (DMT, EBN, RWE) and research institutions (Fraunhofer IEG, TU Darmstadt, VITO) – fostering cross-sector and cross-border cooperation (Fritschle et al., 2021, p. 1).

In summary, stakeholder engagement in the Rhine-Ruhr area is gaining momentum, supported by institutional initiatives and early participatory efforts. To support public confidence, communication strategies should be carefully framed and sensitive to concerns regarding environmental and safety issues.

3.2.5.4 Policy and Regulations

This section analyses the regulatory and political framework for deep GE in the German part of the Rhine-Ruhr region, with specific attention to North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW). The cross-border nature of the underlying geology necessitates regional coordination, but as Dutch regulations have been assessed in earlier chapters, this subsection focuses mainly on German developments.

As already mentioned, NRW has positioned deep GE as a strategic cornerstone of its decarbonization policy. This is most clearly articulated in the state’s Masterplan Geothermie, which sets the goal of covering up to 20% of NRW’s heat demand through GE by 2045 (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 10).

Permitting responsibilities are split between local and regional authorities. In the case of Gelsenkirchen, for boreholes deeper than 100 meters, notification to the Bezirksregierung Arnsberg is mandatory under federal mining law. Despite formal clarity, stakeholders repeatedly cite long approval times as a key bottleneck, particularly in the early exploration and drilling phases (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 13).

Therefore, to address the regulatory complexity surrounding geothermal projects, the state government has initiated several structural reforms. As a result, the implementation of the Onlinezugangsgesetz (OZG) is currently underway, aiming to enable a fully digitalized application process for mining-related permits. Furthermore, the state aims to harmonize approval practices across municipalities and regions to improve planning reliability (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 13).

At the federal level, several regulatory barriers persist. As outlined in their strategy paper "Roadmap for Deep Geothermal Energy for Germany", Bracke and Huenges (2022, p. 6) argue that future regulations should place greater emphasis on the CO₂ savings potential of geothermal projects. According to Bracke and Huenges (2022, p. 6), policymakers should set specific expansion targets for GE and adjust laws such as the BBodMG, WHG, and BauGB to speed up approval processes. In addition, they recommend defining priority areas in regional and local planning and simplifying fees and permitting procedures for municipalities and companies.

In terms of substantive regulation, NRW has adopted a precautionary approach by excluding fracking methods from its geothermal policy. Only hydrothermal systems are permitted, a decision justified by the need for environmental protection and the necessity of maintaining public trust (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 9). Another policy innovation is, as already mentioned above, the integration of societal criteria into regulatory funding schemes. Public acceptance and stakeholder engagement are explicitly defined as prerequisites for receiving financial support (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 43). According to the plan, "transparency, honesty and fact-based information" are key principles for stakeholder communication. This reflects a growing recognition that regulatory success depends not only on procedural efficiency, but also on embedding projects into their social context.

Finally, NRW is closely linked to international policy and research initiatives (including the DGE-ROLLOUT) which coordinates geological research across countries to develop shared geothermal frameworks. This underscores the advantage of transnational cooperation for harmonizing standards and data, particularly in geologically continuous formations such as the Massenkalk platform.

Overall, the policy and regulatory framework in NRW is undergoing substantial transformation. While strategic alignment and legal reforms are progressing, implementation remains partly incomplete, and lengthy approval procedures continue to delay project timelines. At the same time, on a positive note, stakeholder engagement is a noteworthy aspect of geothermal regulations.

3.2.5.5 Market and Financial Resources

This section focuses on the current market situation for deep GE in the Rhine-Ruhr area.

Germany has only recently begun to actively explore deep geothermal energy. As of 2023, deep geothermal accounted for just 0.1% of heating and cooling nationwide (Hockenos, 2020). However, as mentioned above, market interest and political prioritization are evolving rapidly. Both the national and state-level geothermal markets are now in a formative phase, characterized by rising investment volumes, new support instruments, and pilot-scale implementation, with 163 planned or research-phase projects across Germany (Bundesverband Geothermie, 2025). Again, in NRW alone, four plants are operational, three are under construction, and 17 are either planned or in research (Bundesverband Geothermie, 2025), reflecting the growing momentum of deep GE in the region.

The economic viability of deep geothermal projects is shaped by high upfront capital expenditure and relatively low operational costs. Investment costs for deep geothermal heat production are estimated at €2.0–2.5 billion per GW of installed capacity, offering stable, base-load heat supply at production costs below €30/MWh (Bracke & Huenges, 2022, p. 6). Nonetheless, the high "Fündigkeitsrisiko" – the risk of unsuccessful drilling – remains a central barrier to investment. In the context of the DGE-ROLLOUT project, Gonzalez de Lucio and Thiel (2022, p. 6) suggest that risk insurance or incentive

mechanisms can increase the likelihood of investment. One example is the Balmatt geothermal plant in Belgium, which received investment support from the Knowledge Institute and the Flemish Government.

To mitigate these risks, NRW has introduced a risk insurance instrument for geothermal projects. Administered by NRW.BANK, this mechanism covers up to 45% of drilling costs (maximum €10 million), which is non-repayable in the event of an unsuccessful exploration (Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, p. 39). This insurance is part of a broader risk-reduction strategy that also includes publicly funded feasibility studies, 3D seismic campaigns, and exploratory drilling (see Masterplan Geothermie, 2024, pp. 10–11).

The Geological Survey of NRW plays a strategic role in this context, managing a publicly funded program for exploration and subsurface data infrastructure. All resulting geological data is made openly accessible, significantly lowering market entry barriers for municipal and private actors. In Münster, for instance, a €5.7 million state-funded seismic campaign aims to prepare the region's potentially first geothermal heating plant and serve as a demonstrator project for the wider public (Informationsportal Tiefe Geothermie, 2025b).

While public financial support has increased considerably, demand-side structures remain comparatively underdeveloped. Several municipal utilities (Stadtwerke), particularly in cities such as Münster, Aachen and Duisburg, are currently assessing the integration of geothermal heat into existing district heating networks. However, extended planning horizons, uncertainty around drilling success, and dependency on electricity prices for heat pump operation limit short-term market responsiveness. For instance, the DEEP Straelen horticultural project explicitly links its financial viability to the introduction of electricity price subsidies and reduced grid fees, drawing on the Dutch SDE++ model as a reference (Straelen am Niederrhein, 2024).

Industry analysts highlight that with appropriate political and financial frameworks in place, deep GE could not only provide 25% of Germany's heat demand but also create up to 24,000 new jobs and reduce fossil fuel imports by €9 billion annually if 2030 targets are met (Cariaga, 2025). Bracke and Huenges (2022, p. 6) therefore recommend not only expanding funding for heat network development but additionally promoting industrial-scale investment in key enabling technologies such as high-temperature heat pumps, deep drilling systems, and seasonal heat storage – all of which are necessary to scale GE in densely populated urban areas such as the Rhine-Ruhr region.

The InvKG further supports this transformation. As part of Germany's structural aid for coal phase-out regions, Fraunhofer IEG and its research site Geo³ in Weisweiler received €36.5 million in funding from state and federal sources to expand geothermal R&D capacity (RWTH Aachen University, 2025). The aim is not only technological development, but also market acceleration through real-world demonstration and stakeholder involvement.

Cross-border cooperation also strengthens the Rhine-Ruhr market. Within the DGE-ROLLOUT project, partners from Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium and France could collaborate on exploration, data sharing, and joint policy recommendations to improve investment conditions across the transnational Devonian-Carboniferous carbonate platform (Arndt et al., 2021, p. 206).

In summary, the geothermal market in the Rhine-Ruhr region is characterized by cautious but accelerating growth. Public co-financing, risk mitigation, and transparent data infrastructure have significantly improved conditions for early-stage projects. However, further measures – such as demand-side incentives, faster permitting, and electricity price relief – will be needed to enable large-scale implementation. The region is now at a critical juncture where proactive market design has the potential to unlock substantial climate and economic benefits.

3.2.5.6 Summary Devonian-Carboniferous Carbonate Platforms, Rhine-Ruhr Area

This case study assessed the societal embeddedness of deep GE technologies in the Rhine-Ruhr metropolitan region using the SEL framework by Sprenkeling et al. (2022). The Rhine-Ruhr region illustrates a promising yet still emerging SEL for deep geothermal energy, currently situated between the Development and early Demonstration phases across all SEL dimensions (see Figure 8 for a visualization of selected criteria for the case area. The figure focusses more on the pattern, rather than on particular numbers).

Environmentally, the region benefits from a precautionary and low-impact geothermal strategy. Exclusive use of hydrothermal systems, avoidance of fracking, and the adaptive reuse of industrial sites (e.g. in Gelsenkirchen-Hassel) help minimize spatial and ecological footprints. Regulatory mechanisms such as TA-Lärm ensure noise control, and monitoring around seismic risks is evolving, placing this dimension in the Development stage.

Stakeholder involvement is growing, driven by actors such as Fraunhofer IEG, GD NRW, and NRW.Energy4Climate. Engagement formats include info events, co-financing conditions tied to public acceptance, and early participatory tools like the “Vibro-Truck” outreach in Münster. While institutional awareness is high, widespread co-design practices and trust-building strategies are not yet fully integrated – suggesting Development-level SEL, with room to move toward Demonstration.

Policy and regulation emerge as the most advanced SEL component. NRW has laid out clear geothermal targets, streamlined permitting processes (e.g. via OZG), and funding linked to acceptance criteria. Regulatory exclusion of fracking enhances public trust, and significant structural transformation funding (e.g. InvKG) supports deployment. However, delays in federal-level legal alignment and the complexity of approvals temper this progress – positioning this dimension between strong Development and early Demonstration.

Market and financial readiness are actively emerging. Instruments like NRW.BANK’s risk insurance, public co-financing (e.g. Fraunhofer IEG’s €36.5 million Geo³ lab), and accessible subsurface data infrastructure reduce investment barriers. Cross-border research through DGE-ROLLOUT and pilot projects like TRUDI and DEEP Straelen provide momentum, placing this dimension at a Development level.

In summary, the Rhine-Ruhr area is on a clear trajectory toward geothermal integration, with strong institutional frameworks and a growing project pipeline. Achieving full SEL Deployment will require accelerated market activation, broader public inclusion, and streamlined governance across municipalities. Building societal trust early – through transparency, fairness, and clear risk communication – will be essential for transforming the region’s energy legacy from coal to carbon-neutral heat.

Figure 8: Profile of the German case area for selected criteria.

3.2.5.7 References

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3.3 Fractured Crystalline Basement

3.3.1 Fractured Permian Granites – Cornwall, England

3.3.1.1 Case Overview

Cornwall has emerged as the leading region for deep GE development in the United Kingdom (UK), positioning itself as a testbed for low-carbon innovation in the fractured Permian granites that form a key part of the geology of south-west England. While geothermal development in the UK is in its early stages compared to continental Europe, Cornwall’s unique combination of elevated heat flow, favorable geological conditions, and strong regional ambition has enabled it to spearhead the country’s geothermal transition¹¹. The region is home to several pioneering projects, including the Hot Dry Rock project, the United Downs Deep Geothermal Power (UDDGP) project, the Eden Geothermal initiative, and the Langarth Deep Geothermal Heat Network – each representing significant milestones in the development of a domestic GE sector.

¹¹ Note that a) the Hot Dry Rock project of the 1980s, and b) that the GEL power plant should come online this year. Other parts of the UK are investigating sedimentary basin heat, mine water heat, and ground source heat pumps, some of which have been operational for several years.

Cornwall's geothermal portfolio spans both heat and power generation, with recent expansions into lithium extraction and industrial applications such as the Celsius Sustainable Distillery Centre or a planned large lithium car battery plant in Somerset. It is interesting to follow the timelines of both developments to identify potential synergies. These initiatives are underpinned by a diverse network of actors including Geothermal Engineering Ltd. (GEL), Eden Geothermal Ltd., Cornwall Council¹², and a range of public and private funders. Together, they reflect a strategic alignment between climate goals, technological development, and regional economic regeneration. As the first UK region to integrate deep geothermal heat into public facilities and green industry, Cornwall also plays a symbolic role in the national energy transition – demonstrating the potential of geothermal as a 24/7 baseload complement to intermittent renewables like wind and solar.

However, the expansion of GE in Cornwall raises important questions around societal acceptance, regulatory clarity, and environmental risk. Despite growing public interest and local government support, issues such as induced seismicity, regulatory ambiguity, and the invisibility of infrastructure in public narratives have triggered debates about transparency, energy justice, and long-term governance. Nonetheless, prior to and during drilling, GEL and its representatives (including science partners) held many meetings with the public and local council, and a public liaison officer is still active. This was all done to allay public concerns and promote transparency. Furthermore, the financial viability of geothermal projects remains fragile, with high upfront costs, uneven policy support, and limited risk-sharing mechanisms impeding widespread commercial deployment.

Within the SEL framework, Cornwall provides a compelling case for analyzing the interplay between geological opportunity, institutional innovation, and community dynamics. The following sections examine Cornwall's geothermal sector across the four SEL dimensions to evaluate its current state, challenges, and prospects for transitioning from demonstration to large scale deployment.

3.3.1.2 Impact on the Environment

The environmental implications of deep geothermal development in Cornwall are shaped by both its geological advantages and the region's proactive sustainability agenda. Current data show that all the granites are similarly fractured; therefore, they all have good potential. However, most of the work has been done in and around the Carnmenellis granite, largely because the Hot Dry Rock project was located there. The naturally radiogenic granites in Cornwall exhibit high heat flow and natural permeability, particularly along regionally extensive fracture zones. This makes them ideal for geothermal exploitation (Reinecker et al., 2021; GOV.UK, 2024). These conditions enable the development of deep Enhanced Geothermal Systems (EGS), like those at United Downs and Eden, which can provide continuous, low-carbon baseload energy with a minimal surface footprint (Cariaga, 2024; Morris, 2019).

In terms of pollution and emissions, deep GE is generally characterized by low operational impacts. Life-cycle assessments indicate that environmental burdens are concentrated in the drilling and construction phases, particularly due to the use of materials like steel and concrete, as well as the energy intensity of drilling deep wells exceeding 5 km (Paulillo et al., 2020). In the future, it is likely that the introduction of PCD bits (polycrystalline diamond) will reduce drilling times considerably - and hence reduce emissions (and costs). However, operational emissions are relatively modest, especially in high-efficiency configurations. The Eden Project, for example, estimates that its geothermal heating system reduces CO₂ emissions by up to 500 tons annually (Eden Project, 2024),

¹² Moreover, one could mention 'Cornish Lithium Plc', who have now drilled eight boreholes, each 1–2 km deep. In addition to dissolved lithium, there is potential for the use of low-grade heat.

contributing directly to Cornwall Council's goal of becoming carbon neutral by 2030 (Cornwall Council, 2019).

Nevertheless, certain environmental concerns persist, especially regarding induced seismicity. At United Downs, small seismic events have been documented during both drilling and hydraulic testing, attributed to interactions with the naturally fractured subsurface (Reinecker et al., 2021). While these events were generally low in magnitude, the potential for their occurrence prompted the installation of a sensitive seismometer network and a traffic-light monitoring system (similar to the one at Eden) to manage risks (Ledingham et al., 2019). The potential for micro-seismic activity has raised public concerns, particularly in a post-fracking context where subsurface interventions are viewed with heightened skepticism. This has implications not only for safety but also for trust and long-term project legitimacy. For context, it's worth mentioning that just prior to drilling, there was a natural M1.6 event in the area, which was far higher than during drilling/testing. This event served as a local natural baseline. It is also important to note that, for some regulatory compliance aspects, surface magnitude (i.e., felt magnitude) was used instead of absolute magnitude. This aligns closely with quarrying regulations and the effects that local people are familiar with due to blasting in nearby quarries. The BGS put out 10 surface sensors for two years, covering the testing period, as part of an independently funded (UK Research Council) science project — hence an element of independent monitoring.

Visual and aesthetic impacts appear to be limited but not negligible (as the drilling rigs were tall and stood out over the landscape, though they were less tall than the wind turbines in Cornwall.). One critique, articulated by David Salomon (2023), points to the invisibility of geothermal infrastructure at the Eden Project, arguing that its physical and symbolic separation from public exhibits weakens its educational and experiential potential. However, invisibility itself is not necessarily problematic—in many cases, it is the visibility of energy infrastructure that generates concern among local communities. Therefore, it would be interesting to compare its impact with that of wind turbines and solar farms, both of which are present in Cornwall. The Eden Project is notable in this respect for transforming a former clay pit into a vibrant, ecologically rich environment. In this context, geothermal development is integrated into a broader landscape narrative of environmental regeneration, although it remains visually and interpretively distinct from the site's main attractions.

Conversely, other projects such as the Celsius Sustainable Distillery Centre have faced challenges from the heritage and conservation perspectives. Located within a World Heritage Site, the original CGDC distillery plan faced pushback due to its perceived impact on the visual and historical landscape, leading to a scaled-down version on a nearby brownfield site (Cornwall Science Community, 2021).

On land reclamation and site selection, the Cornwall projects demonstrate environmentally sensitive planning practices. Both United Downs and Eden are situated on previously developed or industrial land, reducing the ecological footprint and potential land-use conflicts (Ledingham et al., 2019). Site-specific evaluations, including geophysical surveys and historical mining data, have guided project development to minimize disruption and optimize resource use (Reinecker et al., 2021).

In summary, the environmental profile of deep GE in Cornwall is largely positive, marked by low operational emissions, high site-specific suitability, and integration into broader decarbonization strategies. However, issues such as induced seismicity, visual integration, and potential resource conflicts require ongoing attention. Cornwall's experience underscores the importance of context-sensitive planning, robust monitoring, and careful communication to ensure that environmental co-benefits are fully realized and sustained. Ideally, monitoring should be carried out by a trusted actor. Currently, the operators perform the monitoring themselves and employ a traffic light system. To be fair, they have granted the BGS access to their data. The BGS is the appropriate type of independent

public-sector organization for the task, but they lack the necessary funding unless a science project coincidentally operates in the right area at the right time.

3.3.1.3 Stakeholder Involvement

The stakeholder landscape surrounding deep geothermal development in Cornwall is characterized by a combination of strong local initiative, targeted public engagement, and emerging tensions around transparency, visibility, and procedural fairness. Key stakeholders include geothermal developers such as Geothermal Engineering Ltd. (GEL) and Eden Geothermal Ltd.; public authorities like Cornwall Council; funding bodies including the European Regional Development Fund and UK central government; and a broad array of local actors, including residents, educational institutions, heritage organizations, and community interest groups. Stakeholder identification and roles are relatively well defined in Cornwall's geothermal sector.

Public engagement and communication have been relatively proactive, especially at the UDDGP site. Ledingham et al. (2019) document extensive early-stage outreach by GEL, including the appointment of a community liaison manager, the formation of a liaison group with residents and councilors, and the development of multiple communication platforms – such as a visitor center, public events, and social media channels. These efforts reflect an awareness of the importance of building public trust and addressing potential psychological and emotional responses to subsurface development.

At the same time, several issues highlight the limits of stakeholder inclusion. One is the lack of visibility and integration of geothermal infrastructure into public narratives and spatial experiences. Salomon (2023) critiques the Eden Project for keeping its geothermal plant visually and symbolically separate from its broader landscape of sustainability education. While this decision may reduce potential public opposition to industrial aesthetics, it also restricts opportunities for deeper public understanding and sense of connection to geothermal technologies.

Place attachment and psychological perceptions of the subsurface are also being studied. Research conducted by the University of Plymouth emphasizes how geological unfamiliarity and negative associations with past energy projects (e.g. potential for shale gas extraction in other parts of the UK that would involve 'fracking') can shape public sentiment, suggesting that deeper cultural understanding is essential for successful stakeholder engagement (University of Plymouth, n.d.).

Overall, stakeholder involvement in Cornwall's geothermal development reflects a maturing engagement strategy that blends technical outreach, community integration, and institutional responsiveness. Yet, as the sector scales up, challenges remain regarding equitable participation, long-term trust-building, and the articulation of GE within local identities and narratives. Addressing these dimensions will be critical in moving from project-level demonstration to broader societal embedding.

3.3.1.4 Policy and Regulations

Local geo-consultancies, such as Geoscience, managed the drilling operation and early public-facing aspects for GEL. They were also involved in the drilling at Eden. Also, the UK Research Councils, such as the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), funded a £1.8M project centered around deep geothermal at the United Downs site while it was being drilled and tested. There is potential for other science-driven projects in the area, such as engineering projects or projects related to extracting dissolved metals.

While project developers such as GEL have taken the lead in exploration, drilling, and infrastructure development, public institutions have played a key enabling role by providing financial support and regulatory permissions.

Cornwall Council, in particular, has positioned GE as a cornerstone of its climate strategy, with geothermal projects supporting goals around decarbonization, energy justice, and regional economic regeneration (Cornwall Council, 2019; GOV.UK, 2023). Moreover, the ecosystem includes indirect stakeholders such as educational institutions, exemplified by the University of Plymouth’s Sustainable Earth Institute, which has conducted research on public perceptions of GE (University of Plymouth, n.d.)¹³.

Further justice-related considerations arise from the absence of clearly defined rights to geothermal heat and the potential for resource competition in densely utilized subsurface areas. The Future of the Subsurface report highlights how multiple actors may draw from the same geothermal resource without regulatory mechanisms to mediate access or prevent over-extraction (GOV.UK, 2024). This legal ambiguity risks undermining perceived fairness, especially in areas such as Langarth Garden Village, where geothermal heat is planned for community heating networks.

Trust in institutions and project developers appears generally positive but remains contingent on continued transparency, monitoring, and local benefits. Efforts such as continuous seismic monitoring, noise control, and the implementation of a traffic-light system at United Downs and Eden reflect responsiveness to community concerns and demonstrate a degree of institutional accountability (e.g., Ledingham et al., 2019, Reinecker et al., 2021). The involvement of educational partners and open access to monitoring data further support the legitimacy of these initiatives.

Questions of procedural and distributive justice have emerged in the context of land use conflicts and project siting. For example, the original plan for the CGDC distillery encountered opposition from heritage preservation groups and existing land users, including motorsport enthusiasts operating at United Downs (Cornwall Science Community, 2021). Although the project was subsequently scaled down and relocated to a brownfield site, the initial conflict underscores the importance of negotiated, inclusive planning processes and transparent communication about competing land values.

In terms of benefit distribution, geothermal development is framed as a vehicle for regional development and social equity. Deep geothermal projects like Eden and at United Downs are expected to generate local employment, reduce energy costs, and enhance energy security (Morris, 2021; GOV.UK, 2024). Furthermore, initiatives to extract lithium from deep groundwaters (GEL as well as Cornish Lithium) are also expected to generate job opportunities and help the local economy. Additionally, social initiatives such as Eden’s Growing Point—integrating geothermal heating with inclusive educational programs—demonstrate attempts to embed geothermal benefits within the social fabric (Eden Project, 2024).

3.3.1.5 Market and Financial Resources

The development of deep GE in Cornwall has progressed despite significant market and financial barriers, reflecting both the promise of the technology and the structural challenges it continues to face in the UK. As a capital-intensive sector requiring large upfront investment and long development timelines, GE is particularly sensitive to risk exposure in its early phases. In Cornwall, project developers such as Geothermal Engineering Ltd. (GEL) and Eden Geothermal Ltd. have had to navigate a complex financial landscape combining public grants, local authority support, and, more recently, national market-based instruments.

¹³ The Camborne School of Mines at the University of Exeter not only had academic staff, but also possessed knowledge and at least one Ph.D. student who was effectively working on the drill site for a period of six to twelve months. The British Geological Survey (BGS) has also expressed interest in the project. A NERC-funded scientific project is currently underway at United Downs, a collaborative effort involving the Camborne School of Mines and Heriot-Watt University.

The cost structure of deep geothermal projects presents a key constraint. Drilling expenses alone are substantial, with estimates ranging between £1.6 and £1.8 million per kilometer for vertical wells, and total system costs reaching up to £4 million per megawatt thermal (GOV.UK, 2024). These costs are especially relevant in Cornwall, where geothermal wells have exceeded 5 kilometers in depth, such as at United Downs and Eden. The higher geological risk of the first boreholes at a new site and long payback periods have historically discouraged private investment, making the sector heavily reliant on public co-financing in its early phases.

Several projects in Cornwall have secured public support through the European Regional Development Fund, Cornwall Council, and targeted national schemes. For example, the Eden Project received £16.8 million for its initial phase, with nearly £10 million from the ERDF and further contributions from local authorities and institutional investors (Morris, 2019). The Langarth Deep Geothermal Heat Network, meanwhile, received £22 million from the UK Government's Green Heat Network Fund, positioning it as one of the country's largest zero-carbon heat networks (Born to Engineer, 2023; GOV.UK, 2023). These examples highlight the importance of strategic public investment in enabling geothermal development where private capital alone may be insufficient.

A major breakthrough occurred in 2023, when GEL's projects at United Downs, Manhay, and Penhallow were awarded CfDs under the UK government's Allocation Round 5 (AR5) (Cariaga, 2023; 2024). These 15-year contracts guarantee a stable price for electricity generation, shielding projects from market volatility and providing developers with revenue certainty. Although geothermal was previously eligible for CfDs, the awarding of actual contracts to three projects marks the first time that GE has been formally supported through this mechanism in the UK. This development significantly enhances investor confidence and signals an important policy shift toward recognizing geothermal as a reliable contributor to the national energy mix.

Still, funding gaps remain—particularly during the exploration and drilling phases, which are not covered by the CfD scheme. According to McClean and Pedersen (2023), the absence of early-stage risk mitigation instruments—such as drilling insurance or exploration grants—creates a “valley of death” for geothermal entrepreneurs. Without a clear strategy to de-risk the front end of project development, financial barriers may persist despite improvements in revenue stabilization mechanisms. Nonetheless, it is important to recognize the increasing number of scientific projects in Cornwall focused on enhancing the understanding of fracture networks and zones within the deep subsurface. This should mitigate some of the risks associated with geothermal uncertainty.

Furthermore, the UK's GE sector lacks comprehensive subsidy regimes and policy targets that support other renewable energy sources, like wind or solar. This institutional asymmetry affects investor perception of the geothermal sector's long-term viability and limits the emergence of a robust domestic supply chain. The Future of the Subsurface report suggests that adopting international models – such as Germany's risk guarantee schemes or the Netherlands' licensing reforms – could help build a stronger market base for GE in the UK (GOV.UK, 2024).

Despite these limitations, Cornwall's geothermal sector is increasingly positioned as a driver of local economic development, with projects generating skilled employment, inward investment, and value-added activities such as geothermal-powered distillation and lithium extraction (Richter, 2021a; Cariaga, 2024; Richter, 2025), which may be called a ‘cascade of uses of geothermal fluids’ (i.e. power, heat, minerals - and associated low temperature use for greenhouses, fish farming, tourist spas etc.). The Eden Project and GEL both frame geothermal as a long-term economic opportunity that aligns with regional efforts to “level up” historically disadvantaged areas, suggesting broader socio-economic benefits beyond pure energy production.

In conclusion, the market and financial environment for GE in Cornwall is evolving. Public investment is critical in overcoming early-stage barriers, while the introduction of CfDs marks a turning point for

the financial viability of large-scale geothermal electricity generation. However, persistent funding gaps, high upfront costs, and the absence of a dedicated risk-sharing framework continue to constrain the sector's growth. Addressing these structural limitations will be key to transitioning GE in Cornwall from a demonstration stage to full deployment within the UK's low-carbon energy economy

3.3.1.6 Summary Fractured Permian Granites, Cornwall

Cornwall represents the UK's most advanced region for deep GE development, with projects such as United Downs and Eden Geothermal demonstrating technical feasibility and regional ambition (see Figure 9 for a visualization of selected criteria for the case area. The figure focusses more on the pattern, rather than on particular numbers). These initiatives benefit from favorable geological conditions, strong local political support, and targeted public investment. They also illustrate how GE can contribute not only to decarbonization but also to regional economic renewal through employment opportunities heat networks, and industrial applications.

However, when assessed through the SEL-Matrix, Cornwall's geothermal sector shows clear limitations in societal embedding. Still, it may be worth noting that the GEL plant is scheduled to launch later this year. This will generate significant local and national interest. If managed correctly, it could play a pivotal role in educating the public about the benefits of geothermal energy, while operational impacts are low, concerns around induced seismicity and limited integration into public spatial narratives remain unresolved. Stakeholder engagement is active at the project level but lacks systemic depth in terms of participatory governance, procedural justice, and cultural integration. Most notably, the regulatory framework at the national level is fragmented and underdeveloped: geothermal heat is not defined as a resource, there is no dedicated licensing regime, and planning procedures remain inconsistent. The market dimension shows signs of progress through mechanisms like the CfD scheme, but early-stage financial risk remains largely unaddressed, and private sector involvement is still limited.

Considering these findings, Cornwall's geothermal development is best positioned within Level "Development" of the Societal Embeddedness Level (SEL) framework. While substantial progress has been made and the conditions for further scaling exist, full societal embedding – across regulation, market structure, and public legitimacy – has not yet been achieved. The transition to Demonstration level will require coordinated regulatory reform, long-term financial instruments for early-stage risk, and stronger integration of geothermal systems into public life and governance structures. However, it should be acknowledged that there is an increasing number of projects (besides GO-Forward, e.g. CHPM2030, CRM-geothermal, PUSH-IT) and publications that shed light on the geology (Cotton et al., 2020; Farndale & Law, 2022, 2023; Law et al., 2019, Rochelle et al., 2021).

Figure 9: Profiles of the case area Cornwall for selected criteria.

3.3.1.7 References

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3.3.2 Miocene Fracture System in Basement Rocks. Geothermal Development and social issues in Tuscany, Italy

3.3.2.1 Case Overview

Tuscany is one of Europe's most historically significant and technically advanced geothermal regions. The area has hosted industrial geothermal activity since the early 19th century, with the first successful use of geothermal steam for electricity production taking place in Larderello in 1904. Today, Tuscany remains the epicenter of Italy's GE sector, hosting 34 geothermal power plants operated primarily by Enel Green Power, distributed across the provinces of Pisa, Siena, and Grosseto.

Two key geothermal fields dominate the regional landscape: (a) the Larderello-Travale field, representing the historical core of geothermal development, and (b) the Mount Amiata field, located in a more environmentally and socially sensitive volcanic area. Together, these installations produce approximately 6 billion kWh annually, covering more than 30% of the region's electricity demand and contributing approximately 70% of Tuscany's renewable energy mix.

The region is undergoing a transition toward more sustainable and integrated geothermal practices. Institutions like CoSviG (Consorzio per lo Sviluppo delle Aree Geotermiche) play a central role in coordinating research, territorial development, and stakeholder engagement. Technological modernization, environmental mitigation (e.g. AMIS systems), and projects promoting the direct use of geothermal heat in agriculture, tourism, and district heating have become strategic priorities. Furthermore, initiatives such as geothermal tourism, educational centers, and circular economy models position geothermal not only as an energy source but also as a driver of local development.

At the same time, the expansion of GE – especially in Mount Amiata – faces growing public scrutiny due to environmental, health, and governance concerns. In response, regional authorities have introduced stricter environmental regulations, and the sector is increasingly subject to scientific monitoring and calls for more participatory governance. As the energy transition accelerates, Tuscany stands as a unique case where longstanding geothermal expertise intersects with contemporary debates on sustainability, territorial justice, and public trust.

3.3.2.2 Impact on the Environment

The environmental impacts of GE development in Tuscany, particularly in the Mount Amiata region, have been the subject of both technical assessment and local contestation. The region is characterized by a naturally high geothermal gradient, deep fluid flow circulation, mainly of meteoric origin and extensive fault fracture systems by which permeability in carbonate rocks is favored, resulting in significant geogenic emissions of carbon dioxide. According to geochemical research focused on the Mount Amiata Volcanic–Geothermal Area, geothermal power plants contribute only a minor share (approximately 7.9%) of total CO₂ emissions in the area, with the majority of emissions originating from natural soil degassing. Moreover, geothermal operations in some cases reduce diffuse natural emissions by capturing gases before they are released into the atmosphere, which supports the interpretation that GE production in this context is climate-neutral (Sbrana et al., 2021).

Air quality concerns, however, persist. Emissions of hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), mercury, ammonia, and arsenic from geothermal facilities have drawn criticism from local residents and environmental groups. Public opposition has been particularly strong around the Bagnore 4 plant, where it has been argued that only a fraction of the geothermal fluids is re-injected, leaving pollutants to be emitted through vapor discharge (Shin, 2013). Enel Green Power, the operator of the regional plants, maintains that such emissions reflect the area's natural geochemical background and highlights its investment in AMIS (Mercury and Hydrogen Sulfide Abatement Systems), which are now installed at all facilities and intended to reduce emissions and odor (Enel Green Power, 2024).

From a health standpoint, several studies have examined the relationship between geothermal emissions and public health risks. A large-scale respiratory health assessment conducted in the region found no evidence that chronic low-level exposure to H₂S is associated with reduced lung function or increased prevalence of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). In fact, the findings suggested a statistically significant reduction in impaired respiratory function among those with higher historical exposure to H₂S, though this result was acknowledged as counterintuitive and in need of cautious interpretation (Stoppa et al., 2023). In contrast, survey-based research in the same region revealed that public concern about pollution from geothermal plants remains widespread, shaped less by empirical air quality measurements and more by perceived exposure, bad odors, and long-standing mistrust toward local institutions. Risk perception was significantly higher among women, younger individuals, and residents in close proximity to the plants (Bustaffa et al., 2022).

Water quality has also been an area of concern, particularly regarding the presence of arsenic in drinking water. While critics have raised alarms about potential contamination from geothermal activities, the lack of consistent baseline environmental monitoring has made it difficult to determine the precise origins of such pollutants. This scientific uncertainty has fueled skepticism and resistance, particularly in areas like Mount Amiata with a history of environmental degradation from previous industrial activities (Shin, 2013; Manzella et al., 2019).

Seismic activity near geothermal plants in Tuscany has become a topic of concern, particularly in areas like Mount Amiata. While the region does not typically experience strong earthquakes, a gradual increase in small tremors has been observed near geothermal wells over the past 25 years. Although these events have remained low in intensity, they have prompted scientific investigations into whether geothermal operations could be playing a role. Extracting hot water and steam from underground and reinjecting cooler water back into the ground can change pressure and temperature levels below the surface. These shifts may place stress on underground rock layers and, in some cases, trigger minor earthquakes. One such event occurred in 2000 near the Piancastagnaio plant. It was shallow and caused damage to nearby buildings, reinforcing local concerns about a possible link between geothermal activity and seismic risk (Ohrnberger et al., 2016).

In response to these concerns, regional legislation in Tuscany has introduced stronger regulatory controls. The 2019 geothermal law places new limits on atmospheric emissions of pollutants such as mercury, ammonia, sulfuric acid, and boron. It also mandates continuous environmental monitoring by ARPAT (the regional environmental agency) and ASL (local health authorities) and establishes the possibility of plant shutdowns in case of non-compliance. These regulatory reforms are presented as part of a broader regional effort to align geothermal development with environmental protection and to rebuild public trust (Ingiusto, 2019).

Overall, the environmental dimension of GE in Tuscany presents a dual narrative: on one hand, scientific studies and mitigation technologies support the view that geothermal power can be environmentally sustainable and climate-neutral in this specific geological setting; on the other hand, historical pollution, perceived health risks, and weak institutional trust continue to shape public discourse. The resulting picture is one of both technical viability and social fragility, where environmental performance is subject not only to emissions data but also to the credibility and responsiveness of institutional actors.

3.3.2.3 Stakeholder involvement

Stakeholder involvement in the GE sector in Tuscany reflects a multifaceted and deeply contested terrain where institutional coordination, public trust, and emotional geographies are tightly interwoven. A diverse array of actors - including local communities, municipal authorities, regional institutions, private industry, scientific bodies, and civil society groups - contribute to shaping, contesting, and negotiating the role of geothermal development in the region. However, despite the strong institutional presence of organizations such as CoSviG and Enel Green Power, the broader stakeholder landscape remains marked by tensions around legitimacy, communication, and the distribution of benefits and risks.

CoSviG serves as a central institutional node in the region's geothermal governance architecture. As a publicly controlled consortium governed by municipalities and closely aligned with the Region of Tuscany, CoSviG portrays itself as a mediator and facilitator, aiming to enhance local capacity, support innovation, and strengthen the societal embeddedness of geothermal projects. Through initiatives like CEGLab and SestaLab, the consortium invests in training, stakeholder outreach, and the development of participatory tools (CoSviG, n.d.). However, while institutionally robust, these frameworks do not automatically translate into widespread social acceptance.

Enel Green Power, Tuscany's dominant industrial actor in geothermal energy, also positions itself as a stakeholder-responsive entity. The company emphasizes its historical roots in the region, its environmental mitigation efforts (e.g., the €100 million investment in AMIS abatement systems), and its contribution to local employment, tourism, and educational programs (Enel Green Power, 2024). It highlights partnerships with UNESCO, the "Tour of Fire" – a geothermal-themed cycling route through the steam-rich landscapes of Tuscany designed to connect visitors with the history and operations of GE – and community-facing projects such as the CO₂ recovery collaboration with Nippon Gases in Piancastagnaio to frame geothermal development as aligned with regional identity and sustainability. Despite this expansive self-representation, Enel has faced longstanding criticism from residents and environmental groups who contest the social and ecological consequences of geothermal operations – particularly in Mount Amiata (Shin, 2013).

The Mount Amiata region serves as a focal point of social resistance and stakeholder polarization. Here, strong opposition has emerged over perceived environmental and health risks, including exposure to non-condensable gases, the presence of arsenic in drinking water, and low-level hydrogen sulfide emissions. Although studies such as Stoppa et al. (2023) found no statistically significant correlation between H₂S exposure and respiratory health impairments, public perception remains dominated by suspicion and past environmental grievances. The earlier mining legacy in the

region, particularly mercury extraction, continues to influence risk narratives, often blurring distinctions between historical contamination and current geothermal activities (Bustaffa et al., 2022; Global Atlas of Environmental Justice, 2024).

A key challenge across the stakeholder landscape is the disconnect between technical assessments and lived experiences. While companies and authorities rely on emission data and scientific evidence to reassure residents, many stakeholders – especially those in towns like Arcidosso, Abbadia San Salvatore, and Piancastagnaio – continue to express profound anxiety and distrust. The large-scale survey conducted by Bustaffa et al. (2022) underscores this misalignment: perceived exposure to pollutants and concern about health impacts were widespread and shaped not only by factual knowledge but also by sensory experience (e.g., odors), demographic characteristics (e.g., gender, education level), and the degree of proximity to geothermal plants.

This discrepancy between expert knowledge and public perception underscores a broader procedural justice issue. Despite regulatory monitoring and top-down communication efforts, many residents feel excluded from actual decision-making processes. Studies by Pellizzone et al. (2017) and Manzella et al. (2019) emphasize that the core of opposition is not always technological but procedural. Citizens express dissatisfaction with how decisions are made, citing a lack of transparency, limited public consultation, and minimal inclusion in shaping long-term territorial strategies. Even when projects appear technically sound, the absence of early, anticipatory, and dialogic engagement has led to resistance grounded in a perceived erosion of autonomy and place-based values, yet again highlighting the importance of early-on stakeholder inclusion.

Trust emerges as a pivotal element. The literature consistently shows that trust in political actors and industrial stakeholders is low, while trust in independent researchers is relatively higher. This hierarchy of trust suggests the need for rethinking who communicates with whom, and how. Public opposition, especially in Mount Amiata, is not merely reactive but deeply rooted in local identity, emotional attachment to land, and historical grievances – factors often overlooked in institutional risk assessments (Manzella et al., 2019; Pellizzone et al., 2017).

In conclusion, stakeholder involvement in Tuscany's geothermal development is both a structural and cultural issue. While institutional mechanisms for engagement exist and are expanding, they often fall short of addressing deeper psychological, emotional, and political dynamics that shape public attitudes. Bridging the gap between stakeholder narratives and institutional frameworks requires a shift from information dissemination to deliberative participation – from managing dissent to cultivating trust.

3.3.2.4 Policy and Regulations

The regulatory and political landscape for GE in Tuscany is shaped by a combination of strong regional commitment and national-level ambiguities. At the regional level, the Tuscany Region has taken a proactive role in geothermal governance. This is exemplified by the 2019 regional law that redefined concession practices, tightened environmental standards, and redistributed geothermal revenues to municipalities, while explicitly protecting sensitive landscapes through a ban on new geothermal plants in those areas (Ingiusto, 2019). The law also mandates continuous atmospheric emissions monitoring, with enforcement assigned to ARPAT (Agenzia Regionale per la Protezione Ambientale della Toscana – the Regional Agency for Environmental Protection of Tuscany) and ASL (Azienda Sanitaria Locale – the local health authority). These developments indicate a high degree of regional policy integration, aligning geothermal deployment with broader environmental and socio-economic goals.

The regional government has also supported the creation of cooperation protocols with Enel Green Power, Tuscany's dominant geothermal operator, and promoted the designation of geothermal areas as "Distretto Geotermico" (Geothermal District), intended to centralize and coordinate territorial

planning (Richter, 2020). CoSviG plays a key role in this effort, functioning as an "in-house" public body under municipal control that supports planning, capacity-building, and implementation. Through CoSviG, Tuscany benefits from a direct institutional channel between regional governance and geothermal development, enhancing coordination between policy, innovation, and community engagement (CoSviG, n.d.).

At the national level, however, regulatory coherence has at times been lacking. The most prominent example is the 2018 exclusion of GE from Italy's national renewable energy incentive schemes (particularly the FER incentive system, or *Fonti Energetiche Rinnovabili* – Renewable Energy Sources). This exclusion sparked widespread opposition from Tuscan municipalities and regional officials. Critics warned that the withdrawal of financial support would stall investment and threaten projects such as Enel's planned low-emission geothermal plant in Piancastagnaio (Richter, 2020).

In response, regional political actors - including Enrico Rossi, then President of the Tuscany Region - advocated for the reintegration of geothermal into national funding schemes. Rossi reported that the Ministry of Economic Development (Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico, MISE) was working on a revised incentives framework known as FER2 (*secondo decreto per le Fonti Energetiche Rinnovabili* – second decree on renewable energy sources), which would reinstate geothermal support. Rossi also proposed regional financial measures to support the sector during this transition, including loan packages through Fidi Toscana (a regional financial institution), and the transformation of CoSviG into a full-fledged development agency (Richter, 2020). The local political efforts seemed to pay off: In summer of 2024, FER2 was adopted by Italy's Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security which put GE production back on track in Tuscany and nationwide (Abreo, 2024).

Despite these efforts, communities in geothermal areas - especially in Mount Amiata - continue to express mistrust toward institutional decision-making. Residents often view environmental monitoring and licensing procedures as insufficiently transparent and feel excluded from key regulatory processes. Studies confirm that while formal governance mechanisms exist, local perception of regulatory legitimacy remains low (Bustaffa et al., 2022; Pellizzone et al., 2017). This skepticism can be traced in part to historical grievances and a lack of effective public communication from institutional actors.

In summary, Tuscany demonstrates a relatively advanced and regionally cohesive approach to geothermal regulation, marked by active coordination between public institutions and industrial actors. However, national-regional misalignment - particularly in incentive policy - has disrupted regulatory continuity. The case underscores the need for coherent, transparent, and participatory governance structures that integrate multi-level decision-making with local legitimacy and long-term strategic vision.

3.3.2.5 Market and Financial Resources

The GE market in Tuscany is relatively robust at the regional level, yet it operates within a national policy environment that has hindered its growth at times. Tuscany's geothermal sector is heavily shaped by Enel Green Power's industrial presence, with a long-established infrastructure of 34 geothermal plants that together generate more than 6 billion kWh annually. Despite this, GE still accounts for only about 2% of Italy's national electricity mix, indicating a disconnect between regional potential and national energy priorities (Ingiusto, 2019).

The high upfront capital costs of geothermal development – due to deep drilling, reservoir characterization, and plant construction – necessitate both public and private financial backing. Tuscany has responded to these financial demands through various institutional mechanisms. The Region introduced targeted support via partnerships with entities like Fidi Toscana and CoSviG to provide favorable loan conditions and technical assistance to local SMEs (Richter, 2020). These

measures aim to strengthen local supply chains and reduce entry barriers for smaller firms, yet detailed evaluations of their effectiveness remain scarce in the public domain.

At the national level, however, financial support mechanisms have been unstable. The exclusion of GE from Italy's "FER1" renewable energy incentive scheme in 2018 temporarily removed a key pillar of financial viability. This led to significant uncertainty in the sector, with local officials warning that investment plans – including those for lower-emission geothermal plants in Piancastagnaio – could be shelved (Richter, 2018). The lack of long-term financial predictability was particularly concerning for capital-intensive projects that require sustained policy support to be economically viable.

Following regional pressure, including coordinated lobbying by geothermal mayors, the national government signaled a return to support under the upcoming FER2 framework, though this support was not yet fully operational at the time of reporting (Richter, 2020). Until these national incentives are restored and stabilized, geothermal development in Tuscany remains largely reliant on regional policy, municipal royalties, and industry-led initiatives.

Despite these limitations, market diversification efforts have gained traction. Initiatives such as the recovery and commercial reuse of CO₂ from geothermal fluids – exemplified by Enel's partnership with Nippon Gases – represent efforts to turn operational byproducts into revenue streams, advancing circular economy principles within the sector (Enel Green Power, 2024).

However, some gaps remain. While regional revenues from geothermal royalties are estimated at €20–30 million per year, there is little available data on how these funds are reinvested or whether they create equitable development across all affected municipalities. Similarly, while local employment is often cited as a benefit, there is limited disaggregated data on job quality, wage levels, or the durability of employment contracts within the geothermal supply chain. The long-term economic sustainability of the sector thus hinges not only on innovation and investment, but also on transparent and inclusive distribution of financial returns.

In summary, while Tuscany has developed a proactive regional ecosystem that partially compensates for national-level shortcomings, the geothermal market remains vulnerable to regulatory shifts and funding volatility. The sector is capital-intensive, policy-sensitive, and shaped by a mix of local resilience and national uncertainty. Long-term viability will depend on stable incentives, expanded market applications (such as direct heat uses), and strengthened public-private financial frameworks.

3.3.2.6 Summary Miocene Fracture System, Tuscany

The analysis of the geothermal development in Tuscany, particularly within the Miocene fracture system in basement rocks, reveals a relatively high degree of societal embeddedness across all four SEL dimensions (see Figure 10 for a visualization of selected criteria for the case area. The figure emphasizes the overall pattern, rather than specific numbers). The region benefits from a long-standing geothermal tradition and strong institutional infrastructure, but it also faces specific challenges that shape the trajectory of future deployment.

From an environmental perspective, Tuscany demonstrates extensive geological knowledge, a mature understanding of reservoir behavior, and integration of environmental monitoring mechanisms. The legacy of geothermal production in the region provides a robust empirical foundation, although concerns persist over induced seismicity and land use conflicts, especially in relation to landscape protection and biodiversity conservation in certain areas (e.g., Amiata). These factors suggest an advanced Development to Demonstration level of environmental embeddedness.

In terms of stakeholder involvement, the case reflects a complex and historically charged landscape. Public opposition – particularly in zones with increased ecological or cultural sensitivity – has shaped the dialogue around new developments. At the same time, participatory governance tools and local engagement mechanisms are increasingly institutionalized, notably through municipal frameworks

and regional energy strategies. The involvement of local governments and environmental NGOs reflects a solid Development level, though uneven trust and participation across different localities temper progress toward full Deployment.

The policy and regulatory framework for GE in Tuscany reflects a high degree of regional coordination, with the 2019 regional law strengthening environmental controls, redistributing revenues, and restricting development in sensitive areas. Institutional mechanisms such as ARPAT, CoSviG, and territorial planning tools like the “Distretto Geotermico” enhance alignment between governance, innovation, and local implementation. However, national-regional inconsistencies – especially the 2018 exclusion from renewable energy incentives – have undermined regulatory continuity. Despite formal governance structures, public mistrust remains pronounced, particularly in areas like Mount Amiata, where local actors perceive limited transparency and participation. Overall, the framework operates at a Demonstration level, combining institutional maturity with persistent legitimacy gaps.

Finally, market and financial resources are marked by the presence of strong incumbent actors (notably Enel Green Power) and long-term investment pathways. Feed-in tariffs and national incentives support economic viability, while the sector benefits from access to both public and private financing. However, the dominance of a few key players and challenges in diversifying market entrants limit broader scalability and innovation. These conditions suggest a Demonstration level maturity with selective Deployment characteristics.

Figure 10: Profile of the case area Tuscany for selected criteria.

Overall, the Tuscany case ranks at the upper end of the SEL spectrum, with most dimensions operating between Development and Demonstration, and partial elements approaching Deployment. The region represents a relatively mature socio-technical context for geothermal energy, albeit with localized friction points – particularly regarding stakeholder trust and land-use conflicts – that merit ongoing attention. Future progress hinges on enhancing community co-ownership, fostering

transparent multi-level governance, and diversifying the geothermal market landscape to ensure long-term societal alignment and resilience.

3.3.2.7 References

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3.3.3 Neogene Faulting in Basement Rocks – Catalan Coastal Range (Vallès Basin), Catalonia

3.3.3.1 Case Overview

This chapter examines the conditions for geothermal development in Catalonia, focusing on the Vallès Basin, within the Catalan Coastal Ranges. As with the Iberian Basin discussed in Chapter 3.2.2, this case study is located in Spain and therefore, shares broader national regulations and strategies. However, due to its distinct geological context and the influence of regional (autonomic) institutions, the Catalan case is addressed independently in this chapter.

Spain represents a geologically and institutionally diverse context for the development of geothermal energy (GE). Despite the country's considerable geological potential, including high-temperature and deep geothermal resources, the sector remains underdeveloped relative to other European countries. Nevertheless, national and regional energy and climate strategies, largely driven by broader decarbonization commitments and the availability of EU recovery funding, are gradually accelerating GE in Spain's energy transition policies.

Geothermal potential and development in Spain vary significantly across regions. In Catalonia, institutional coordination and preliminary strategic frameworks are beginning to shape a pathway for geothermal integration. These include works led by universities but also through the Catalan geological survey (*Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya*, ICGC), with some publications like resource mapping, scenario planning, 3D modelling, and early-stage technical feasibility studies. While commercial deployment remains limited, the region exhibits increasing alignment between geological knowledge, institutional planning, and long-term energy foresight.

The Vallès Basin, located within the Catalan Coastal Ranges, is one of the historically recognized regions with significant geothermal potential, since some of the hot springs nearing 70°C have been used since Roman times. Geologically, this region is characterized by Neogene extensional faulting, result of the long-term reactivated crustal faulting that has enabled deep fluid circulation. These major structures, especially the Vallès Fault, generate significant geothermal anomalies in form of hot springs in several localities, including Caldes de Montbuí, La Garriga and Samalús towns.

First investigations into the geothermal potential of the Vallès Basin began in the late 70's, led by the Spanish geological survey (*Instituto Geológico y Minero de España*, IGME) (IGME, 1977). These works continued during the 80's with the drilling of several deep geothermal exploration boreholes, the deepest of which, located in Samalús town, reached 1,000 meters and recorded temperatures of 90°C (IGME, 1982, 1984, 1986a, b). Following the release of these reports, which provided initial

insight into the geothermal system characteristics, some related publications focused on the more detailed characterization of this geothermal system (Albert, 1988; Fernández & Banda 1988, 1990; Baqués et al., 2012; Canals et al., 1990).

In recent years, renewed interest in geothermal energy promoted by EU climate goals, has led to more advanced and comprehensive characterization of the Vallès Basin. Key academic contributions include hydrothermal circulation models, fracture characterization and 3D subsurface reconstructions (e.g., Cantarero et al., 2012, 2013, 2014; Fullea et al, 2009; Mitjanas et al., 2021, 2023, 2024; Piris et al., 2021; Torné et al, 2023). In this context, the ICGC has taken a leading role in providing publicly accessible geothermal datasets, including updated geothermal mapping, thermal gradient modeling, and geophysical campaigns (i.e., Arnó et al., 2025). Despite ongoing research studies in the area, there are currently no known active commercial projects underway or proposed. In contrast, regions such as the Iberian Basin remain at a nascent stage of exploration. Although geological conditions are favorable, particularly in formations such as the Upper Jurassic carbonate ramp, there is a notable absence of region-specific initiatives, stakeholder networks, or regulatory planning for geothermal development. The disparity between these regions illustrates the fragmented nature of Spain's geothermal landscape.

(a) Iberian Basin – Upper Jurassic Carbonate Ramp

The Iberian Basin, and specifically its Upper Jurassic carbonate ramp formations (commonly referred to as the Kimmeridgian ramp), is a geologically promising region for deep GE exploration in Spain. Characterized by extensive carbonate platforms with favorable thermal gradients and sedimentary basin structures, the region holds theoretical potential for medium- to high-enthalpy geothermal development. However, from a Societal Embeddedness Level (SEL) perspective, the current state of knowledge and institutional embeddedness remains limited.

Recent geological studies primarily focus on stratigraphy, sedimentary evolution, and basin dynamics (e.g., Aurell et al., 2010; Bádenas & Aurell, 2008), providing a detailed understanding of the depositional settings and facies architecture of the Kimmeridgian carbonate ramps. These contributions are essential for assessing subsurface heat storage and fluid flow pathways, yet they do not incorporate the regulatory, stakeholder, or market contexts necessary for advancing project implementation within a societal framework.

A significant and more recent technical advancement comes from Torné et al. (2023), who use an integrated modeling approach to characterize the thermal structure of the Iberian lithosphere. Their work highlights the temperature distribution at various crustal depths, offering a regional-scale geodynamic framework that is essential for identifying high-potential geothermal zones. Importantly, they note that while no anomalously high temperatures are found at shallow depths, some areas – particularly in the central and northeastern Iberian Peninsula – do exhibit heat flow values and temperature gradients conducive to deep geothermal exploitation. These findings suggest that the Iberian Basin should not be excluded from geothermal planning, even if surface expressions are less prominent than in volcanic regions.

Despite this, the region remains underrepresented in national policy instruments and funding programs. Unlike Catalonia or the Canary Islands, where targeted roadmaps (e.g., GEONERGIA-CAT 2030) and public-private stakeholder platforms exist, the Iberian Basin lacks geothermal-specific institutional or community-based initiatives.

From a governance perspective, the regulatory landscape in Catalonia is shaped by both national and regional frameworks. At the national level, geothermal exploration is regulated by the Ley de Minas. Recent national efforts to promote deep geothermal energy include the Orden TED/467/2023, which outlines eligibility criteria for funding under the EU-backed *Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia* (PRTR). However, after the PRTR final resolution signed on the 13th of February of 2024, and

as of 2025, there are no deep geothermal demonstration projects publicly announced in the area., and the basin has not been a major recipient of the “Geotermia Profunda” funding under the Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan (PRTR).

Despite the lack of official ongoing deep geothermal commercial projects, Catalan institutions are currently working on a regional strategy. The GEOENERGIA-CAT 2030 Plan, developed jointly by ICAEN (*Institut Català d’Energia*) and ICGC, establishes a roadmap for geothermal resources integration into Catalonia’s decarbonization strategy. This plan aligns with the broader energy foresight program PROENCAT 2050, which includes geothermal energy as a significant contributor in the decarbonization of heating and cooling systems in residential and public buildings.

In summary, while the geothermal sector in Catalonia remains in the early stages of development, the region benefits from a key geological setting, strong research capabilities, and increasing institutional support at both national and regional levels. These conditions suggest that with continued regulatory development, public investment, and stakeholder engagement, the Vallès Basin could become a strategic location for deep geothermal demonstration in Spain. From an SEL standpoint, the Iberian Basin thus remains firmly in the Exploration stage across all four dimensions. The environmental potential is geologically plausible, as Torné et al. (2023) demonstrate, but not yet developed; stakeholder involvement is minimal to non-existent; regulatory and policy frameworks have not been localized to the basin; and market engagement is constrained by the absence of feasibility studies and public investment.

Nevertheless, the basin shares geological analogies with other European sedimentary basins successfully deploying geothermal technologies, such as Germany’s Molasse Basin. This indicates that with proper investment, stakeholder consultation, and integration into broader energy planning instruments, such as the PNIEC (Plan Nacional Integrado de Energía y Clima) and PRTR, the Iberian Basin could transition from latent potential to actionable geothermal development. Thus, further research on this topic is strongly advised.

(b) Vallés Basin, Catalan Coastal Range - Neogene faulting in basement rocks

The Vallés Basin in the Catalan Coastal Range has experienced significant Neogene faulting, which has influenced geothermal activity in the region (Queralt et al., 2021). The societal embeddedness of GE here is notable for its potential for sustainable energy production, which is in line with local and regional objectives for reducing carbon emissions and promoting renewable energy sources. In addition, historical and ongoing geological studies have fostered strong academic and industrial interest, further integrating GE into the local socio-economic fabric, supporting local employment and technological advancement, and enhancing community acceptance and support for geothermal projects.

3.3.3.2 Impact on the Environment

Geothermal energy in Spain presents a significant but underutilized opportunity to reduce environmental impacts associated with conventional energy systems. With a theoretical technical potential estimated at approximately 600 GWe for Enhanced Geothermal Systems (EGS) at depths between 3 and 10 km and temperatures above 150°C, Spain's deep geothermal resources could contribute substantially to climate mitigation goals (Chamorro et al., 2014). The environmental appeal of GE lies in its ability to supply baseload power with minimal surface land use, low emissions, and minimal visual or acoustic impact, compared to other renewable technologies, making it suitable for urban and industrial areas.

In this context, Catalonia holds notable potential for geothermal exploitation, particularly through EGS, with an estimated capacity of 39 GWe (Chamorro et al., 2014). Recent advances in subsurface characterization have reduced the need for invasive early-stage drilling. For instance, Lialestani et al.

(2022), developed a hybrid deep learning model to generate 3D geothermal temperature maps, increasing accuracy in thermal gradient prediction while reducing the need for invasive exploratory drilling and minimizing environmental disturbance during early-stage project development.

At the regional level, the ICGC, in collaboration with academic institutions (i.e., Mitjanas et al., 2023, 2024; Piris et al., 2021), has produced high-quality public datasets and tools that support potential geothermal projects development. These include geological and geophysical datasets and models, geothermal maps and geothermal systems knowledge. These tools help identify favorable zones for development while minimizing environmental disturbances. For example, obtaining detailed 3D models of subsurface structures and thermal gradients enable the use of digital twins to anticipate aquifer and thermal anomalies behavior, critical for mitigating risks related to overexploitation, induced seismicity, and fluid contamination.

The environmental implications of deep geothermal exploitation in Catalonia require careful assessment, especially in the context of climate change (Government of Catalonia & Institute of Catalan Studies, 2017). Although no operational projects currently exist, the region's high urban density, water stress, and protected thermal water uses introduce important environmental considerations. Catalonia is experiencing increasing drought frequency, aquifer overexploitation, and growing pressure on thermal springs, especially in municipalities like Caldes de Montbuí, where thermal waters are socially and economically important (Altava-Ortiz et al., 2018; IDAEA-CSIC, 2024; Joint Research Centre [JRC], 2024). Any future geothermal project in such areas must include predictions on potential effects on potable and thermal aquifers, as well as reinjection strategies that maintain fluid balance and chemical composition (Kaya et al., 2011).

Land-use conflicts also present challenges, as the Vallès Basin is characterized by mixed urban-industrial zones and environmental protected areas (Olarieta et al., 2008). Although geothermal plants require limited surface space compared to other renewables, temporary disturbances during drilling and infrastructure installation must be considered in local spatial planning. Integration with local spatial plans and environmental protections is essential to prevent ecological and social impacts.

At the national level, the Orden TED/467/2023, under the EU-funded PRTR scheme, outlines environmental criteria for geothermal feasibility studies. To be eligible for funding under Spain's Deep Geothermal Program, projects must comply with environmental protection regulations and conduct impact assessments prior to drilling activities. The regulation promotes exploration studies that include non-invasive methods and limits funding eligibility to projects that incorporate a minimum of one 1,000-meter borehole.

Regionally, the GEOENERGIA-CAT Plan 2030 in Catalonia, coordinated by ICAEN and ICGC, emphasizes geothermal energy's role in decarbonizing heating and cooling systems. The initiative includes an evaluation of both shallow and deep geothermal potential and seeks to align with long-term energy decarbonization goals under the PROENCAT 2050 foresight strategy, which envisions geothermal heat pumps contributing 100% of building cooling, 82% of heating, and 62% of hot water production by 2050 (Cariaga, 2024).

In summary, geothermal development in Catalonia offers a strong option towards low-carbon heating and energy, but potential environmental risks should be considered for responsible deployment. On the one hand, geothermal represents a low-impact, climate-aligned energy source that could reduce emissions, free up land, and improve air quality. On the other hand, it introduces localized environmental risks related to aquifer protection, thermal water rights, and land-use conflicts, particularly in populated and hydrologically sensitive areas like the Vallès Basin. To protect both the environment and local communities, Catalonia needs clear regulations, ongoing risk monitoring, and

open involvement from stakeholders. With these safeguards in place, the region could become a leading example of responsible geothermal development in southern Europe.

3.3.3.3 Stakeholder Involvement

In the context of deep GE development in Spain, stakeholder involvement remains at an early but evolving stage. Traditionally, the geothermal sector has been characterized by limited public visibility and relatively weak engagement with broader societal actors, including local communities, civil society organizations, and end-users. However, recent institutional efforts and strategic frameworks indicate a shift toward greater inclusivity and participatory approaches.

At the national level, the launch of GEOENERGÍA, Spain's first national geothermal association, marks a key development in structuring stakeholder representation. As a spin-off of GEOPLAT (the Spanish Technology and Innovation Platform for Geothermal Energy), GEOENERGÍA aims to consolidate private sector actors and provide a unified voice to promote regulatory, political, and market conditions conducive to geothermal development. The association explicitly seeks to “facilitate intelligence on markets” and improve visibility of geothermal actors, while establishing alliances across public and private sectors to support strategic decision-making (Ardila, 2024). Though primarily industry-led, GEOENERGÍA's intention to influence policymaking suggests emerging pathways for stakeholder influence in regulatory agendas.

Public agencies have also taken steps to involve institutional stakeholders. The Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO) and its affiliated body IDAE (Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving) have launched calls for proposals under the Deep Geothermal Program, explicitly encouraging public-private partnerships. These calls incentivize collaborative applications involving energy companies, public administrations, research institutes, and technological centers (La Moncloa, 2023).

In Catalonia, the GEOENERGIA-CAT 2030 Plan, led by ICAEN and ICGC, represents an integrative planning effort that includes stakeholders from geological, energy, and policy sectors. The plan envisions a coordinated approach to harness both shallow and deep geothermal resources, with alignment to broader regional strategies like PROENCAT 2050 (Cariaga, 2024). The plan includes assessments of both shallow and deep geothermal potential and is intended to guide regional planning and investment priorities. While the planning process is largely institutional, it reflects a more holistic governance framework that includes territorial and technological stakeholders, thereby contributing to multi-level stakeholder coordination.

Despite these advancements, the involvement of local communities, citizen groups, and non-technical stakeholders in early planning and decision-making remains limited. For instance, while public financing mechanisms are available, there is minimal evidence of structured public consultations or participatory governance frameworks at the project level. This gap is particularly relevant in regions where geothermal developments are anticipated to intersect with inhabited or environmentally sensitive areas, such as the Vallès Basin in Catalonia. Although academic studies – such as the work by Mitjanas (2023) – highlight geothermal potential near populated urban zones, their engagement strategies remain technocratic, with no explicit mechanisms for incorporating community input or addressing local concerns.

In summary, the stakeholder landscape for deep GE in Spain is becoming increasingly formalized and involves multiple actors, particularly through industry associations and institutional partnerships. Nonetheless, significant efforts are still required to broaden stakeholder involvement beyond the technical and administrative domains and to include meaningful participation by communities, social actors, and potential end-users. Future projects will need to incorporate public engagement strategies, particularly in regions where geothermal activities may affect natural resources, land use, or thermal water traditions. Anticipating social concerns and facilitating open dialogue will be crucial

for increasing societal trust and legitimacy. Without such engagement, the long-term societal embeddedness of geothermal technologies may be constrained despite growing technical and political support.

3.3.3.4 Regulation and Policy

The regulatory and policy landscape for deep GE in Spain is undergoing gradual formalization, as both national and regional authorities begin to recognize its potential within broader energy transition strategies. Historically, GE in Spain has been hampered by a fragmented and underdeveloped regulatory framework, particularly in comparison with other European countries with more mature geothermal sectors. And as of 2025, the legal environment remains fragmented, with limited geothermal-specific regulation, procedural ambiguities, and governance overlaps between national and autonomous administrations (APPA Renovables, n.d.; Richter, 2021).

At the national level, deep geothermal activities fall under the scope of the Ley de Minas (Mining Law), which governs the exploration and use of subsurface resources. However, this legal framework was not originally designed with renewable energy in mind, leading to procedural mismatches and uncertainties in project implementation. While this law provides the legal basis for subsurface exploration, it imposes long permitting timelines and complex administrative requirements. The broader renewable energy framework is defined by Royal Decree-Law 9/2013, Law 24/2013 on the Electricity Sector, and Royal Decree 413/2014, which together set the economic and technical conditions for renewable electricity production, including geothermal, but lacks targeted support mechanisms for heating or district systems (APPA Renovables, n.d.).

More recently, Royal Decree-Law 15/2018 and Royal Decree 244/2019 have introduced measures to promote energy self-consumption and accelerate the energy transition, although their specific application to geothermal remains limited. A key regulatory advancement is the Orden TED/467/2023, which defines the criteria and procedures for granting public subsidies for deep geothermal feasibility studies. This measure, aligned with the EU-funded Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan (PRTR), provides financial support for exploratory activities and incentivizes medium- and high-enthalpy geothermal development (La Moncloa, 2023). The regulation requires applicants to submit environmental assessments and comply with both national mining regulations and region-specific permitting rules, underscoring the need for coordination across governance levels.

In addition to national efforts, the IDAE plays a central role in managing geothermal-related grants and overseeing regulatory compliance, especially in the context of the Deep Geothermal Program (*Programa GEOTERMIA PROFUNDA* | *Idae*, n.d., Redacción, G. T. R.SmartGridsInfo, 2024). The program represents the first substantial public investment in geothermal exploration, with a dedicated budget of €120 million and strict criteria concerning minimum drilling depths (1,000 meters) and project timelines. This shift signals the beginning of a more structured regulatory environment but also highlights the embryonic nature of project deployment in Spain. At the regional level, Catalonia stands out for taking a proactive approach to structuring GE within its energy planning framework. The GEOENERGIA-CAT 2030 Plan, led by ICAEN and ICGC, represents a strategic planning instrument that explicitly integrates GE into the region's decarbonization goals. Although not regulatory in nature, this roadmap promotes geothermal integration into heating and cooling networks, district systems, and public infrastructure. It also prioritizes knowledge generation, resource mapping, and coordination across territorial actors, aligning with the broader PROENCAT 2050 strategy for Catalonia's long-term energy foresight (García-Ceca, 2024; Cariaga, 2024).

Additionally, Catalonia has some regulatory safeguards for thermal water protection and land use, relevant for geothermal development in areas like the Vallès Basin. These include zoning regulations, aquifer vulnerability maps, and permitting requirements for thermal spring use under water and health regulations (e.g., Arnó et al., 2020). However, no region-specific law currently exists for deep

geothermal exploration, and developers must navigate both national mining regulations and regional spatial planning instruments.

In summary, the regulatory framework for GE in Catalonia is evolving but still incomplete. While significant steps have been taken to improve the legal basis for deep geothermal development – especially through subsidy schemes and long-term planning initiatives – there remains a need for more coherent and geothermal-specific regulation. Catalonia’s regional initiatives represent a promising example of strategic foresight, but regulatory execution still relies on legacy mining and energy laws. To move up the SEL scale, particularly in terms of enabling efficient deployment and reducing investor risk, Spain and Catalonia will need to harmonize permitting procedures, protect critical water resources, and develop geothermal-specific rules that offer legal certainty and environmental guarantees. These efforts are essential to accelerate deployment and attract public and private investment in the geothermal sector, establishing clearer and more integrated regulatory mechanisms across all governance levels.

3.3.3.5 Market and Financial Resources

The market and financial landscape for deep GE in Spain is characterized by increasing political support and recent public funding initiatives, but also by persistent structural and economic barriers that limit its large-scale development. Historically, GE in Spain has suffered from underinvestment, fragmented market structures, and a lack of financial instruments tailored to its specific risk profile. These issues have hindered the commercialization of geothermal technologies, especially those related to high-enthalpy systems targeting electricity generation and medium-enthalpy applications for industrial heating.

One of the most prominent barriers remains the high upfront capital cost of geothermal exploration and development, especially due to drilling and geological risk. For example, the cost of installing a geothermal heat pump in a single-family home is estimated at €18,000, which, despite long-term energy savings of up to 70% and lifespans of 50 years, remains a significant financial hurdle for widespread adoption (Richter, 2021). This challenge becomes even more critical for deep geothermal projects, which require substantial investment in feasibility studies, geological modeling, drilling, and infrastructure development before any return on investment can be realized.

To address these financial barriers, the Spanish government has begun deploying financial support mechanisms. The most significant of these is the Deep Geothermal Energy Program, funded through the EU-backed Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan (PRTR). This initiative has allocated €120 million for feasibility studies, including €60 million specifically reserved for the Canary Islands, and up to €15 million per project for exploratory drilling of at least 1,000 meters (La Moncloa, 2023). The program is managed by the IDAE and represents a substantial step toward de-risking early-stage geothermal investments. Importantly, grants are offered on a non-repayable basis and can be paid in advance, facilitating liquidity for project developers. However, administrative delays and limited technical support continue to challenge the effective absorption of funds, especially for small developers and municipalities.

To complement public funding, future strategies could explore blended finance models, risk-sharing facilities, or green bonds to mobilize private capital and reduce investor exposure to geological uncertainty. Some policy experts have also suggested EU-backed guarantees and facilitating access to European structural funds to attract private-sector participation (Portillo, 2024). Parallel to these national programs, GEOENERGÍA-CAT aims to strengthen market coordination, develop policy proposals, and enhance the visibility of geothermal stakeholders (Ardila, 2024). The organization functions as a collective business platform and knowledge hub, promoting market intelligence and facilitating partnerships across the geothermal value chain. Its role is particularly relevant in aligning

industrial actors with regulatory and financial developments, thereby helping to build a cohesive geothermal ecosystem in Spain.

At the European level, Spain is also increasingly aligned with EU market priorities for geothermal deployment. This is reflected in support from the European Parliament and the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) for a unified European geothermal strategy, including calls for a comprehensive resource map, coordinated funding mechanisms, and risk-sharing facilities. GEOENERGÍA's participation in a petition to the European Commission for a geothermal roadmap underscores the sector's efforts to secure favorable financial and regulatory conditions for expansion (Geoenergía, 2025).

Private sector engagement in geothermal technology remains limited but shows early signs of growth. Spanish manufacturer Ecoforest, the only domestic producer of geothermal heat pumps, reported a 50% year-on-year increase in sales in 2019 (Richter, 2021). While this growth is promising, more recent figures are not publicly available. However, the total number of geothermal installations in Spain remains very low by European standards. For example, in 2019, only 198 geothermal heat pumps were sold in Spain compared to over 25,000 in Sweden and 19,000 in Germany. The absence of a centralized market registry obscures investment trends and undermines the inclusion of geothermal contributions in national renewable energy statistics.

In summary, while Spain's geothermal market remains underdeveloped, recent public investment programs and institutional coordination efforts are beginning to address historical gaps. However, to unlock the sector's full potential, it will be crucial to overcome the remaining financial, regulatory and technical barriers. Improving permitting efficiency, providing geological risk insurance, and expanding private-sector financing pathways will be essential (e.g., Antics et al., 2021, from the GEORISK EU-project). The success of current programs like the Deep GE Program and regional initiatives like GEOENERGIA-CAT, will be critical to build a competitive geothermal market capable of supporting Spain's and Europe's decarbonization targets.

3.3.3.6 Summary Neogene Faulting in Basement Rocks, Catalonia

All in all, Spain exhibits considerable geological potential for deep geothermal energy, particularly through high-enthalpy resources and EGS. However, development across the country remains fragmented and in early stages compared to other European nations. Recent policy momentum – driven by EU funding, national climate goals, and emerging regional strategies – has begun to create supportive conditions for geothermal exploration and planning. Figure 11 shows a qualitative comparison between the two Spanish cases of study, the Vallès Basin and the Iberian Basin (Chapter 3.2.2).

Catalonia stands out as a region where institutional alignment is gradually forming. The GEOENERGIA-CAT 2030 Plan, for example, demonstrates a coordinated strategy to integrate geothermal energy into regional decarbonization frameworks, aligning with the PROENCAT 2050 foresight plan. Technical studies and preliminary assessments have improved our understanding of the subsurface, leading to more environmentally informed development. However, practical deployment remains limited.

From an environmental perspective, geothermal energy offers significant benefits in terms of emissions reduction, land efficiency, and low visual impact. However, its development in Catalonia would influence local opinions related to aquifer protection, drought-related water scarcity, and the cultural importance of thermal waters. In this context, environmental safeguards and reinjection strategies will be key to ensuring that geothermal development aligns with water protection and land-use priorities.

Spain’s regulatory framework for deep geothermal energy is still in a transitional phase. While national instruments such as the Orden TED/467/2023 provide criteria for project funding, and the Mining Law offers a legal framework for subsurface exploration, a fully geothermal-specific legal framework is still lacking. Regionally, Catalonia’s planning instruments are advancing, but regulatory execution still depends on national procedures and legacy frameworks.

Stakeholder engagement continues to be led primarily by institutions and technical actors. While national and regional agencies are forming alliances and promoting knowledge exchange, community participation and local consultation remain underdeveloped in areas like the Vallès Basin.

At the market level, Spain’s geothermal regions are geologically promising but lack region-specific policies, stakeholder networks, and project activity. Public funding through the PRTR and programs such as “Geotermia Profunda” are helping to close early-stage financial gaps, but long-term market growth will depend on improving permitting processes, expanding financing instruments, and reducing perceived risks.

From a SEL perspective, Catalonia, and Spain more broadly, remain in the early stages of development. The regions show promising signs of alignment between geological potential, technical knowledge and institutional investment efforts. However, while environmental and regulatory dimensions are gaining maturity, further efforts are needed to consolidate regulatory clarity and unlock market mechanisms that support long-term investment and social acceptance.

Figure 11: Profiles of the two case areas in Spain for selected criteria.

3.3.3.7 References

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4 Conclusions and answers to the research question

4.1 General conclusions from the case analysis

To answer the research question “What is the current state of the societal embeddedness level (SEL) of deep GE technologies in each of the 14 cases in nine countries that are studied in GO-Forward?” we analyzed various reports, media articles, scientific literature, and policy documents. It became clear that the quantity and quality of information on the case areas vary. Therefore, we refrain from stressing numerical expressions and instead primarily use qualitative descriptions. Nevertheless, we present an overview table indicating the respective embeddedness level for the cases (Table 4) according to the reviewed literature. Of course, there may be additional ongoing processes that are invisible to us or not yet formally documented. Expert judgment from GO-Forward colleagues should remedy any lack of knowledge. We summarize common themes across the cases along the four dimensions of the SEL.

Impact on the environment: In Denmark's Gassum Formation and the Paris Basin, projects benefit from proactive impact mitigation, including noise abatement, low emissions, and ongoing monitoring. The Dutch Delft Sandstone Member combines emission-minimizing drilling practices with integrated seismic and groundwater surveillance. In contrast, its Neogene counterpart is too nascent for a definitive impact assessment. Most of Switzerland's Molasse Basin sites use stringent seismic monitoring; however, environmental protests and inconsistent data availability make it difficult to predict long-term effects with confidence. Vienna's Aspern project minimizes surface disturbance through directional drilling and real-time monitoring, providing some of the strongest environmental protections in the sample. Germany's Rhine-Ruhr region uses hydrothermal approaches, frack-free systems, and adaptive reuse of industrial sites to keep the ecological footprint low. However, noise and seismic protocols are still evolving. Cornwall's United Downs and Eden fields demonstrate low-impact operational performance, yet they reveal gaps in integrating geothermal projects into broader land-use narratives and in addressing induced seismicity. Tuscany stands out for its deep empirical base. Decades of production data guide reservoir management and biodiversity safeguards. However, land-use conflicts and seismicity concerns around Amiata suggest ongoing friction. Finally, Spain's Catalonia and Iberian Basin initiatives, which are still in the exploratory phase, are improving subsurface knowledge and preliminary risk analyses, but they lack robust, site-specific environmental monitoring. Overall, projects that combine transparent monitoring, low-impact techniques, and clear mitigation pathways—especially in Vienna, Tuscany, and Rhine-Ruhr—are the furthest toward full environmental embedding. Meanwhile, early-stage or data-scarce regions still need deeper impact assessments and long-term ecological safeguards.

Stakeholder involvement: In Denmark and France, formal public consultation is legally required. However, its effectiveness depends on how early, transparent, and participatory the process actually is. The Netherlands stands out by integrating public engagement directly into the permitting process and by offering online tools that provide access to project data and allow people to voice their concerns. In Tuscany, the long-standing presence of GE has created institutionalized stakeholder relationships, though new projects still face opposition. Projects have stumbled in places like Cornwall and Austria due to limited local consultation, unclear communication of risks and benefits, and the perception of external imposition. To embed GE socially, one must move beyond procedural compliance and build genuine relationships of trust. This requires mechanisms for benefit-sharing, long-term dialog, and community ownership or co-governance.

Policy and regulation vary between centralized and decentralized models, but the key insight from a societal embeddedness perspective is that effective regulation must not only reduce administrative barriers but also support long-term social legitimacy. This means ensuring that GE is recognized not

just as a technical solution to energy goals but as a socio-technical system that intersects with land use, cultural values, and local livelihoods. Countries like Germany (NRW) and the Netherlands demonstrate how clear frameworks, combined with transparency and safeguards for citizens, can establish the conditions for a social license to operate. Conversely, where regulatory regimes are fragmented or opaque, even geologically promising projects may falter in the face of public resistance or local political opposition.

Market and financing conditions complete the picture, shaping both investor appetite and societal perception. Financial instruments that de-risk early-stage exploration — such as insurance schemes in Germany, subsidies in France and the Netherlands, or long-term incentives in Italy — can help attract capital. However, they also carry social implications: Who bears the risk? Who benefits from the returns? In contexts like Vaud (Switzerland) or Denmark, where public institutions play an active role in co-investment or ownership, GE becomes more than a merely private infrastructure project — it evolves to a shared resource with widespread accountability. Moreover, financing models that prioritize short-term profitability over long-term community benefits can provoke resistance, especially when coupled with environmental or governance concerns. Therefore, a socially embedded geothermal sector requires financial models that align investor returns with local benefits, perhaps through cooperatives, public–private partnerships, or community dividend schemes.

In summary, societal embeddedness is not a static condition but a process that unfolds across environmental, social, political, and economic terrains. The most promising geothermal initiatives — whether in the Netherlands, Tuscany, or NRW — are those which understand this interplay and embed responsiveness, transparency, and shared value into their core design. Future efforts should avoid isolated thinking and rather treat GE as a living interface between deep heat and human life, requiring not just technical innovation, but social imagination and institutional care.

Table 4: Case overview with indication of social embeddedness level.

SEL level	1: Exploration				2: Development				3: Demonstration				4: Deployment			
	Env	Sth	PoR	MFR	Env	Sth	PoR	MFR	Env	Sth	PoR	MFR	Env	Sth	PoR	MFR
01 Austria (Southern Vienna Basin)				(X)			X		X	X		(X)				
02 a) Switzerland (Western Vaud)	X	X	X	X		(X)										
02 b) Switzerland (Geneva)					X	X	X	X		(X)	(X)					
02 c) Switzerland (Eclépens)	X	X	X	X		(X)										
03 a) Denmark (Aarhus)					X	X				(X)	X	X				
03 b) Denmark (Stenlille)	X	X	X	X		(X)										
03 c) Denmark (Onshore)	X	X	X	X												
04 France (Paris)									X	X	X	X	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)
05 Netherlands (Delft)					X			X		X	X					
06 Germany (Rhine/Ruhr)					X	X	X	X	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)				
07 a) Spain (Catalonia)					X	X	X	X								
07 b) Spain Iberian Basin	X	X	X	X												
08 Italy (Tuscany)					X	X			(X)		X	X				
09 Great Britain (Cornwall)					X	X	X	X								

Legend: Env = environmental, Sth = stakeholder, PoR = policy and regulations, MFR = market and financial resources.

Note: This is a rough estimate at which SEL the respective cases can be located based on the analysis. An X indicates the approximate level in each dimension. For example, an X for Stakeholder Involvement at 3 means that the SEL for stakeholder involvement is fairly developed, Brackets signify the respective dimensions overlap (e.g. the current state may be between Development and Demonstration).

4.2 Focus: the policy and regulation dimension

The policy and regulation dimension, in particular, highlights important enabling conditions. Therefore, we provide more in-depth insights, which are categorized into five sections.

1. Regulatory complexity vs. clarity

Across the nine cases, a clear tension emerges between regulatory complexity and procedural clarity. In Denmark and Austria, project developers often find themselves navigating a patchwork of overlapping statutes and permits: Denmark's elaborate regulations, while comprehensive, tend to delay approvals and dampen local political will, and in Austria the division of responsibilities among federal, provincial, and municipal bodies creates uncertainty at every turn. Switzerland illustrates this same challenge on a cantonal scale, where the federal Energy Strategy of 2050 offers strong support in theory, but its implementation varies widely from Geneva to Vaud to Eclépens. By contrast, the Netherlands and parts of Germany have managed to streamline their processes. The Dutch Mining Act and digital "one-stop" portals cut through red tape, and North Rhine-Westphalia's (NRW) unified permitting system, along with clear geothermal targets have accelerated project timelines. In Tuscany, too, a regionally tailored law and coordinated territorial planning tools have succeeded in aligning environmental controls, revenue sharing, and geological data requirements into one coherent package.

2. Devolution vs. centralization of authority

A second cross-cutting pattern concerns the balance between centralized and decentralized governance. France and Spain, with their strong national programs and funding schemes, provide clear, country-wide signals for geothermal development — even though their sometimes rigid, top-down procedures can be slow to adapt to regional circumstances. Spain's new "Geotermia Profunda" initiative and France's suite of tax credits and risk-sharing instruments demonstrate policy ambition at the center, but local uptake remains uneven. Conversely, more decentralized systems like Switzerland's canton-based approach or the UK's project-by-project licensing in Cornwall allow for tailored responses to local geology and public sentiment, but they also risk leaving gaps where supportive regions coexist alongside areas of regulatory inertia, and national strategies are not consistently implemented.

3. Embedded risk-mitigation and incentive mechanisms

Despite these structural differences, nearly all cases embed risk-mitigation and incentive mechanisms within their regulatory frameworks. Mandatory environmental and seismic monitoring is now a hallmark of best practice — from the required public participation in Dutch permits to Switzerland's six-month pre-drilling seismic station deployments. Financial de-risking tools likewise appear wherever policy is most mature: France's feed-in tariffs, the Netherlands' SDE++ and RNES subsidies, Germany's NRW.BANK insurance products, and Italy's long-standing incentives all reduce the upfront burden for investors. These mechanisms do more than just lower costs; they send a signal of political continuity and assure stakeholders that GE is here to stay.

It can also be argued that advanced modeling approaches, such as those developed in GO-Forward, could be used as eligibility criteria for insurance schemes¹⁴. Insurance for geothermal exploration phases can be made dependent on advanced modeling in the sense of adequate risk mitigation measures during (early) exploration.

¹⁴ For instance, see EGRIF: <http://www.geoelec.eu/wp-content/uploads/2011/09/D-3.2-GEOELEC-report-on-risk-insurance.pdf>.

4. Recognition & definition of geothermal as a resource

A more subtle but equally important subject is the legal recognition of GE as a distinct resource. In countries like the Netherlands, France, Germany, and Italy, GE enjoys explicit status within mining or renewable-energy legislation, granting projects privileged access to funding and clarifying subsurface rights. By contrast, in the UK's Cornwall region geothermal heat is neither formally defined nor given a dedicated licensing regime, forcing developers to negotiate planning permissions on an ad hoc basis and slowing the emergence of a coherent market.

5. General implications for geothermal exploration policy

Taken together, these lessons suggest a balanced approach to future GE policies. This approach would consolidate permitting authorities into a transparent “one-stop” framework while allowing regions to adapt processes to their specific geology and social context. It would also incorporate robust environmental and seismic monitoring and mandatory public participation milestones to foster trust. Furthermore, it would explicitly codify GE in national or regional energy laws. Finally, clear, long-term targets would be paired with financial de-risking tools to attract private capital. Combining the best elements of centralized ambition and decentralized flexibility enables new geothermal initiatives to swiftly transition from exploration to deployment within diverse communities, ultimately unlocking the heat potential beneath various landscapes.

4.3 Overall recommendations

By learning from both the “best practice” cases (e.g., such as those in the Netherlands, Germany, and Italy), as well as the “cautionary tales” (such as Austria's fragmentation, and the UK's regulatory gaps), future geothermal programs can design transparent, efficient regulatory frameworks that are tailored to local geology and communities — thereby advance the development of geothermal energy. This will accelerate the transition from early exploration to embedded full deployment. Accordingly, the following five recommendations are proposed.

1. Simplify and unify permitting by consolidating overlapping authorities into a single "one-stop shop" on the appropriate scale.
2. Incorporate mandatory early monitoring and public participation requirements to build trust and reduce seismic and environmental risks from the outset.
3. Codify geothermal energy (GE) explicitly in national and regional renewable energy laws to secure dedicated incentives and clarify subsurface rights.
4. Use risk-sharing financial instruments, such as guarantees, insurance, and feed-in tariffs, to reduce upfront cost barriers and demonstrate long-term political commitment.
5. Balance central guidance with local flexibility. Set national targets and minimum standards while empowering regions to adapt processes to geological and social contexts.

These lessons learned, Deliverable 5.2 Recommendations for communication and stakeholder engagement, which will take place in two selected case study areas, is a further step towards better understanding regarding the national, regional, and local peculiarities. The last section of this report details how this selection will be made.

4.4 Outlook for Deliverable 5.2 Recommendations for communication and stakeholder engagement

The next deliverable will focus on the stakeholder process, particularly including representatives from authorities, industry, and non-governmental organizations (according to the proposal). Decision makers will be involved in selected dialogue formats to potentially exchange information and take action to enhance the respective SRL. The goal is to increase engagement among the region, the city, and its citizens regarding geothermal energy. A central tenet of the project is assessing and enhancing societal readiness as an integral part of exploration planning and design. GO-Forward starts in the early stages of deep geothermal development by implementing advanced exploration methodologies and ensuring the accessibility and availability of relevant data. Along with the technical and economic evaluation of the developed technology, GO-Forward's recommendations for future geothermal exploration initiatives can be applied to any region. Deliverable 5.2, stakeholder engagement, is a further step toward a better understanding of national, regional, and local peculiarities. This engagement will take place in two selected case study areas. The final section of this report explains how these areas will be chosen. Please note that D5.1 was only a preliminary step and not a decision-making instrument. The final case selection will be made after Deliverable 5.1 is accepted and in preparation for Deliverable 5.2.

The case analysis revealed substantial heterogeneity in development and maturity across the four SEL dimensions and among the countries studied. Despite differences in data availability and quality, the analysis provides a robust basis for characterizing each case and guiding the selection of two cases for further investigation of stakeholder engagement for Deliverable 5.2. To ensure the methodological soundness of this selection process, we developed a set of technical and social selection criteria through a brainstorming session. At the first Annual Consortium Meeting in June 2025, colleagues refined and prioritized these criteria. The criteria are presented in Table 5, which also shows the results of the ranking exercise. Some of the criteria are more technical, while others are more social or societal.

Table 5: The ranking results from the dot voting exercise at the consortium meeting.

Criterion	Frequency
Degree of local awareness/concern regarding Geothermal	10
Awareness of the benefits of Geothermal*	10
Data available (degree of geology. Knowledge; rich/poor)	8
Expected potential (MWh, °C, ...)	5
Degree of "transferability" to similar regions in Europe #generalizable*	5
Existing infrastructure*	4
Centralized - decentralized (energy system)	3
Historical: N of failed cases	3
Degree of risk and uncertainty (from a geologic. perspective)	2
Political stability	2
Maturity level of case	1
N of existing contacts to key-agents/stakeholders (local, regional recruitment potential)	1
Degree of trust/mistrust among population/stakeholders	1
Jobs for the local people*	1
N of high-risk facilities in vicinity (nuclear power plants, mines, storage, ...)	0
Favorable business case*	0
Scale of projects (NB. Wells, drilling/production sites)*	0
Negative experiences with Geotherm (e.g. seismicity,)*	Was merged with "Historical...."

Note: * indicates criteria added by the colleagues.

The results of the ranking task indicate that awareness and benefits of, as well as concern for GE, must be considered in the selection process. From a technical and modeling perspective, data availability and geological knowledge must also be considered.

Since early exploration is central to GO-Forward, we will select two sites with poor exploration data and operational experience (low TRL). For practical reasons, stakeholder recruitment capacity will guide our choices: we may select one region with established engagement processes and strong trust ties to leverage existing networks and another region with low awareness and fragile trust dynamics to gain insight into stakeholder mobilization under contrasting conditions. To ensure that our comparative analysis captures the breadth of challenges and opportunities in geothermal deployment, we deliberately select cases that vary in terms of data availability, system characteristics, regional legacies, and stakeholder landscapes. Of course, it is impossible to have all contrasts at the same time, so the selection is based on a procedure that considers and weighs multiple criteria.

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Appendix: expert survey

<h3>GO-Forward - Case / Region that you want to focus on</h3>	
<p>Aim: Assessment of the societal readiness level on a regional scale</p> <p>Regional for us means states, several provinces and the like Size: approximately NUTS-2 region or several NUTS-3 regions combined, see below https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/overview</p>	
<p>Partner contact (you):</p> <p>Name: <i>fill-in</i></p> <p>Affiliation: <i>fill-in</i></p> <p>Email Address: <i>fill-in</i></p>	
<p>Case Study Name: <i>fill-in</i></p> <p>Case / Area definitions: <i>dropdown</i></p> <p>NUTS level <i>dropdown</i></p> <p>NUTS code <i>fill-in</i></p> <p>Case / Area phase: <i>dropdown</i></p>	
<p>Geothermal Energy in your Country</p> <p>What is your general impression of the state of geothermal energy in your country? What is the level of public acceptance in your view?</p> <div style="background-color: #e0e0e0; height: 100px;"></div>	
<p>Stakeholder View</p> <p>Why would this case be relevant from a stakeholder perspective? (a few sentences) What is the level of public acceptance in your view?</p> <div style="background-color: #e0e0e0; height: 100px;"></div>	
<p>Pros and Cons from a stakeholder perspective? (a few sentences)</p> <div style="background-color: #e0e0e0; height: 50px;"></div>	

<p>Population View</p> <p>Why would this case be relevant from a population perspective? (a few sentences) What is the level of public acceptance in your view?</p> <td style="background-color: #cccccc; height: 100px;"></td>	
<p>Pros and Cons from a population perspective? (a few sentences)</p> <td style="background-color: #cccccc; height: 100px;"></td>	